

ACT4CAP²⁷

Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

Deliverable D7.2 (D21) Communication, Dissemination and Impact Strategy and Plan, and Impact Reporting M6, M18

Topic ID	Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Commission Agricultural Policies post 2027
WORK PROGRAMME CALL	HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01 Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the Green Deal
PROJECT WEB SITE:	https://act4cap27.eu/

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FOREWORD

Task 7.2 Planning, delivery and monitoring of joint project communication, and results dissemination activities, led by POS, is a task running throughout the entire duration of the project [M1-60] and even beyond with contributions from all partners.

Being an output of Task 7.2, this deliverable D7.2 consists of two parts:

- the first part, is as submitted to the EC in month 6, describes the communication, dissemination and impact strategy of ACT4CAP27, ensuring that the foreseen project communication, results dissemination, and exploitation activities in ACT4CAP27 are appropriately and effectively undertaken by the project consortium partners, during the project implementation and beyond,
- the second part, has been first produced and to be submitted to the EC in month 18, entails the impact assessment of the COMDISS activities performed by the consortium in the first reporting period (RP1).

Aligning with the dates of annual meetings and further project reporting periods (RP2, RP3) updates of the COMDISS Impact Reporting will be produced by months 42, 60.

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Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

Deliverable D7.2 (D21) Communication, Dissemination and Impact Strategy and Plan and Reporting

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Abbreviations / Acronyms

AAM	Author Accepted Manuscript, accepted for publication
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System
APC	Article Processing Charges
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons
CCO	Central Communications Office
CDISP	Communication, Dissemination and Impact Strategy and Plan
CDET	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Team
COMDISS	Communication and dissemination
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EB	Executive Board of ACT4CAP27
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GA	Grant Agreement
GD	Green Deal
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
MS	Milestone
OA	Open Access
REA	EU Research Executive Agency
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SyGMA	System for Grant Management
VoR	Version of Record, final version of publication

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Task 7.2 Planning, delivery and monitoring of joint project communication, and results dissemination activities, led by POS, is a task running throughout the entire duration of the project [M1-60] and even beyond.

This deliverable D7.2 from Task 7.2 is produced with the purpose of ensuring that the foreseen project communication, results dissemination, and exploitation activities in ACT4CAP27 are appropriately and effectively undertaken by the project consortium partners, during the project implementation and beyond.

The document discusses key questions in the following structure:

WHY do we need project communication and results dissemination?

- Purpose, aims and objectives of this document, and key principles and obligations for project communication and dissemination in Horizon Europe projects are explained, and how we apply those in ACT4CAP27.

WHO is in charge of coordinating partner teams' communication and dissemination efforts?

- The internal arrangements for implementing the COMDISS plan: the operational cycle (plan-do-check) together with the responsibilities of the COMDISS task leader, and of partners' COMDISS Officers are described.

WHAT is the overall strategy in ACT4CAP27 for project communication, results dissemination and creating impact?

- The elements of the overall strategy are informed by the scope and expected outcomes of the topic call, and are in line with the expected results of ACT4CAP27. The strategy for impact and ACT4CAP27's success, to a great extent, is dependent on the ability of the consortium to attract policymakers' attention by being at the right place, right time and having the right fact presented in a right way needed for evidence-informed policy making.

WHOM do we target project messages?

- Main target audiences, nature and means of their engagement in ACT4CAP27, key project messages per target audience, as well as the initial list of international/national/regional target audiences identified for reaching out by project partners with project information are described.

HOW do we deliver COMDISS activities?

- Best practices in using communication channels responsibly and elements of the project's distinct visual identity are presented, followed by a description of the various forms of communication channels, materials, and different modes of dissemination including using EC services, collaboration with other projects, and ACT4CAP27's final conference.

WHEN do we deliver COMDISS activities?

- The 1 to 3 planning Intervals of communication and dissemination activities in ACT4CAP27 are aligned with the timing of project reporting periods (RP1 in month 18, RP2 in month 42, RP3 in month 60) and beyond (Interval 4). We describe the changing focus of

project communication and, in particular, of results dissemination throughout the different phases of the project.

How do we **document, monitor, evaluate, and report** COMDISS activities?

- The COMDISS plan and strategy is operationalised and regularly monitored throughout the whole project duration and beyond with participation of all project partners. This section presents the monitoring procedures and requirements of documenting COMDISS activities that are in place within the consortium and the key performance indicators that are used for the impact evaluation of ACT4CAP27 COMDISS actions – all this in a structure and format that helps best informing the project’s continuous reporting in the EC’s SyGMA grant management system.

The COMDISS Impact Reporting part of this deliverable will be first produced in month 18 and will entail the impact assessment of the COMDISS activities performed by the consortium in the first reporting period (RP1). Aligning with the dates of annual meetings and further project reporting periods (RP2, RP3) updates of the COMDISS Impact Reporting will be produced by months 42, 60.

A closely related deliverable to D7.2 is the development of the **Exploitation Plan** (D7.3). The planning and preparations for exploitation activities are carried out in Task 7.3 led by POS and ECORYS and WR, with participation of all partners. The Exploitation Plan (D7.3) aims to create conditions for influencing strategic policy planning, based on project outcomes; maximising the exploitation potential of project activities, findings and outputs for ongoing economic, environmental and social benefits and supporting the use and benefit from the outcomes during and beyond the project’s lifetime.

Task 7.2 through massive and multichannel distribution of contents, as well as Task 7.3 having started up in month 1 with the iterative development of the Exploitation Strategy and Plan, are to **ensure effective dissemination, exploitation and user uptake of the ACT4CAP27 project results** in order to strengthen the overall impact of the project. Both Tasks run in parallel with the other WPs over the project’s lifetime and focus on defining a comprehensive and consistent project dissemination and exploitation strategy, that ensure maximum project visibility and the sustainability of its results during and beyond the lifetime of the project.

1. WHY?

1.1. Purpose, aims and objectives

This deliverable on **Communication, Dissemination and Impact Strategy and Plan (CDISP)** is produced with the purpose of ensuring that the foreseen **project communication, results dissemination, and exploitation activities** in ACT4CAP27 **are appropriately planned and effectively undertaken by the project consortium partners**, during the course of the project and beyond. As a result, the ACT4CAP27 consortium can create significant impacts and project legacy by help contributing to meeting the following specific needs:

- Improved analytical capacity and tools able to assess short-and long-term impacts of future EU agri-food policies (e.g. GD, CAP post 2027) on food systems in EU. (WP2,3,5)
- Future agricultural policies and strategies that support the EU agricultural sector in achieving environmental, social (including health) and economic targets required by the Green Deal. (WP1,6)
- Boosting the agricultural modelling capacity, biophysical as well as socio-economic, of EU member states and associated countries. (WP2,3,4,5)
- Recommendations for future agricultural policies in the EU Europe post 2027 and policy evaluation. (WP1,6)
- Stronger EU science-policy interfaces to achieve sustainable food system goals. (WP4,7)
- Better informed decision-making processes, stakeholder engagement and governance innovation. (WP5,7)

This document 1) analyses target groups for the creation of impacts, 2) identifies key messages and channels most appropriate for engagement and communications, external partners with whom to cooperate on co-dissemination, 3) provides a visual identity and templates for project communications, 4) establish project partners' responsibilities and timelines, guidelines on approaches to communication, requirements for continuous monitoring and reporting of project communications, in compliance with Open access.

The specific objectives of project communication and results dissemination in ACT4CAP27 include:

- maximizing visibility and create awareness of the project to target groups and the public at large;
- sharing information about the project, including challenging problems and solutions;
- sharing information about the potential of ACT4CAP27 Services in support of bringing evidence-based policy decisions;
- maximizing the uptake of the project results to reach a wide number of representative ACT4CAP27 stakeholders;
- organizing synergies and collaborations with ongoing projects and initiatives in the field;

- supporting and enhancing all scientific dissemination of the project outcomes during and after the project;
- integrating the project's findings into the broader European context.

For a glossary on how we understand in this document, key terms related to communication and dissemination see **Appendix 1**.

1.2. Continuity and document maintenance, related deliverable

Planning, delivery and monitoring of joint project communication, and results dissemination activities are undertaken in Task 7.2, that is running throughout the whole duration of the project, with participation of all partners. In Task 7.2 this deliverable establishes the individual partner responsibilities, timelines, guidelines and suggestions for project communication and result dissemination, under continuous monitoring of the WP7 T7.2 task leader POS.

The COMDISS Impact Reporting part of this deliverable will be first produced in month 18 and will entail the impact assessment of the COMDISS activities performed by the consortium in the first reporting period (RP1). Aligning with the dates of annual meetings and further project reporting periods (RP2, RP3, RP4) updates of the COMDISS Impact Reporting will be produced by months 36, 48, 60. These updates are to include an evaluation of the extent and impact of the dissemination and communication activities and materials performed by consortium partners, where available and possible.

A closely related deliverable to D7.2 is the development of the **Exploitation Plan** (D7.3). The planning and preparations for exploitation activities are carried out in Task 7.3 led by POS and ECORYS and WR, with participation of all partners. Planning exploitation activities is a progressive, iterative process coordinated by the Exploitation Team and with participation of all partners, co-developed with stakeholders. The approach builds on the experience of project partners in exploiting research into impacts for policy, including previous H2020 and Horizon Europe projects (e.g. BrightSpace, MIND STEP, SUPREMA). Along with the emergence of technical deliverables from month 9 onwards, a set of draft key exploitable results will be identified for each WP, and their potential assessed by expert inputs from the Project Advisory Group and the project teams. Exploitation workshops will be organised at project meetings. The Exploitation Plan (D7.3) aims to create conditions for influencing strategic policy planning, based on project outcomes; maximising the exploitation potential of project activities, findings and outputs for ongoing economic, environmental and social benefits and supporting the use and benefit from the outcomes during and beyond the project's lifetime.

Task 7.2 through massive and multichannel distribution of contents, as well as Task 7.3 having started up in month 1 with the iterative development of the Exploitation Strategy and Plan, are to **ensure effective dissemination, exploitation and user uptake of the ACT4CAP27 project results** in order to strengthen the overall impact of the project. Both Tasks run in parallel with the other WPs over the project's lifetime and focus on defining a comprehensive and consistent project dissemination and exploitation strategy, that ensure maximum project visibility and the sustainability of its results during and beyond the lifetime of the project.

1.3. Project communication and dissemination principles and obligations for Horizon Europe projects

As a point of reference, in this section the generic EC communication and dissemination principles obligations and requirements per se are summarised, that are considered during the elaboration of the ACT4CAP27 COMDISS Strategy.

1.3.1. Concepts of Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation & Impact

Understanding the concepts behind communication, dissemination and exploitation helps creating successful and targeted action plans. The differences in objective, focus and target audience are explained in **Error! Reference source not found.** and **Error! Reference source not found.**

For a glossary on how we understand in this document further key terms related to communication and dissemination, see **Appendix 1**.

Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation	
Reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of EU-funded R&I activities, e.g. by addressing and providing possible solutions to fundamental societal challenges.	Transfer knowledge & results with the aim to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximising the impact of EU-funded research.	Effectively use project results through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes aiming to turn R&I actions into concrete value and impact for society.	 Objective
Inform about and promote the project AND its results/success.	Describe and ensure results available for others to USE → focus on results only!	Make concrete use of research results (not restricted to commercial use.)	 Focus
Multiple audiences beyond the project's own community incl. media and the broad public.	Audiences that may take an interest in the potential USE of the results (e.g. scientific community, industrial partner, policymakers).	People/organisations including project partners themselves that make concrete use of the project results, as well as user groups outside the project.	 Target Audience

Figure 1 Differences in objective, focus and target audience explained, EC 2021

Figure 2 The concepts of communication, dissemination and exploitation explained, EC 2021

1.3.2. Partners' contractual obligations related to COM-DISS-EXPL

Partners' contractual obligations related to project communication, results dissemination and exploitation are set out in [REGULATION \(EU\) 2021/695](#) containing the rules for participation in Horizon Europe, and the Grant Agreement of the ACT4CAP27 project. We list here the relevant articles to which we refer in the next section when describing the requirements. Exploitation related obligations will be detailed in Deliverable 7.3 Exploitation Plan.

Rules for Participation

- Article 39: Exploitation and Dissemination
- Article 40: Transfer and Licensing
- Article 41: Access Rights

ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Grant Agreement

- Article 16: Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) – Background and Results – Access Rights and Rights of Use
- Article 17: Communication, Dissemination & Visibility
- Annex 5 Specific Rules: No specific communication, dissemination and visibility rules have been set in the case of the ACT4CAP27 project.

1.3.3. EC requirements related to communication and dissemination measures

1.3.3.1. Communication and visibility

Communication and visibility are important parts of all EU programmes including Horizon Europe. Since the EU grants are financed by public funds, EU Beneficiaries are generally expected to actively engage in communication activities, to promote the projects and to publicly acknowledge the EU support.

“Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), in accordance with Annex 1 and in a strategic, coherent and effective manner.” (GA Article 17.1).

Why do we communicate?

- ✓ Attract the best experts to our team
- ✓ Share best practices with others
- ✓ Promote our project’s activities and results
- ✓ Trigger new collaborations & opportunities
- ✓ Generate market demand for the products or services developed
- ✓ Increases the visibility of your research/business, enhances your reputation
- ✓ Opens up other funding sources and business opportunities by explaining how your project successfully tackles current issues and challenges
- ✓ Raise citizens’ awareness of how their money is spent
- ✓ Show the success of European collaboration

Every EU programme implements the **EU political priorities**. It is important that we link back to these priorities in our communication activities, so that we show the citizens the big picture and how the ACT4CAP27 project contributes to this.

Furthermore, all our communication measures shall:

- be adequate to promote the project and its findings throughout the **full lifespan** of the project;
- be strategically planned with **clear objectives**;
- clearly define the main **message, tool(s) and channel(s)** that is be used to reach out to target groups;
- promote the project and its results **beyond the project’s own community**;
- communicate the research in a way that is **understood by non-specialists**, e.g. the media and the public.

Going digital (website, videos, social media, newsletters, factsheets) and building networks (events, project and expert meetings, reaching out to the media) are preferred ways of communication encouraged by the EC.

Our communication strategy and efforts into communication shall be proportionate to the scale of our project.

In ACT4CAP27:

- through our strategy and operations, we fully comply with the “why and how to communicate” principles above.

1.3.3.2. Visibility and acknowledgement of EU funding

All recipients of EU funding have a **general obligation** to acknowledge the origin and ensure the visibility of any EU funding received (see Article 17.2 of the Horizon Europe grant agreement: Visibility - European flag and funding statement).

Beneficiaries of EU funding must display the EU flag and funding statement ("Funded by the European Union" or "Co-funded by the European Union") in all their communication and dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result results funded by the grant.

The EU flag (emblem) and funding statement must be displayed in a way that is easily visible for the public and with sufficient prominence on all printed and digital products, websites, social media channels and other communication products. EU funding must moreover be acknowledged in all types of public outputs (including patent applications, EU standardisation of results), media contacts and other public statements.

The funding statement “Funded by the European Union” should always be spelled out in full and placed next to the emblem. The emblem and the statement must not be separated.

The funding statement can be added in local languages, where appropriate, and can be displayed in two different languages in the case of a bilingual local context.

IMPORTANT! The EU Commission’s logo must not be used when acknowledging the EU funding.

Official guidance and download the EU emblem:

- [Download centre for EU emblem and the funding statement](#)
- [Use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes 2021-2027](#)

In ACT4CAP27 :

- generally all templates comply with this general obligation of visibility and acknowledgement of funding (the Visual Identity Guide in **Appendix 5.**)
- for other, specific cases partners can reach the official visuals from the ACT4CAP27 Sharepoint site:

Funded by European Union logos available from the ACT4CAP27 SharePoint

Documents > General > WP7 > T7-2 > 01 Logos-Templates-VIG > [04 Funded-by-EU-logos-rules](#)

The details of how we apply this requirement in ACT4CAP27 are detailed in the Visual Identity Guide in **Appendix 5**.

1.3.3.3. Involve the EU when communicating

Before engaging in a communication or dissemination activity expected to have a major media impact, beneficiaries must inform the granting authority. (GA Article 17.1).

In ACT4CAP27:

- the Coordinator is to inform the granting authority (REA project officer), upon approval of the Executive Board of WP leaders.

1.3.3.4. The EU has the right to use our communication material

The European Union has the right to use communication material produced and owned by the recipients of EU funding. This right is granted in the form of a royalty-free, non-exclusive and irrevocable licence. The cost of this licence can be covered by EU funding. The ownership of the material remains with the recipients of the EU funding (GA Article 16.3).

1.3.3.5. Eligibility of costs related to communication and visibility

Any expenditure related to communication and visibility is part of the action and can benefit from EU funding.

Financial reductions for non-compliance: there may be financial reductions in case of non-respect of the requirements. If recipients of EU funding breach any of their contractual obligations, the EU's financial contribution may be reduced.

1.3.3.6. Open Access Mandate to publications

Beneficiaries must ensure **OA to peer-reviewed scientific publications** relating to their results. In particular, **they must ensure:**

- at the latest upon publication, **deposition** of the AAM or VoR in a trusted repository + **immediate open access via the repository** under **CC BY** or equivalent (CC BY-NC/CC BY-ND are allowed for long-text formats e.g. monographs; a chapter in an edited book is not eligible),
- **information** via the repository about any research output/tools/instruments needed to **validate the conclusions of the scientific publication**.

Horizon Europe Open Access Mandate

Source: https://www.openaire.eu/images/Guides/HorizonEurope_OA_mandate_graphic.png

Figure 3 Horizon Europe open access mandate to publications explained

Beneficiaries (or authors) **must retain sufficient intellectual property rights** to comply with the OA requirements (i.e. no Copyright Transfer Agreement).

There are no restrictions on where to publish, but **publication fees are reimbursable only if publishing venue is full open access** (publication fees in hybrid journals are not covered).

The publisher copyrights and open access achieving policies of journals can be checked in the online resource Sherpa Romeo: www.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo

For more details on how to comply, which repository to use, how to retain your copyright, are publication costs supported please consult OpenAIRE’s Guide on [How to comply with the Horizon Europe mandate for publications](#).

- <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-comply-with-horizon-europe-mandate-for-publications>

or watch the video by OpenAIRE on Horizon Europe Open Science requirements in practice

- https://youtu.be/t_ok3Jyk7cl

For a quick guide on Creative Commons (CC) licenses visit

- <https://www.wur.nl/en/article/What-are-Creative-Commons-licenses.htm>

1.3.3.6.1. *Open Science strategy in ACT4CAP27*

Open access sharing and non-commercial exploitation: ACT4CAP27 aims to make tools, data and output fully open access, following the Horizon Europe principles of Open Science to scientific publications and data. Permitting certain licenses to software (e.g. commercial solvers) and data (e.g. commercial datasets or confidential micro-data), code of models and tools are to be made accessible through code repositories (e.g. GitHub and GitLab) and data will be published on open data repositories (e.g. Zenodo). For further arrangements on data management see Deliverable 8.2 Data management Plan.

1.3.3.6.2. *Strategy in ACT4CAP27 for avoiding predatory journals and conferences*

Digitisation, online publishing, rapid communication and open access models have revolutionised the way scientific results are presented in many ways and have also had an impact on the criteria system for the acceptance of publications. The positive consequences of the new publishing methods include, for example, greater visibility and easier access to scientific results, faster peer review and publication, and the involvement of a wider peer reviewer circle. However, the downside of these changes is that a number of new unethical behaviours has also emerged, which can significantly distort a healthy research environment, that is, a science which is predominantly based on peer review. One of these new distortions is the emergence and proliferation of “predatory” (or “parasitic”) journals.

The InterAcademy Partnership aimed to identify such unethical practices by conducting an international survey in 2020, the results of which were published in 2022 ([Combatting Predatory Academic Journals and Conferences](#)). In their report, they formulated recommendations on possible actions to be taken against predatory journals and conferences for the research community, universities, academies, research funders, publishers, libraries and conference organisers.

In ACT4CAP27 :

- we put in place of compulsory notification of article title, authors and journal title to the Board of WP Leaders from any partner(s) before starting any publishing procedures (also see Section 5.2.2.6);
- it is the respective COMDISS Officers of partners who are to check whether the journal they intend to publish in is predatory;
- guidelines and recommendations of the following websites are to be followed:
 - **IAP report;**
 - Erasmus University Library page on [Publication strategies & Open Access: Watch out for predatory journals and publishers](#)
 - UNESCO’s [Open Science Toolkit](#) – in particular the [Factsheet on Identifying predatory journals and conferences](#)
 - the [Think.Check.Submit](#) initiative aims to educate researchers, promote integrity and build trust in credible research and publications
 - [Think. Check. Attend](#) guides researchers and scholars to judge the legitimacy and academic credentials of conferences

- ISSN (International Standard Serial Number) is an identifier that uniquely identifies journals and publishers. It is therefore always a good idea to check whether the ISSN is listed in the [ISSN register](#).
- [DOAJ](#) (Directory of Open Access Journals) is an indexing service that provides information on open access journals. Indexing in DOAJ is a certain indication of the openness and credibility of a journal.
- [COPE](#) (Committee on Publication Ethics) is an organization where journals and publishers agree to abide by ethical guidelines issued by COPE. If a journal or publisher is a member, it is a good sign that they are following the highest standards of legitimate publishing.
 - If you want to check ISSN, DOAJ and COPE information at once, we recommend using the [Predatory publishing ISSN Check website](#).

Further recommended websites:

- [CoARA](#);
- [DORA](#);
- [Leiden Manifesto](#);
- [ALLEA](#). ([ALLEA STATEMENT](#) on curbing predatory practices in open access scholarly publishing)

2. WHO? - INTERNAL ARRANGEMENTS

Effective external project communication and results dissemination requires the **active engagement of all project partners in COMDISS activities**, in order to help collecting and formulating all pieces of information during the project’s technical implementation that could be of interest to ACT4CAP27 stakeholder audiences, thereby **help building and assessing the multi-channel public storyboard documentation of project activities and results**.

Communication, dissemination and exploitation in ACT4CAP27 draws on the experience of partners in the creation of impact for EC and national, regional policy and regulatory or managing authorities, professional, scientific and public audiences. **All project partners** are involved in project communication and results dissemination and exploitation, in order **to foster awareness and transfer results for impact, not only within their own countries but in the whole territory of the EU**, as much as possible.

Each partner in ACT4CAP27 is responsible for the dissemination and communication of the project results **in their respective country** and for liaising closely with stakeholders and stakeholder media that could be interested in and/or benefit from project findings.

With one representative of each partner (plus a nominated substitute), called COM-DISS Officers (**Error! Reference source not found.**), a specific **Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Team** (COM-DISS-EXPL Team, CDET) has been set up early in the project to 1) enable the deployment and implementation of the Communication, Dissemination and Impact Strategy and Plan (CDISP) at the partners’ level, and 2) facilitate the continuous documentation, progress monitoring and evaluation of COMDISS actions, realised by project partners.

Table 1 List of COMDISS Officers and their substitutes

Nr	Partner/ WP representation	COMDISS Officer and nominated substitutes	Nr	Partner/ WP representation	COMDISS Officer and nominated substitutes
1	WR / WP1, WP8	Marjan Vooijs, Siemen van Berkum	8	PNU	Olga Nykolyuk, Oleksandr Rozhkov
2	THÜNEN / WP6	Verena Laquai, Davit Stepanyan	9	UNIROMA3	Cristina Vaquero Pineiro, Luca Salvatici
3	EUROCARE	David Schaefer, Peter Witzke	10	ECORYS / WP7	Elena Feo, Bérénice Dupeux
4	IIASA / WP4	<i>not yet appointed</i>	11	POS	Katalin Balazs
5	SLU / WP3	<i>not yet appointed</i>	12	UCL / WP2	<i>not yet appointed</i>
6	UPM / WP5	Alberto Usero, Maria Blanco	13	JRC	Caetano Beber, Thomas Fellmann
7	WU	Jack Peerlings, Monica Sartorius Riveiro			

2.1. Responsibilities of POS as COMDISS task leader

POS with ECORYS are the task leaders for T7.2. POS is responsible for:

- initialising the setting up of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Team (CDET);

- drafting and editing D7.2: Communication, Dissemination, Impact Strategy and Plan, and the reporting part in its subsequent updates in months 18, 42 and 60;
- setting up, maintaining and monitoring the performance of ACT4CAP27's central channels for external communication, including the project website, project e-newsletter, social media channels (Twitter and LinkedIn), YouTube, and the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community;
- operating the virtual ACT4CAP27 External Communications Office (ECO). The ECO acts as a central point for receiving, transforming and sharing information on project implementation and results. It:
 - receives information from COMDISS Officers (in particular from partners with WP/Task leading roles),
 - transforms incoming information into communication messages with assistance of concerned COMDISS Officers (and through them with concerned WP/Task leaders),
 - keeps a “live diary” at the ACT4CAP27 central communication channels about the ongoing project processes and emerging results from the project, based on inputs from COMDISS Officers of partners with WP/Task leading roles,
 - shares information among all COMDISS Officers to be communicated through partners' communication channels to external audiences, thereby supporting multiplication effects in reaching target audiences;
- organising 6-monthly COMDISS meetings for the CDET to report the work carried out and discuss timely actions to be performed;
- collecting and summarizing partners' COMDISS reports, to supply information into periodic technical reports, and updates of D7.2 about the levels and success of COMDISS performance at the consortium level, based on the established Key Performance Indicators.

2.2. Responsibilities of COMDISS Officers

Each project partner's COMDISS Officers support the ACT4CAP27 External Communications Office with:

- coordinating the continuous implementation of the CDISP at the partner team level, this means:
 - a. **acting as a multiplier** to ensure a large uptake of the project results by translating project results and presentations for the dissemination to the national actors and stakeholders, and beyond as appropriate, through the partner's own communication channels, including echoes of ACT4CAP27 press releases and website news items, retweets. COMDISS Officers are required to keep continuous contact with their institution's central communication specialists and supply them with ACT4CAP27 related news/communications, either created in the project centrally by the ECO or together with the respective partner. COMDISS Officers are encouraged to improve central messages with locally relevant contexts, as appropriate.
 - b. **mediating COM-DISS-EXPL related information between the Partner's research team and POS** as central point for the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Team. COMDISS Officers are required to provide timely information to the

ECO about planned COMDISS related activities of the Partner's research team members, such as participating and representing ACT4CAP27 (e.g. giving presentation or having poster) at events, including conferences, workshops, exhibitions, local interview and media appearances etc.

- documenting appropriately by keeping records and proofs of partner level COMDISS activities, and **providing quarterly progress reports** on partner level COMDISS actions; thereby being contributor to and reviewer for the reporting part of D7.2 in its subsequent updates in months 18, 36, 48 and 60;
- **participating at the 6-monthly COMDISS meetings** to report the work carried out at partner level and discuss timely actions to be performed.

2.3. Additional responsibilities of COMDISS Officers of partners with research WP/Task leading roles

Project implementation broken down into thematic work packages and tasks, are key sources of information about ongoing project processes and emerging results.

To ensure the continuous information harvest for project external communications, COMDISS Officers of partners with WP/Task leading roles are required to cooperate within each work package, and between related work packages.

COMDISS Officers of partners with WP/Task leading roles (thereafter: WP/Task COMDISS Officers) are in the immediate position to identify ongoing project activities and results at their respective WP/Task level that are of concern for external communications and dissemination.

Apart from roles mentioned in Section 2.2 ***COMDISS Officers of partners with WP leading roles*** are required:

- to ***monitor their WP in concern for identifying project activities and results that can provide a basis for news items***, suitable to be published through the project's central communication channels, and those of partners;
- to assist in documenting those activities for external communications by ***writing up short draft news items and supplying a relevant photo*** if possible, and submit these to the ECO for further handling;
- to discuss those drafts with ***WP leaders and get their approval*** before submitting to the ECO.

Apart from roles mentioned in Section 2.2 ***COMDISS Officers of partners with research Task leading roles*** are required:

- to ***monitor their research Task in concern*** for identifying project activities and results that can provide a basis for news items,
- to ***support the WP COMDISS Officer*** with identification of, documenting those activities, results and drafting news items.

2.4. Overview of operating COMDISS in ACT4CAP27

Operating COMDISS in ACT4CAP27 is based on the plan-do-check cycle, as described Figure 4.

Figure 4 Operating COMDISS in ACT4CAP27

3. WHAT? – OVERALL STRATEGY FOR COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND IMPACT

The overall strategy for stakeholder engagement, capacity building, communication, dissemination and impact is to:

1. **increase awareness of** the short-medium and long term **ACT4CAP27 policy scenarios and policy recommendations** in Europe amongst regulators, policy makers and programme operators, through co-learning, co-development and co-implementation;
2. **motivate key stakeholders and decision-makers** at different levels to support adoption of novel ACT4CAP27 Modular Toolbox boosting the economic and environmental impact modelling of agri-food models, through project communication (e.g. technical and policy briefs) and through the Stakeholder Platform (liaising with the EC, knowledge exchange through policy-science interface) and capacity building (e.g. e-trainings) and peer-to-peer events (e.g. workshops, demonstrations);
3. **help boosting analytical and modelling capacities in agriculture** in the EU and Associated Countries via trainings, knowledge and innovation transfer to reinforce AKIS;
4. **help facilitate communications and reiterate synergies** between ACT4CAP27 and other projects funded through and referenced in the Call Topic and across other relevant EU funded and national projects.

Communication campaigns are fully aligned with project activities, milestones and deliverables, see Section 6.

Effective dissemination and exploitation are at the core of ACT4CAP27 to support the expected results and project outcomes in Table 2.

Table 2 Expected results and outcomes in ACT4CAP27

Expected results	Outcomes
Novel food systems framework, indicators (holistic) and gap analysis to guide development of agri-food models (D1.1, D1.2)	More informed and engaged stakeholders through the ACT4CAP27 Data and Modelling Portal for user-friendly access to key results
Modular Toolbox for Sustainable Food System Policy Modelling to support agricultural modelling capacity of EU member states (D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4, D5.1, D5.3)	ACT4CAP27 Modular Toolbox boosting the economic and environmental impact modelling of agri-food models
Assessment of potential future agri-food policy options able to bridge the gap between current unsustainable food systems and targeted long term sustainable food systems. (D1.2, D3.4, D6.1)	ACT4CAP27 Stakeholder validated Baseline and alternative policy futures
Monitoring and projecting environmental, social (including health) and economic indicators of the EU food system. (D1.1, D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, D3.1, D3.3)	4 Integrated Assessment Modelling teams adopt ACT4CAP27 models informing pathway chapters of future IPCC reports
New generation of agri-food system modelers and EU wide community of model practitioners (M5.1, M5.2)	Increased capacity of modelling community and network partners through trained PhDs and summer school students;
Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform that brings together food system experts and EU modellers and analysts providing them with an open access to the ACT4CAP27 Portal via cloud-	ACT4CAP27 Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform

Expected results	Outcomes
based solutions and interactive dashboards. (D4.1, D7.1, D7.2)	
Impact of agricultural policy analysis on performance of the EU food system will be fostered through a programme of engagement with key stakeholders by project partners at regional, country and EU levels. (D5.2, D7.1, D7.1)	Additional research institutes in and outside of the consortium, as well as JRC use ACT4CAP27 models for policy assessments
ACT4CAP27 Interactive Roadmap with transition narratives and pathways to achieve medium- to long-term sustainable food systems in the EU. (D6.2)	ACT4CAP27 Interactive Roadmap widely disseminated via final and scientific conferences, stakeholder workshops, and meetings with the EU DGs.

Contents and recommendations are to be refined following sharing draft materials with target audiences in policy, practice and science in the final stages of the project (e.g. stakeholder workshops at project meetings, discussions with the Project Advisory Group, scientific conferences)

The strategy for impact and its success is largely dependent on the ability of the consortium to attract policymakers’ attention by being at the right place, right time and having the right fact presented in a right way needed for evidence-informed policy making.

Trust and credibility are key to the long-term development of a policy network through informal (e.g. policy briefs, research reports, maintaining databases, presentations, reviews) and formal (e.g. policy workshops) ways.

The types of project results expected in ACT4CAP27 are highlighted in yellow in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Types of project results expected in ACT4CAP27

4. TO WHOM? – AUDIENCES, TARGET GROUPS, KEY MESSAGES

The ACT4CAP27 consortium has identified the following categories of stakeholders, taking into account the geography of their interests (e.g. Europe-wide, EU, national, regional), and purposes of information exchanges (e.g. influence, adoption, originating ideas and identifying concerns, training and education, information, provision, feedback, dissemination).

Through the integration of different interests, science can sketch out different paths or courses of action for policy makers. ACT4CAP27’s main target audiences, nature and means of engagement are summarised in Table 3. The key project messages per target audience are described in detail in **Appendix 2**.

Table 3 Main target audiences, nature and means of engagement in ACT4CAP27

Target audience	Description of engagement	Mechanisms for engagement
European, level policy makers and decision-makers	Project contributions to events hosted by EU or associated groups (e.g. EU R&I Days; DG Agri Innovation series) sharing findings for design of measures in policies post-2027 to decision-makers responsible for policies in agriculture (e.g. AGRI, ENV, CLIMA, SANTE, JRC, EU CAP network), strategy teams (e.g. EC European Strategy and Policy Analysis System (ESPAS), analysis and research team supporting the European Council and the Council of the European Union), and committees to promote the science-policy dialogue.	Contacts facilitated by the Project Policy Officer/Project Officer. ACT4CAP27 knowledge synthesis Policy Information event with DG AGRI (online/in Brussels), Methodological briefs; Sharing knowledge, through the stakeholder reference group, knowledge base on project website and repositories, e-newsletters, social media, event attendance (online & face-to-face) invited presentations at Final conference, video interviews for online podcasts.
Members of European Parliament (MEP) and research staff	Engagement through presentations and events with relevant intergroups [IG9-04, IG9-08] and contributions to MEP events.	Targeted ACT4CAP27 leaflets, website and e-newsletters, social media, event attendance (online and face-to-face); invitations to speak at final conference.
National and regional policy makers	Policy-makers and decision makers at national and regional levels (e.g. government departments, public agencies) responsible for CAP planning	Targeted ACT4CAP27 leaflets with outcomes translated to national languages of project partners, website and e-newsletters, social media, event attendance (online and face-to-face); final conference.
EU initiatives and projects, scientific community, academia	Uptake of methodologies and multiplication of information through science-business-policy networks, think-tanks; Scientists external to project providing feedback, sharing knowledge and using ACT4CAP27 outputs in development of research.	Participation in joint events. Peer reviewed, disseminated in scientific papers and conferences, methodological briefs, deliverable reports on project website, Open Access data (Zenodo), and promoted by social media, project newsletters
Agri food sector representatives, national	Up- and downstream in value chains, industry associations, food retail and input suppliers’ representing	Dissemination events, showcasing activities, video interviews, project

Target audience	Description of engagement	Mechanisms for engagement
stakeholders	organizations, agricultural cooperatives, food quality scheme representatives, AKIS, advisory services, education and training promote the science-practice dialogue.	newsletters, summary on key outcomes translated to national languages of project partners, sharing knowledge among AKIS stakeholder representatives, promoted through social media and website
General public	Consumer groups and representatives of communities to promote science-society dialogue attending (online) events or accessing information	Project leaflet, project website, e-newsletters, social media, online public lectures and podcasts, media appearances, popular articles, citizen engagement.

Important target audiences for the COMDISS activities are:

- 1) EC and its agencies, international bodies and government representatives**, tailoring findings for design of measures in policies and mechanisms post-2027;
- 2) Local, regional and national governments, policymakers and technical staff, regulatory and managing authorities, regional planning authorities** to participate in the capacity building and knowledge sharing activities;
- 3) Scientific community** in disciplines relevant to policies dealing with agriculture and related natural resources, food and international trade in economics, social and natural sciences, climate change adaptation, biodiversity, rural development and landscape planning;
- 4) Agricultural sectors, environmental organisations and public at large**, to communicate in laymen's terms what are the benefits and how ACT4CAP27 contributes to generating knowledge and tools for reshaping Europe's agri-food systems for sustainability.

5. HOW?

5.1. Best practices in using communication channels responsibly

It is important that partners in the ACT4CAP27 consortium have a commitment to using all forms of spoken, written and digital communication (including social media and networking sites) responsibly.

Forms of unacceptable, unprofessional or unlawful communication include (but are not limited to):

- sharing confidential information inappropriately;
- posting pictures of people without their consent;
- expressing personal opinion related to policies or target groups;
- encouraging violence or self-harm; and
- inciting hatred or discrimination.

ACT4CAP27 project partners are required to adhere to best practices at all times.

ACT4CAP27 project partners have a responsibility to ensure that they declare any conflict of interest regarding materials that they post on social media, including financial or commercial dealings.

5.2. Communication activities / channels and modes of dissemination

ACT4CAP27 uses a wide range of communications tools and dissemination channels to promote the project and its findings. They are designed to enable reach to audiences at international (i.e. beyond Europe), European (EU, institutions, Member and non-Member States, Associated Countries), national and regional levels.

5.2.1. Visual identity

The Visual Identity Guide has been designed to ensure that throughout the 5 years of operation of the ACT4CAP27 project, the members of the project consortium prepare their communication materials in a coherent way. This manual includes rules for the use of the visual identity of the project in communication, which are aimed at promoting the ACT4CAP27 project.

These visual identity guidelines are in line with the obligations of beneficiaries regarding information and communication and dissemination measures included in Articles 16 and 17 of the Grant Agreement Nr. 101134874. For details of the Visual Identity Guide see **Appendix 5**.

5.2.2. COMDISS materials and publications

5.2.2.1. Project flyer

The ACT4CAP27 flyer is an A4 sized online and printed information material. The printable version is two-page U fold format, while the online version is displayed as a flipbook. It provides brief information document written in clearly understood language, containing an overview of the objectives, the work plan, expected results and participants. It is designed in a layout suitable to conveying its message effectively, to be read quickly, and understood by all target groups interested in the project.

The ACT4CAP27 flyer may be produced in relevant national languages of the consortium upon need, and used for distribution to public audiences, at scientific meetings, and among relevant stakeholders. In prospective years of the project, newer issues of the flyer will contain summaries of major findings, achievements, and specific policy recommendations will be produced tailored to target audiences (see in section 5.2.2.5 on policy briefs). All flyers will be available in electronic format for download from the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community page: <https://zenodo.org/communities/act4cap27-eu-project/>

5.2.2.2. ACT4CAP27 generic poster, digital backdrop and roll-up

A generic ACT4CAP27 poster is designed to provide basic information about the project, including the financial support from the EU. This poster, in an editable form, also serves as a customizable template for partners to create specific posters on project activities and results for dissemination events.

One specimen of physical roll-up poster is produced for the Coordinator: serving as backdrop for dissemination events.

In other cases when the logistics of a physical roll-up poster is uneasy to the venues of on-site events across the consortium and to reduce the environmental footprint of the project, a digital backdrop is used, aligned to the project's visual identity, and customized for the respective event.

5.2.2.3. Project document templates

ACT4CAP27 consortium partners are provided with a Word document template, Word deliverable report template, Excel template and PowerPoint template to ensure a standardised presentation of project documentation, with a unique visual identity throughout the project's lifetime. The templates are made available at the WR Coordinating Team's ACT4CAP27 SharePoint system.

5.2.2.4. E-Newsletter and information notes

An email will be sent to newsletter subscribers and partner's networks at 6-monthly intervals inviting them to read our visually appealing electronic newsletter. It will include the latest news from the topic area, with links to read more and orient traffic to the project website, project progress, events and results, as well as serving as a platform for the exchange of good practices and networking with other projects, working on other topics of relevance. Utilising a database of contacts, the management of which complies with relevant data protection regulations, the newsletter invitation is e-mailed to interested parties, with an automatic free subscription available, also regularly promoted on the project's social media channels.

Newsletters will be available in a flipbook format on the project website <https://act4cap27.eu/newsletters/> and in pdf format for download from the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community page: <https://zenodo.org/communities/act4cap27-eu-project/>

The 1st newsletter is planned to be published in autumn 2024.

Information notes in the later stages of the project will provide synoptic information in easy-to-understand language, translated into local languages as needed, and agreed with partners and the Project Advisory Board. *E-briefs* targeted at different audiences will be used to convey key findings in open-access format, available from the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community site.

5.2.2.5. Policy briefs

For writing up ACT4CAP27 policy briefs, we take the following definition and recommendations of the [EC JRC's Course book on The practice of informing policy through evidence](#).

Policy briefs are documents reflecting the “state-of-the-art scientific knowledge” for a given policy issue. They are short, concise documents written in a style making the messages easily accessible to a non-scientific community with an ultimate goal to prompt change.

Key elements of a policy brief are:

- 2 pages long, 800 words maximum;
- a short, neutral summary of what is known about a particular issue or problem;
- a vehicle for providing policy advice / designed to facilitate decision-making;
- evidence-based;
- ‘news’ and evidence + it offers practical solutions/options/recommendations;
- easy to understand without specialised knowledge or additional reading.

A brief can contain graphs and tables, sometimes a photograph, bullet style text boxes, a short list of references and contact info (expert, department, organisation).

Messages that can be conveyed through a policy brief may include:

- raising awareness: if policymakers are not aware that a problem exists, they will not do anything about it;
- raising importance of an issue: giving information about the scale of the problem (e.g. how big it is, how many people are affected, how they are affected, where they are);
- providing analysis: a discussion of the background, causes and effects of the problem, explaining why the problem exists, where it comes from, what its effects are);
- giving option(s): explaining what the policy options are for solving the problem, and what the strengths and weaknesses of each option are);
- concluding recommendations: giving evidence in favour of a particular option to show that it will be (cost) effective and explain why this option is better than the others.

A template for printable 2-page policy briefs is to be developed after month 18, into which emerging information and results from the first deliverables of technical WPs will be arranged.

5.2.2.6. Open access publications, scientific articles

ACT4CAP27 will fully comply with the open access requirements of the Horizon Europe programme detailed in Section 1.3.8.

Open access scientific publishing: OpenAIRE and Zenodo

The Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe is an electronic platform for aggregating content (including peer-reviewed articles, datasets and other important scientific publications such as preprints or conference publications) from different validated sources from Europe and

beyond. Further information on the functionalities of the systems is available here: www.openaire.eu/intro-to-functionality/

A research result publishing platform and publication repository related to OpenAIRE is ZENODO managed by CERN. More information is here: www.zenodo.org/features.

ACT4CAP27 's OpenAIRE page

<https://tinyurl.com/act4cap27-OpenAIRE>

ACT4CAP27 's Zenodo Community site

<https://zenodo.org/communities/act4cap27-eu-project/>

All partners are welcome to contribute with uploads to the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community repository page. All uploads will receive a DOI. Any uploads will appear publicly on the page, once it is authorised by the page's current curator POS.

Keeping track of planned publications, and reporting scientific articles in SyGMA

The Grant Management System continuous reporting has a specific tab on Publications (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Screenshot of the Publications reporting page in the System for Grant Management (SyGMA)

The upper part of the SyGMA publications reporting page automatically harvests publications from OpenAIRE (whereas Open AIRE also automatically harvests publications from Zenodo). The lower box enables to add further publications manually.

In ACT4CAP27, to help keep track of planned (it is compulsory to notify Board of WP leaders, see the part on internal communication processes in the D8.1 Project Management Plan), in-progress and implemented publications for the whole consortium, the lower table of the SyGMA publications reporting page is constructed in Excel that is available on SharePoint under WP7 in the root of the TASK 7.2 folder with a file name: [ACT4CAP27 -Sygma-Publications-Results-IPR-reporting.xlsx](#).

5.2.3. COMDISS channels

Project specific communication and dissemination channels were set up and maintained (project website, social media channels, video channel, on-line repositories), strong project communication through the European Commission channels, partner websites and social media channels.

Dissemination materials and publications have been (project flyer, e-newsletter, project roll-up poster) and are continued to be produced (e.g. project result briefs, open access peer-reviewed scientific publications).

Project website

The ACT4CAP27 website, under the domain name [act4cap27.eu](#) is a key management tool, capable of improving the communication and dissemination of project activities and results to a wide range of stakeholders including experts and specialists, policy decision makers at all geographic levels, publicly funded authorities, and the general public and citizens. The domain name was set up with the first press release of ACT4CAP27 by the time of the project's kick-off meeting. POS has created the ACT4CAP27 project website concept (**see D.7.4**), and maintains the project website based on contributions from all partners. The full-content version of the website was published on 31 July 2024.

The site hosts information about the aims, objectives and scope of ACT4CAP27, about the partnership, and provide details about the project activities, progress and results. Key findings and results are to be disseminated as they emerge. Its regular updates and management ensure contemporary content and up-to-date news on external policy and science developments relevant to project's remit. The project website is to be maintained for up to 5 years after project completion.

5.2.3.1. Publishing ACT4CAP27 on other websites

For dissemination through partners' channels, tailored sections of re-useable text are prepared and to accompany effective and visually coherent use of video clips, infographics, icons, explorable explanations and images produced in WP7.

Communications about ACT4CAP27 on partners' websites are collected and listed on the respective partner page of the project website, and documented in the partners' quarterly COMDISS reports.

5.2.3.2. Social media and visual support

To maintain contacts, interest and awareness, a comprehensive social media strategy is implemented through X (Twitter) <https://x.com/ACT4CAP27> and on LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/act4cap27-eu-project/>, which adheres to all relevant regulations, ethical considerations and personal privacy. We specifically refer to the 2021-2027 [Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects](#) issued as a guidance for Horizon Europe projects.

A social media content calendar is implemented and updated regularly through an editable content sharing platform. This enables co-ordination of regular posts on Twitter and LinkedIn, retweets, and the sharing of content through COMDISS Officers by partner social media channels. A database of useful hashtags (e.g. #HorizonEU, #EUfunded, #ResearchImpactEU, #SciencePolicy, #EUGreenDeal, #circulareconomy, #sustainability, #AgPolicy, #FoodSecurity, #Water, #FoodSystems, #ForOurPlanet, #agecon, #researcher, #ClimateChange, #UniteBehindTheScience, #Scientists4Future, #DataScience, #AgriculturalEconomics, #Productivity, #Policy, #FoodSystem, #economicmodelling, #agriculture, #agrifood, #sustainabledevelopment, #AGMEMOD, #MAGNET, #modelling, #annualmeeting, #pressrelease, #EuropeanGreenDeal, #landuse, #policies, #landuse, #foodsecurity, #EU_Commission), and accounts to be followed (e.g. @HorizonEU, @EUAgri, @EU_ENV, @REA_research), is continuously built with joint efforts of COMDISS Officers for common use. **ACT4CAP27 specific own hashtags such as #ACT4CAP27cooperates or #ACT4CAP27results are also established.**

The regular posts aim to:

- promote the project website; link with contents on the website: articles, new content, events etc.;
- inform about important progress / results / success stories of the project;
- promote project publications, and public deliverables (after approval of the EC);
- inform of any new partnerships and collaborations of the project;
- link to interesting articles related to the project theme, etc. and beginning a thread/conversation with the social media connections (sharing/retweeting).
- share relevant contents from other sites (projects, EU organisations, local organisations, initiatives etc.);
- report on project events (consortium meetings, workshops etc. – with photographs and comments);
- report on participation in EU events & congresses and any other media activities of the project (radio broadcasts, TV broadcasts, etc.);
- share information on other associated events (EU, other projects etc.);
- for LinkedIn in particular: provide professional articles from the academic partners.

Online promotional campaigns are regularly launched throughout the duration of the project, exploiting the latest trends and functions of social media (Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube) and utilising visually appealing graphic designs.

Social media channels foster networking and linking opportunities, enabling greater participation and engagement of target groups and stakeholders. A project profile is designed and regularly updated to serve as an interface with a broad range of stakeholders who are also able to initiate communication and exploitation.

ACT4CAP27 's Social Media Strategy

The social media strategy aims at:

- identifying and approaching people and organizations already active in fields related to the project activities (e.g. professionals in LinkedIn);
- get the project/ service well known through social media and call for “Action”;
- spreading news/content about the project: project content, activities, news, results etc.;
- engaging social media followers, preferably by directing them to the ACT4CAP27 project website;
- creating interactive forums at European and national scale.

Actions to be performed in this context include:

- identifying and approaching the relevant people and organizations;
- open European accounts in proper media: LinkedIn, Twitter;
- enlisting in relevant LinkedIn Professional Groups;
- regular social media posts aiming at informing or initiating discussions/debates/feedback;
- Social Media Campaigns: boosting posts towards the target group;
- utilizing already existing social media accounts of partners with relevant followers/members for communicating ACT4CAP27.

Steps to grow social media accounts

1. map individual personal contacts, as well as organisations with a potential interest in the project;
2. invite these contacts to connect with the project either through the social media or through personal messages. This includes stakeholders involved in the project and press distribution lists;
3. maintain the audience and keep accounts interactive. It is important to qualify and optimize the discussions and information provided, and post regularly. Responsibilities should be distributed amongst the COMDISS officers of the Communication Dissemination, Exploitation Team, providing discussions, posts, articles, etc. and particularly as regards the LinkedIn account.

Principles for using social media responsibly

- Think before you post: It is important to realise that even the strictest privacy settings have limitations. This is because, once something is online, it can be copied and redistributed by others.
- Protect your professionalism and your reputation: If you are unsure whether something you post online could compromise your professional position or your reputation, you should think about what the information means for you in practice. It is important to consider with whom and what you associate on social media. For example, acknowledging someone else’s post can imply that you endorse or support their point of view. You should consider the possibility of other people mentioning you in inappropriate posts.

Overview of Social Media Accounts of Partners

The existing social media accounts of project partners are also to be used to multiply the dissemination of information from the project Twitter site by following the ACT4CAP27 accounts, and retweeting or re-posting materials published by these means.

In Table 4 the social media accounts are described of ACT4CAP27 consortium partners on Twitter and LinkedIn that are to be used to further promote the project.

Table 4 Social media accounts of ACT4CAP27 consortium partners

Nr	Partner	website: https://	Twitter @	LinkedIn https://www.linkedin.com/
1	WR	www.wur.nl/nl/Onderzoek-Resultaten/Onderzoeksinstituten/Economic-Research.htm	WUReconomic	company/wageningeneconomicresearch/
2	THUENEN	www.thuenen.de/en/	Thuenen_aktuell	company/thuenen
3	EUROCARE	www.eurocare-bonn.de/	-	-
4	IIASA	iiasa.ac.at/	IIASAVienna	company/iiasa-vienna/
5	SLU	http://www.slu.se	-	school/slu/
6	UPM	http://www.upm.es/	https://twitter.com/La_UPM	school/universidad-politecnica-de-madrid/
7	WU	https://www.wur.nl/en.htm	https://twitter.com/wur	school/wur/
8	PNU	https://polissiauniver.edu.ua		school/polisia-national-university/
9	UNIROMA3	http://www.uniroma3.it/	https://twitter.com/UnivRoma3	school/universita-degli-studi-roma-tre/
10	ECORYS	http://www.ecorys.com	https://twitter.com/Ecorys	company/ecorys/
11	POS	https://www.possessio-ltd.eu	-	company/possessio-ltd/
12	UCL	https://www.ucl.ac.uk/	ucl	-
13	JRC	ec.europa.eu/info/departments/joint-research-centre_en	EU_ScienceHub	showcase/european-commission-joint-research-centre

5.2.3.3. Traditional mass media

Press-friendly **citizen-focussed** articles are to be produced centrally to launch solutions, linked with human interest narratives to encourage press uptake of project results and outputs at EU, national and regional levels.

Partner COMDISS Officers are responsible for actively searching and contacting relevant national and regional press outlets, and help checking machine translated texts into national language(s), and tailoring them to national/regional contexts as appropriate.

5.2.4. EC services to support communication, dissemination and exploitation

An overview of EC tools in support of communication, dissemination and exploitation of Horizon Europe projects is given in Figure 7 Overview of EC tools in support of communication, dissemination and exploitation of Horizon Europe projects.

Figure 7 Overview of EC tools in support of communication, dissemination and exploitation of Horizon Europe projects

The European Commission offers various free-of-charge services to support your dissemination and exploitation activities:

- **Open Research Europe (ORE) platform**: An open access, publishing platform for scientific papers for Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe beneficiaries, including an open peer review and article revision.
- **Horizon Results platform**: A platform for showcasing your research results, finding collaboration opportunities and getting inspired by the results of others. The Horizon Results Platform is free, is part of the F&T portal, available to all beneficiaries and is based on results, not on projects.
- **Horizon Results Booster**: Free consulting services including a portfolio dissemination and exploitation strategy, business plan development and go-to-market support.
- **European Standardisation Booster Service for EU Projects** (an action supported by the European Research Area HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01 Call, managed by REA): supports Horizon Europe and H2020 projects to contribute to standardisation in Europe and beyond.
- **Innovation radar**: An initiative that identifies high-potential innovations, based on a data-driven methodology, and assists EU-funded researchers and innovators in reaching the market with their innovation.
- EU social media accounts initially followed by ACT4CAP27 include the European Research Executive Agency @REA_research, European Commission @EU_Commission, Horizon Europe @HorizonEU, for Horizon Europe Cluster 6 – Food, bioeconomy, natural resources,

agriculture and environment @EUgreenresearch but many more are to be gradually added as a result of active searching by POS (also at [the EU social media accounts search tool](#)) and as suggested by project partners through the COMDISS Officers in the consortium.

In ACT4CAP27

Since ACT4CAP27 is not aiming at developing a product/service for commercial markets, the Innovation Radar and the Standardisation Booster service are less relevant. The Horizon Results Booster again is rather targeted for go-to-market projects.

The ORE and the Horizon Results platform are, however, relevant for promoting ACT4CAP27 results and success stories. It is up to discussion and strategic decision at the WP leaders' meeting, and partners' ambitions which of these services will be used.

Any project communications through EC channels first will have to be reviewed and approved by the WP Leaders' Executive Board.

Success stories

If the project has achieved outstanding results relevant to EU citizens, then through liaising with the Project Officer for further information, it could be promoted via some of the European Commission's free-of-charge channels such as: [Cordis Results in Brief](#), [CORDIScovery podcasts](#), [Research & innovation success stories](#), [Horizon Magazine](#) or during events such as the [R&I Days](#).

Th **European Research Executive Agency** REA's Communication team can help promote by:

- Proposing the project's success story for inclusion in the European Commission's free-of-charge communication channels.
- Highlighting & multiplying the project's news and results through REA's and the Commission's social media channels (to this end it is recommended to tag @REA_research)

CORDIS News <http://cordis.europa.eu/news/>

CORDIS is the EC portal for results of research projects. CORDIS News provides the latest research and innovation developments within Europe and beyond, focusing on policy topics, interviews, events, and projects.

The CORDIS page of ACT4CAP27 is at <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101134874>

Events at the Research and Innovation portal of the European Commission:

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/events_en

This website displays research and innovation-related conferences and events. An event can be entered into the event calendar by using the form at the following link:

https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/events/suggest-event_en

The selection criteria for inclusion are that the event has to be related to a research and innovation activity in the European Union. The ACT4CAP27 Final conference will also be announced and promoted through this channel.

Audiovisual news: Futuris on EuroNews www.euronews.com/programs/futuris

A short, documentary-style, television magazine item, in various languages which appears at least 22 times on the EuroNews channel throughout Europe. EuroNews has editorial independence. As the medium is television, it offers considerable potential for visually appealing projects and demonstration activities. The route to project coverage is through the Project Officer of EuroNews.

EC Newsletters

Newsletters are published by the European Commission for different research areas. The route to project coverage is through the Project Officer who can provide information about how to publish something in a specific newsletter.

Co-publications or editorial partnerships

The European Commission works with private publishers and international organisations to promote the dissemination of relevant publications. Scientific publications and books, including conference proceedings, may be co-published in this way.

In ACT4CAP27

Based on the nature of project results achieved, upon discussion and agreement at the WP Leaders' Executive Board, the most appropriate EC service provider is to be contacted by the Coordinating Team through the EC project Officer.

5.2.5. The project Final Conference

The project final conference will be designed as an on-line/hybrid (in Brussels) open international science and stakeholder conference to provide a synthesis of the research findings and the impacts created by the project on the primary analysis and findings and recommendations with primary target audience of those with European and national level responsibilities for policy and practice, including representation from and outside Europe.

5.2.6. Networking and external peer-to-peer exchange

External peer-to-peer exchange events will include

- organisation of workshops, conferences or sessions, the project final conference;
- participation at conferences and workshops;
- participation in relevant platforms of organisations (e.g. European Association of Agricultural Economists, EAAE) and relevant projects or initiatives (e.g. SCAR at EU level), and AKIS actors in Member States and in Associated Countries, networking and collaborating with other H2020 and Horizon Europe projects.

Stakeholder engagement is planned, implemented and monitored in Task 7.1, led by ECORYS. Participants of the workshops are to be provided with relevant information in advance (in general about the ACT4CAP27 project and specific information related to the workshop in concern), and a summary after the event. Narratives from such participatory events are to be used for developing 'end-user' oriented messages for publishing on the website, social media and online broadcasts.

All opportunities are to be taken to organize targeted thematic events that add value to project events, e.g. special sessions of international conferences, disseminations at a Coordinators' Day organised by the EC, and other events organised by DG AGRI or DG Research (also see Events under Section 3.2.3.6 on project communication through EC channels). Opportunities for organising of and participation at other events are actively sought by the consortium, information collected in a common calendar.

Synergies and success factors: collaborating with other projects

ACT4CAP27 is to promote its activities and collect regular information and news related to the topic of Sustainable Food System Policy modelling in the EU by monitoring and contributing to relevant online media blogs, news portals, publications and other media. ACT4CAP27 is to establish close ties with other relevant initiatives under EU-funded, international or national programmes helping to raise awareness and impacts amongst the target groups. Partners identify opportunities to participate in each other's events and the organisation of shared events. With this as an aim, close linkages are to be established on both centralised and decentralised project levels. A regularly updated, non-exhaustive list for networking and collaborating with other project includes: 1) legacy of H2020 projects funded under e.g. SFS-49-2017 ([SUPREMA](#)), RUR-04-2018-2019 ([AGRICORE](#), [BATModel](#), [BESTMAP](#), [MIND STEP](#)), RUR-21-2020 ([MATS](#), [TRADE4SD](#)), and 2) Horizon Europe funded projects selected under e.g. CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-12 ([BrightSpace](#)) CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-13 ([LAMASUS](#)), CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-08 ([GenBEcon](#)), CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01-01 ([RATION](#)) and CL6-2022-CIRCBIO-01-03 ([BIOTRANSFORM](#), [Sustrack](#)), HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01-6 ([STEP UP](#)), HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-17 ([FoodDataQuest](#), [SOSFood](#)), HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-4 ([FoSSNet](#)).

ACT4CAP27 makes use of, and integrate with, relevant activities of projects and events to add value, avoid duplication of effort and dilution of impact on policy advisors, and maximise combined impacts. Contacts with other EU level research consortia and teams working on relevant topics are well established and will be further developed to ensure coherent and complimentary communications.

Means of collaborating with other projects

- Exchange of information
- Cross-referencing each other's websites
- Holding bi-lateral meetings on strategy and dissemination
- Sharing information regarding key stakeholders
- Organising joint public events

A list of these projects is also available at the Useful Links section of the project website.

Synergies will be sought in common activities including 1) dissemination actions, 2) exchange of materials, 3) establishing links between websites and social media channels 4) regular inter-project meetings for exchange of information on project implementations, planning and evaluating joint activities and 5) co-operation to increase efficiency of deliverables.

In addition to events organised by ACT4CAP27, partners will collaborate with organisations and institutions responsible for planning leading policy, technical and scientific events scheduled over the period of the project, where ACT4CAP27 will seek to organize targeted sessions relating to the project's topic. EU level initiatives of relevance will be approached for facilitating dissemination and exploitation of results.

6. WHEN? - COMDISS IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

The planning Intervals of communication and dissemination activities in ACT4CAP27 are aligned with the timing of project reporting periods (Figure 8).

Reporting Periods

Reporting Period No.	From Month	To Month	Duration	Start Date	End Date
1	1	18	18	01/03/2024 (00:00)	31/08/2025 (23:59)
2	19	42	24	01/09/2025 (00:00)	31/08/2027 (23:59)
3	43	60	18	01/09/2027 (00:00)	28/02/2029 (23:59)

Source: EC SyGMA

Figure 8 Reporting Periods in ACT4CAP

In the following we describe the plan for, project communication, media tools, and dissemination activities planned for the two reporting intervals.

6.1. Project communication and media tools, and dissemination activities planned for M1-18 Interval 1: March 2024 - August 2025

The project communication activities within Interval 1 include:

- initializing the development of communication and media tools,
- general communications about the project (its ambition, aims, objectives, expected results, targeted messages for awareness raising of stakeholders) and its implementation (including due milestones reached) through e.g. press releases, project newsletter, popular articles, events.
- supporting other WPs with communicating about their activities,
- initialising networking activities with relevant projects, and initiatives at national and EU levels.

Project communication and media tools planned within Interval 1 are listed in Table 5.

Table 5 Project communication and media tools planned and made available within Interval 1

Nr	Item name	month of delivery planned
1	project visual identity – logo, project message, templates	08/ 2024
2	social media accounts: Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube	08/ 2024
3	project website	08/ 2024
4	ACT4CAP27 Zenodo community	03/ 2024
5	press-release on 1st General Assembly	03/ 2024
6	project general poster prototype in English, subsequent language versions, as needed	09/ 2024
7	project general flyer prototype in English, subsequent language versions, as needed	3/2024
8	6-monthly newsletters	10/ 2024, 04/ 2025
9	press-release on 2 nd General Assembly	03/ 2025
10	communications about M1 milestone (of WP1, WP2) reached: Conceptual framework for food system indicators	11/2024

Dissemination activities within Interval 1 have no relevance. Dissemination of deliverables may start after being submitted to and approved the EC. The open release of public deliverables before the EC’s approval is contingent on the decision of the project’s management board.

6.2. Project communication and media tools, and dissemination activities planned for M19-42 Interval 2.: September 2025 – August 2027

The project communication activities within Interval 2 include:

- maintenance of communication and media tools,
- continued general communications about the project (its ambition, aims, objectives, expected results, targeted messages for awareness raising of stakeholders) and its implementation through e.g. press releases, project newsletter, popular articles, events.
- supporting other WPs with communicating about their activities,
- maintaining and continued additional initialising of new networking activities with relevant projects, and initiatives at national and EU levels.

The communication and media tools listed in Table 5 are planned to be maintained and further developed if needed as appropriate, additional items are to include a press-release on 3rd General Assembly (March 2026) and further issues of 6 monthly project newsletters in April 2026, October 2026, April 2027.

Communications on website and through social media channels about due milestones if reached before the end of Interval 2:

Miles	Milestone Name	Work Package No	Lead Beneficiary	Delivery Date
2	CAP post 27 policy scenario studies	WP1,WP5	Thuenen	28 Feb 2026
3	ACT4CAP27 medium and long term baselines	WP5	UPM	28 Feb 2027
4	Modular ACT4CAP27 modelling toolbox	WP4,WP5	IIASA	31 Aug 2027

Source: EC SyGMA

Figure 9 ACT4CAP27 milestones in RP2

The project dissemination activities within Interval 2 include:

- supporting other WPs with promoting the dissemination of public deliverables from PR1 (Figure 10) and results through e.g. policy briefs, press releases, project newsletter, OA journal articles, popular articles, academic and policy events.
- maintaining and continued additional initialising of networking activities with relevant projects, and initiatives at national and EU levels for exchanges focusing on informing target audiences, stakeholders and end-users about emerging project results and making those results available for use.

Work Package	Deliver	Delive	Deliverable Name	Lead Ber	Type	Dissemi	Due Date
WP7	D7.1	D20	Stakeholder engagement strategy plan and annual reports	ECORYS	R	PU	31 Aug 2024
WP7	D7.2	D21	Communication, Dissemination and Impact Strategy and Plan and Reporting	POS	R	PU	31 Aug 2024
WP7	D7.4	D23	Project website	POS	R	PU	31 Aug 2024
WP1	D1.1	D1	An operational food systems framework for analysing sustainable outcomes	WR	R	PU	30 Nov 2024
WP7	D7.5	D24	Policy brief 1	POS	R	PU	30 Nov 2024
WP4	D4.1	D10	Report on technical guidance and examples for data processing and modularization	IIASA	R	PU	31 May 2025
WP7	D7.6	D25	Policy brief 2	POS	R	PU	31 Aug 2025

Source: EC SyGMA

Figure 10 ACT4CAP27 Public deliverables from in RP1

6.3. Project communication and media tools, and dissemination activities planned for M43-60 Interval 3: September 2027 – February 2029

The project communication activities within Interval 3 include:

- maintenance of communication and media tools,
- continued general communications about the project (its ambition, aims, objectives, expected results, targeted messages for awareness raising of stakeholders) and its implementation through e.g. press releases, project newsletter, popular articles, events.
- supporting other WPs with communicating about their activities,
- maintaining and continued additional initialising of networking activities with relevant projects, and initiatives at national and EU levels,
- pre-event promotion of the final conference.

The communication and media tools listed in Table 5 are planned to be maintained and further developed if needed as appropriate, additional items are to include a press-release on 4th General Assembly (November 2026) and further issues of 6 monthly project newsletters in December 2026, May 2027, and final issue in October 2027.

Communications on website and through social media channels about milestones due in month 60 within Interval 3 (Figure 11).

Miles	Milestone Name	Work Package No	Lead Beneficiary	Delivery Date
5	ACT4CAP27 Interactive Roadmap	WP6	WR	28 Feb 2029
6	Capacity building	WP5	UPM	28 Feb 2029
7	Final conference	WP7	ECORYS	28 Feb 2029

Source: EC SyGMA

Figure 11 ACT4CAP27 milestones in RP3

The project dissemination activities within Interval 3 include:

- supporting other WPs with promoting the dissemination of public deliverables from RP2 (Figure 12) and results through e.g. policy briefs, press releases, project newsletter, OA journal articles, popular articles, academic and policy events.
- maintaining and continued additional initialising of networking activities with relevant projects, and initiatives at national and EU levels for exchanges focusing on informing target audiences, stakeholders and end-users about project results and making those results available for use.
- post-event promotion of the final conference.

Work Package	Deliver	Delive	Deliverable Name	I	Lead Ber	Type	Dissemi	Due Date
WP1	D1.2	D2	Report on CAP post 2027 policies, modelling gaps, and identification of scenarios	I	Thuene	R	PU	28 Feb 2026
WP4	D4.2	D11	Report on Prototype of the Database (T4.1) and Scenario Explorer	I	IIASA	R	PU	28 Feb 2026
WP2	D2.1	D3	A health assessment module: documentation on data, implementation and analysis	I	LSHTM	R	PU	28 Feb 2027
WP2	D2.2	D4	Environmental assessment modules: documentation on data, implementation and analysis	I	IIASA	R	PU	28 Feb 2027
WP2	D2.3	D5	Socio-economic assessment module: documentation on data, implementation and analysis	I	WR	R	PU	28 Feb 2027
WP3	D3.1	D6	Global input module: documentation on data, implementation and analysis	I	SLU	R	PU	28 Feb 2027
WP3	D3.2	D7	EU module of consumer preference shifts: documentation on data, implementation and analysis	I	Thuene	R	PU	28 Feb 2027
WP3	D3.4	D9	CAP and GD policies module: documentation on data, implementation and analysis	I	Thuene	R	PU	28 Feb 2027
WP7	D7.7	D26	Policy brief 3	I	POS	R	PU	28 Feb 2027
WP4	D4.3	D12	Report on Prototype of the Computational Framework	I	IIASA	R	PU	31 Aug 2027

Source: EC SyGMA

Figure 12 ACT4CAP27 Public deliverables in RP2

6.4. Post-project dissemination activities planned

Dissemination activities planned after the closure of the project:

- promoting the outputs of the project, dissemination of all public deliverables, and in particular those that emerge during RP3 (Figure 13) and results through e.g. policy briefs, press releases, project newsletter, OA journal articles, popular articles, academic and policy events.
- supporting exploitation activities by maintaining networking with relevant projects, and initiatives at national and EU levels focusing on informing target audiences, stakeholders and end-users about project results and making those results available for use, and promoting the use of key exploitable results.

Work Package	Deliver	Delive	Deliverable Name	Lead Ber	Type	Dissemi	Due Date
WP3	D3.3	D8	Network model of supply chains: documentation on data, implementation and analysis	I UPM	R	PU	29 Feb 2028
WP5	D5.1	D14	Model infrastructure to bring model-based evidence closer to policy making	I SLU	R	PU	29 Feb 2028
WP5	D5.2	D15	Documentation on analytical tools to design and assess CAP policies post 2027	I EUROCA	R	PU	29 Feb 2028
WP7	D7.8	D27	Policy brief 4	I POS	R	PU	29 Feb 2028
WP6	D6.1	D18	Fast track results of all task results	I Thuene	R	PU	31 Aug 2028
WP4	D4.4	D13	The ACT4CAP27 Portal for user-friendly stakeholder engagement	I IIASA	R	PU	28 Feb 2029
WP5	D5.3	D16	ACT4CAP27 Modular Toolbox for Sustainable Food System Policy Modelling	I SLU	R	PU	28 Feb 2029
WP5	D5.4	D17	Capacity building activities	I UPM	R	PU	28 Feb 2029
WP6	D6.2	D19	ACT4CAP27 Interactive Roadmap for transferring to a sustainable European Food System	I WR	R	PU	28 Feb 2029
WP7	D7.3	D22	Exploitation Plan	I POS	R	PU	28 Feb 2029
WP7	D7.9	D28	Policy brief 5	I POS	R	PU	28 Feb 2029

Source: EC SyGMA

Figure 13 ACT4CAP27 Public deliverables in RP3

7. DOCUMENTING, MONITORING, EVALUATION AND REPORTING OF COMDISS ACTIVITIES

7.1. Monitoring of Communication and Dissemination Activities

The project has an overall evaluation strategy to ensure high quality, however separate monitoring for dissemination and exploitation is vital since the impact of those activities contributes to the successful implementation of the project. This evaluation will be carried out on a continuous basis, to ensure:

- an effective impact assessment and update or redefinition of dissemination and exploitation activities,
- the quality of the dissemination and exploitation carried out.

7.1.1. Continuous reporting of Communication and Dissemination activities in the SyGMA

In the Project Continuous Report of the SyGMA there are three tabs relevant for reporting about COMDISS activities:

- Communications activities,
- Dissemination activities,
- Publications (also see 5.2.2.6).

The screenshot shows the SyGMA web interface. At the top, there's a navigation bar with 'Grant Management' and 'Project Continuous Report'. Below this, a progress bar shows various categories: 'Communications Activities' (green checkmark), 'Standards' (green checkmark), 'Intellectual property rights (IPR)' (red X), 'Datasets' (green checkmark), 'Impact' (green checkmark), 'Impact Continuation' (green checkmark), and 'Other Results' (green checkmark). Below the progress bar, there's a form titled 'Add Communication Activity'. The form has several fields: 'Communication Activity Name', 'Description', 'Who? Target audience', 'How? Communication channel', 'Outcome', and 'Status'. The 'Who? Target audience' dropdown menu is open, showing a list of options: 'Industry, business partners', 'Innovators', 'Investors', 'EU Institutions', 'National authorities', 'Regional authorities', 'Local authorities', 'Civil society', 'Citizens', and 'Research communities'. A red asterisk indicates that 'Who? Target audience' is a mandatory field.

Figure 14 Types of Target audiences in COM activities report in SyGMA (one option possible)

Figure 15 Types of communication channels in COM activities report in SyGMA (one option possible)

Figure 16 Overview table of Dissemination activities reporting in SyGMA (one option possible)

SyGMA - System for Grant Management - Personal - Microsoft Edge
 https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/grants-app/reporting/DLV-101134874

nbalazka (EXTERNAL)

Add dissemination activity

Dissemination activity name*

What?
 Type of dissemination activity*

Who?

Clustering activities
 Collaboration with EU-funded projects
 Conferences
 Education and training events
 Meetings
 Other
 Other scientific collaboration

Figure 17 Types of activity categories in Dissemination activities reporting in SyGMA (one option possible)

SyGMA - System for Grant Management - Personal - Microsoft Edge
 https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/grants-app/reporting/DLV-101134874

nbalazka (EXTERNAL)

Add dissemination activity

Who?
 Target audience Reached*

Industry, business partners
 Innovators
 EU Institutions
 National authorities
 Regional authorities
 Local authorities
 Civil society
 Citizens
 Research communities
 Specific end user communities
 International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.)
 Other
 Investors

Figure 18 Types of target audiences reached in Dissemination activities reporting in SyGMA (selection of more types is possible)

SyGMA - System for Grant Management - Personal - Microsoft Edge
 https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/grants-app/reporting/DLV-101134874

nbalazka (EXTERNAL)

Add dissemination activity

Why?
 Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)*

Status of the dissemination activity*

* mandatory fields

[Add](#) [Cancel](#)

Figure 19 Description of objectives with reference to a specific project output in Dissemination activities reporting in SyGMA

The COMDISS Task 7.2 leader POS is responsible for filling in these tabs based on the information supplied by partners in their regular COMDISS reports (see section 7.2), and based on the updates of this deliverable.

Publications are automatically harvested in SyGMA from OpenAIRE, and POS is to check centrally, based on partner’s COMDISS reports, if these publications suggested by OpenAIRE are linked to the project and if the information displayed are correct and complete.

7.1.2. Monitoring and evaluation tools in ACT4CAP27

The system of tools for COMDISS monitoring and evaluation in ACT4CAP27 is designed to best serve the reporting requirements of SyGMA.

The following Monitoring and Evaluation tools will be set up:

1. Performance of project central COM channels: Statistics on the use, reach and engagement of the website and social networks

POS will analyse trends, statistics, and the impact of each activity performed on the website and on social networks. This will allow partners to better understand the most appropriate timing, communication style and target audience of each message based upon the patterns of access, and downloads of files.

2. Partner level COM activity indicators

For a coherent reporting based on the types of communication channels in the COM activities report in SyGMA (Figure 15) a typology of partner level COM activity indicators were set up (Table 6).

Table 6 Typology of partner level COM activity indicators in ACT4CAP27

COM channels specified by EC reporting	COM activity indicators
C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)	C01. 1. act4cap27 event organisation with external audience C01. 2. event participation/networking (with act4cap27 presentation/poster), C01. 3. act4cap27 project representation at event (with act4cap27 project flyer) specific types: C01. 4. act4cap27 cooperation/collaborating with other HE projects: events of info exchange/collaboration activities C01. 5. Policy information event with the EC: events organised by the EC where act4cap27 project and its results are presented
C02. Exhibition	C02. 1. physical exhibition: act4cap27 project appearance with printed materials C02. 2. online exhibition: act4cap27 project appearance with virtual materials (e.g. pdf, video) specific types: C02. 3. cooperation/collaborating with other HE projects: exhibition of act4cap27 project info at other project's event (physical or online) C02. 4. exhibition organised by the EC where act4cap27 project and its results are presented (physical or online)
C03. Interview	C03. 1. Interview with act4cap27 project info, appearing in written form: newspaper C03. 2. Interview with act4cap27 project info, appearing in broadcasting: TV/radio C03. 3. Interview with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner SM item C03. 4. Interview with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner video C03. 5. Interview with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website
C04. Media article	C04. 1. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in written form: press release, newspaper/popular article C04. 2. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in broadcasting: TV/radio C04. 3. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner SM item C04. 4. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner video

COM channels specified by EC reporting	COM activity indicators
	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website
C05. Newsletter	C05. 1. Newsletter: issuing act4cap27 project newsletter C05. 2. Newsletter: act4cap27 project info appearing in partner newsletter
C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 1. Print materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) physical form: used at events C06. 2. Print materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) physical form: used at exhibitions C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo) C06. 4. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published/echoed on project/partner social media C06. 5. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on project/partner website
C07. Radio/TV campaign	C07. 1. Radio/TV campaign: act4cap27 project appearance on radio/TV launched by project partner
C08. Social media	C08. 1. Social media: act4cap27 project appearance on project SM channels C08. 2. Social media: act4cap27 project appearance on partner SM channels
C09. Video	C09. 1. Video: act4cap27 project video appearance on project channels C09. 2. Video: act4cap27 project video appearance on partner channels
C10. Website	C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website
C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	act4cap27 project item deposited. Resource types: - dataset - event - image (diagram, drawing, figure, other, photo, plot) - lesson - model - Other - physical object - poster - presentation - publication (annotation collection, book, book chapter, conference paper, conference proceeding, data paper, dissertation, journal, journal article, other, output management plan, patent, peer review, preprint, project deliverable, project milestone, proposal, report, software documentation, standard, taxonomic treatment, technical note, thesis, working paper) - software (incl. computational notebook) - video/audio - workflow

The relation of COM channels specified by EC reporting to the ACT4CAP27 COMDISS activity typology and to the ACT4CAP27 COMDISS KPIs are assessed in **Appendix 3**.

Dissemination activities will be carefully evaluated ex ante, in fieri and ex post, to learn about the effectiveness of the mechanisms of communication and dissemination, and to record the visibility of the project. Examples of monitoring of impacts in this framework are photos taken from events, registration sheets, presentations, Tweets by external participants/stakeholders, subsequent references to in materials produced by stakeholders (e.g. uptake, adoption, citation).

3. COMDISS activity reports by all partners, to be delivered in every project quarter

Every three months, all partners deliver a report on communication and dissemination activities they have performed, using the respective online forms (See **Appendix 4**).

7.2. Monitoring procedures: reporting and feedback from partners via the quarterly COMDISS reports

To facilitate an accurate monitoring and assessment of the communication and dissemination (CD) activities, and to understand the impact of the actions carried out, it is necessary for all partners to register the activities that they implement, therefore all partner should

- prepare their CD activities accordingly to the action plan;
- report all CD activities, at least every 3 months;
- register these activities using the respective online forms (see **Appendix 4**);
- save evidence of the activities conducted, and of any references made by stakeholders to outputs or activities.

An appropriate folder structure at the ACT4CAP27 Shared working folder will provide partners with space for storing evidence of their communication and dissemination activities, including:

- presentation materials,
- photos of communication/dissemination events,
- print screens of online communication/dissemination events,
- metrics on dissemination activities,
- best practice guidance with documenting and minuting key discussions.

These partner reports will serve a basis for analysis and summary to be performed by POS, to be published as updates to this deliverable, and also provide input for periodical technical reporting on COMDISS activities at a consortium level. The timing and delivery of the Plan is to be evaluated through regular monitoring of activities. An aim is to identify which activities had the most significant impacts on stakeholders (both in quantitative and qualitative terms) and to adjust CD actions accordingly.

To facilitate the process of collecting information on dissemination activities, the ACT4CAP27 WP7.2 SharePoint folder contains all relevant and necessary templates to be used by partners.

To ensure compliance, the dissemination activities of partners are to be monitored, with regular reminders of obligations and assistance as appropriate.

Based on the quarterly reporting documents received from the partners, POS is to provide recommendations for the future dissemination and exploitation activities and actions

7.3. Monitoring the impact of COMDISS activities

Monitoring is against project-level COMDISS key performance indicators, 6-monthly online COMDISS Team meetings, partner COMDISS activity indicators reported in every project quarter in partner level COM-DISS registers.

7.3.1. Project level indicators of success and COMDISS KPIs

Main achievements and targeted end-users are described in Table 7.

Table 7 Specific project outputs to be referenced in reporting of DISS activities

Main outcomes/achievements	Target end-users
Advances in data analyses, economic theory, econometric techniques and simulation models including the capacity to account for a wider coverage of food system (i.e., analyses including upstream and downstream industries to agriculture) and sustainability dimensions (i.e. economic, social (including health), environmental and climate) in agri-food modelling	Policy makers, supporting staff and practitioners (EC, JRC, national governments) Scientific community
Improvements and extensions of existing models used by the EC based on close collaboration among researchers working on simulation models and on econometrics and data specialists	Scientific community
ACT4CAP27 Modular Toolbox for Sustainable Food System Policy Modelling (includes the ACT4CAP27 Data and Model Portal for accessing and exploration of key results).	Policy makers, supporting staff and practitioners (EC, national governments) Scientific community (including early carrier researchers)
ACT4CAP27 Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform	Policy makers, supporting staff and practitioners (EC, national governments) Stakeholders, citizens and public
ACT4CAP27 Interactive Roadmap	Policy makers, supporting staff and practitioners (EC, national governments) Stakeholders

Indicators of success (Table 8) is to inform project management of progress towards achieving project objectives. They are to be used to evaluate contributions to achieving the principal and expected impacts and outcomes of ACT4CAP27, and the specific project outputs to be referenced in reporting of DISS activities.

Table 8 Indicators to be used to evaluate contributions to achieving the principal and expected outcomes of ACT4CAP27 (outcomes numbered by listing in Call)

Outcomes	Indicators	Means of monitoring and evaluating: specific project outputs / related tasks, deliverables & milestones
Outcome I: Improved analytical capacity and toolbox to assess short-term and long-term impacts of future EU agri-food policies on food systems (and on their actors)	Agricultural modelling capacity of EU member states supported	ACT4CAP27 Toolbox: Modular Toolbox for Sustainable Food System Policy Modelling developed: D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4 Structurally enhanced models to better assess the trade-offs between biophysical and socio-economic domains including a wide number of environmental (e.g. water, nutrients, pollution and biodiversity), economic (welfare, value added, prices) and social (e.g. food security, equality, employment and health) indicators D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, D2.4 policy scenario simulations (D6.1). cloud-based solutions and interactive dashboards allow open access (licensing permits) to the ACT4CAP27 Toolbox (D4.1, D5.3) and environmental, socio-economic and bio-physical input data (M4.1) 3 model trainings/summer schools organized (M5.2); an Agri-food Model Young Researchers Network initiated (T5.4); one PhD candidate selected (M5.1) ACT4CAP27 Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform created to share and discuss the findings of the work with existing model platforms, research communities and policy makers (D7.1); scientific output presented at conferences and published in open access journals (D7.2) ACT4CAP27 Interactive Roadmap launched for guiding the European food system towards more sustainable outcomes in the medium and long run (task 6.4)
Outcome II: Enhanced evidence-based knowledge	An assessment of EU agri-food policies (in particular the CAP and Green	Sustainability modules (on health, environment, socio-economic) (D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, D2.4) and enhanced model structures (D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4) developed

Outcomes	Indicators	Means of monitoring and evaluating: specific project outputs / related tasks, deliverables & milestones
supporting analysis and design of agri-food policies.	Deal) is produced, and how they relate to sustainable food systems in the EU to provide relevant input for the CAP post 2027 revision process and the future EU legal framework for sustainable food systems	Containerized models/modules by IT infrastructure are hosted for easy access and exploration of data and results (D4.1) Stakeholders are engaged in scoping the EU food system and validating findings of baseline and alternative policy scenario assessments (D7.1).

Table 9 describes the key performance indicators specified for COMDISS activities.

Table 9 KPIs for impact evaluation of ACT4CAP27 communication /dissemination actions

KPI Nr	Indicators	Targets for the project lifetime	related COM channels / activity types	DISS activity types
01	N° of policy makers engaged	at least 250	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.) C02. Exhibition	clustering activities, conferences, meetings, other: DISS event with EU
02	N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	600 by the end of the project	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.) C02. Exhibition C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	clustering activities, conferences, meetings, other: DISS event with EU
03	N° of users accessing project website	200	C10. Website	clustering activities, conferences, meetings, education and training events, other scientific collaboration
04	N° of users following social media channels	800	C08. Social media	clustering activities, conferences, meetings, education and training events, other scientific collaboration
05	N° of video interviews	20	C03. Interview	conferences, meetings
06	N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media	30	C03. Interview C04. Media article	conferences
07	N° of times datasets and documentation downloaded from Zenodo repository	35	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	clustering activities, conferences, meetings, other: DISS event with EU
08	N° of scientific publications in international peer-reviewed publications	12 by project end	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	conferences, other scientific collaboration
09	scientific conferences - N° of organised sessions	3 project organized sessions	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)	conferences
10	scientific conferences - N° of presentations	20 presentations by project end	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)	conferences
11	N° of newsletter subscribers	act4cap newsletter: 150 by project end	C05. Newsletter	other

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APPENDIX 1 GLOSSARY OF KEY TERMS RELATED TO COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION

Key terms related to communication, dissemination and exploitation are listed here. Sources of information include the [EC Research and Innovation Participant Portal](#), the [HE NCP portal](#) and the [ERA-LEARN project portal](#) :

Civil society. The term covers: 1) labour market organisations (e. trade unions and employers' federations — the 'social partners') 2) organisations that represent social and economic interests (g. consumer organisations) 3) NGOs (non-governmental organisations) — groups bring people together for a common cause (e.g. environmental organisations, human rights organisations, charities, educational and training organisations) 4) CBOs (community-based organisations) — community interest groups (e.g. youth organisations, family associations and any organisations that enable people local and municipal life) 5) religious groups.

Civil society organisation: Non-governmental, not-for-profit organisation that does not represent business interests. Pursues a common purpose for the good of society.

Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results to external audiences. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. Communication measures should promote the project throughout the full lifespan of the project. The aim is to inform and address multiple audiences outside the project's community and reach out to society at large, to show the activities performed, and highlight the use and the benefits of the EU-funded project will have for citizens. The purpose of the communication activities is to make the research activities known to multiple audiences (in a way that they can be understood by non-specialists) and the activities must address the public policy perspective of EU research and innovation funding, by considering aspects such as (i) transnational cooperation in a European consortium (i.e. how working together has allowed to achieve more than otherwise possible) or (ii) scientific excellence or (iii) contributing to competitiveness and to solving societal challenges.

Data Management Plan (DMP): Document outlining how the research data collected or generated by a project will be handled during and after the life of the project. It sets out: 1) the data to be collected/generated 2) the methodology and standards to be used 3) whether and how the data will be shared and/or made accessible 4) how data will be curated and preserved.

Deliverable: a specific output of the project, meaningful in terms of the project's overall objectives in the form of a report, document, technical diagram, piece of software, etc. Should usually be reported on and submitted to the EU.

Destination: consists of packages of actions around which each work programme part will be designed, aimed at contributing to the objectives and the expected impacts set out in the strategic orientations. The destination will provide the policy narrative for the calls and actions included in the Work Programme.

Dissemination is the public disclosure of the results by appropriate means, other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results, including scientific publications in any medium. It means the transfer of knowledge and results to enable others to use and take up results. Dissemination only focuses on results by describing them and ensuring that results are available for others to use. Its target audience entails people/organisations that may have an interest in using the project's results.

Effectiveness: the extent to which the set objectives and the intended results and impacts are achieved.

Efficiency: the extent to which the desired effects are achieved at a reasonable cost (in terms of resources consumed, such as time, financial inputs, etc.).

Evaluation: the rigorous, scientifically based collection of information about program/intervention activities, characteristics, and outcomes that determine the merit or worth of the program/intervention.

Expected impacts are a core element of the impact-driven approach of Horizon Europe, describing the long-term effects to which research and innovation are due to contribute. In total, the strategic plan defines 32 expected impacts that cover a wide range of social, economic, ecological and scientific aspirations. The expected impacts for Pillar II were codesigned to bridge the intervention areas set out by Horizon Europe legal basis with societal expectations. Each expected impact is deployed in the work programmes relevant parts, to cover the different dimensions (creation of knowledge, technology and social innovation) of research and innovation needed to achieve the objectives. The European Commission's Horizon Europe Intervention Logic distinguishes between three types of expected impacts – scientific, innovation/economic and societal. But successful Horizon Europe proposals need to cover impacts that go even further, such as: - Generating or improving awareness - Changing attitudes - Positive effects on the economy or the environment - Improving health and wellbeing - Effecting a desired cultural change.

Exploitation means the use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including e.g. commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities. Exploitation focuses on making the concrete use of research results through appropriate exploitation routes (not restricted to commercial use). Its target audience entails people/organisations – inside and outside the project - that make concrete use of the results.

Green Deal The European Green Deal is the plan to make the EU's economy sustainable carbon-neutral by 2050. The plan outlines investments needed and financing tools available. The Green Deal brings together all the measures and research programmes put in place to achieve this objective

Impacts can be defined as positive and negative, primary and secondary long-term effects produced by an intervention, directly or indirectly, intended or unintended. While outcomes rather relate to those directly addressed by an intervention, impacts rather refer to the wider environment surrounding the policy intervention. Also see Expected impacts

Indicator: a quantitative or qualitative variable that provides a valid and reliable way to measure achievement, assess performance, or reflect changes connected to an intervention.

Impact pathway indicators: Scientific/Technological/Economic: The Horizon Europe Programme is expected to have scientific/ technological/economic impact especially within the Union by influencing the creation and growth of companies, especially SMEs including startups, creating direct and indirect jobs especially within the Union, and by leveraging investments for research and innovation. Progress towards this impact will be monitored through proxy indicators set along these three key impact pathways.

Innovation: The introduction within a firm or market of a new or significantly improved: 1) product (good or service) 2) process 3) marketing method 4) organisational method (business practices, workplace organisation or external relations). The minimum requirement for an innovation is that the product, process, marketing method or organisational method must be new (or significantly improved) to the firm.

International organisation (IO) An intergovernmental organisation with legal personality under international public law, or any specialised agency set up by such an international organisation.

Key Exploitable Result (KER) is an identified main interesting result (as defined below) which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive

benefits- downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.

Objectives (global): provide a basis for assessing an intervention in relation to longer term and more diffuse effects (or global impacts). Indicators at this level are also called impact indicators.

Objectives (intermediate): provide a basis for assessing an intervention in relation to its short to medium-term effects (or intermediate impacts) on both the direct and indirect beneficiaries/recipients of assistance. Indicators at this level are called impact indicators.

Objectives (operational): provide a basis for assessing an intervention in relation to its outputs. The latter can be defined as what is directly produced / supplied through the activities and actions carried out during the implementation process. Indicators at this level are called output indicators.

Objectives (specific): provide a basis for assessing an intervention in relation to the short-term results that occur at the level of direct beneficiaries/recipients of assistance. Indicators at this level are called outcome indicators.

Open access: means online access to research outputs, in particular scientific publications and research data, free of charge to the end user. Practice of providing free online access to scientific information in 2 main categories: 1) peer-reviewed research articles (published in academic journals) 2) research data (data underlying publications and/or raw data). There are 2 types of open access: 1) gold access (open publishing – publication is immediately provided in open access mode by the scientific publisher) 2) green access (self-archiving – document is archived (deposited) by the author in an online repository before, alongside or after its publication; repository software usually allows authors to delay access to the article for an embargo period).

Open access to research data: Practice of making results public by providing access to digital research data (such as statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images) and giving the possibility to re-use it. Openly accessible research data can typically be accessed, mined, exploited, reproduced and disseminated free of charge for the user.

Open science is an approach based on **open cooperative** work and systematic **sharing of knowledge and tools** as early and widely as possible in the process. Open Science is defined as an umbrella term that involves various practices that aim to make academic research more accessible, inclusive, and transparent. It encompasses several movements such as open access to publications, open research data, open-source software, open collaboration, open peer review, open notebooks, open educational resources, open monographs, citizen science, or research crowdfunding. Each one of them has a specific goal but a common objective to remove the barriers for sharing any kind of output, resources, methods or tools, at any stage of the research process, trying to re-define the paradigm of the future of knowledge creation and dissemination of scientific knowledge. The European Commission has defined eight ambitions in Open Science : 1) Open Data: FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable data) and open data sharing should become the default for the results of EU-funded scientific research. 2) European Open Science Cloud (EOSC): a ‘federated ecosystem of research data infrastructures will allow the scientific community to share and process publicly funded research results and data across borders and scientific domains. 3) New Generation Metrics: New indicators must be developed to complement the conventional indicators for research quality and impact, so as to do justice to open science practices. 4) Future of scholarly communication: all peer-reviewed scientific publications should be freely accessible, and the early sharing of different kinds of research outputs should be encouraged. 5) Rewards: research career evaluation systems should fully acknowledge open science activities. 6) Research integrity: all publicly funded research in the EU should adhere to commonly agreed standards of research integrity. 7) Education and skills: all scientists in Europe should have the necessary skills and support to apply open science research routines and practices. 8) Citizen science: the general public should

be able to make significant contributions and be recognised as valid European science knowledge producers.

Open Research Europe is an open access publishing platform for the publication of research stemming from Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe and/or Euratom funding across all subject areas. The platform makes it easy for Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe and Euratom beneficiaries to comply with the open access terms of their funding and offers researchers a publishing venue to share their results and insights rapidly and facilitate open, constructive research discussion. <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

OpenAIRE: is a pan-European research information system, which provides services to find, store, link and analyse research output from all disciplines. OpenAIRE is a pan-European meta repository with more than 60 partner institutions from all EU countries and beyond, with National Open Access Desks (NOADs) in 35 countries. OpenAIRE aims at promoting and implementing the directives of the European Commission (EC) and the European Research Council on the promotion and funding of science and research. OpenAIRE has started out as a policy support mechanism for the EC (FP7 pilot and H2020 OA policies), with the aim to be the European scholarly communication hub providing its services to many European funders.

Outcomes: can be defined as the likely or achieved short-term and medium-term effects of an intervention's outputs.

Outputs: items directly produced by certain activities (e.g. workshop reports, Strategic Research and Innovation Agendas, databases of programmes, etc.) and are typically produced within the short-term. A specific output of the project, meaningful in terms of the project's overall objectives in the form of a report, document, technical diagram, piece of software, etc. It should usually be reported on and submitted to the European Commission through the relevant IT platform.

Pathway to impact: Logical steps towards the achievement of the expected impacts of the project over time, in particular beyond the duration of a project. A pathway begins with the projects' results, to their dissemination, exploitation and communication, contributing to the expected outcomes in the work programme topic, and ultimately to the wider scientific, economic and societal impacts of the work programme destination.

Persistent Identifier (PID) is a long-lasting reference to a resource. That resource might be a publication, dataset or person. Equally it could be a scientific sample, funding body, set of geographical coordinates, unpublished report or piece of software. Whatever it is, the primary purpose of the PID is to provide the information required to reliably identify, verify and locate it. A PID may be connected to a set of metadata describing an item rather than to the item itself. There are different PID types for different kinds of resources. In the current research environment, we most commonly see two varieties: those for objects (publications, data, software, such as URNs, DOIs, ARKs, Handle) and those for people (researchers, authors, contributors, such as ORCIDs, ISNIs). Many repositories will assign a PID of the former type when an object is deposited.

Political Guidelines focus on six headline ambitions for Europe over the years from 2019 to 2024 and well beyond: A European Green Deal, An economy that works for people, A Europe fit for the digital age, Protecting our European way of life, A stronger Europe in the world, A new push for European democracy

Prototype, testing activities: Proof of S&T feasibility: Results of innovation activities that confirm/verify the technical feasibility of new products and processes in a (near) operational environment. Includes: 1) prototypes & demonstrations of new products and processes 2) results of testing/piloting with users 3) trial production and pilot plants in manufacturing 4) trials & testing for services, such as how new technologies affect provision or how significant improvements in existing services perform

Product: Good or service introduced to the market or to the company/organisation that is new or significantly improved in its capabilities, usability, components or sub-systems. Goods include packaged & downloadable software/music/film.

Result: any tangible or intangible effect of the action, such as data, know-how or information, whatever its form or nature, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights. Project results can be reusable and exploitable (e.g. inventions, prototypes, services) as such, or elements (knowledge, technology, processes, networks) that have potential to contribute for further work on research or innovation. Key results are the outputs generated during the project which can be used and create impact, either by the project partners or by other stakeholders

Stakeholder: a person, group, or entity who has a direct or indirect role and interest in the goals or objectives and implementation of a program/intervention and/or its evaluation.

Strategic Plan (2025-2027) The 2nd Horizon Europe strategic plan ([Link here](#)) defines the strategic orientations for EU research and innovation investments over the period 2025-2027 and acts as a compass to stay on course with the political priorities of the Commission. The aim is to ensure an effective interface between EU policy priorities, and programme activities and ultimately, the research and innovation projects funded by Horizon Europe.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) or Global Goals are a collection of 17 interlinked global goals <https://sdgs.un.org/goals> designed to be a “blueprint to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all”. The SDGs were set in 2015 by the United Nations General Assembly and are intended to be achieved by the year 2030. They are included in a UN Resolution called the [2030 Agenda](#) or what is colloquially known as Agenda 2030. Horizon Europe is supporting the achievement of the Union’s key policy goals, including the Sustainable Development Goals. Each project funded by HE will support the overall SDGs implementation.

Utility: the extent to which outcomes corresponded with the needs, problems and issues to be addressed.

Zenodo: launched in 2013 it is a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by the European Organisation for Nuclear Research (CERN). It allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artefacts. For each submission, a persistent digital object identifier (DOI) is minted, which makes the stored items easily citeable.

APPENDIX 2 ACT4CAP27 KEY MESSAGES PER TARGET AUDIENCE

Key Messages for Target Audience: European Commission, International Bodies, and Government Representatives

The following key messages emphasize the strategic importance of the ACT4CAP27 project in enhancing policy tools, supporting sustainable development, and fostering collaboration within the research community to achieve the objectives of the European Green Deal.

Enhancing Policy Tools for Post-2027: ACT4CAP27 strengthens key analytical tools (CAPRI, GLOBIOM, MAGNET, AGMEMOD) to better support the design and evaluation of post-2027 agri-food policies.

Supporting the European Green Deal: The project aligns with the European Green Deal, enhancing the CAP's role in achieving sustainable agriculture, food security, and rural development.

Interdisciplinary Analytical Framework: Development of a comprehensive, interdisciplinary framework to quantify economic, social, environmental, and climate sustainability impacts of EU agri-food policies.

Broadening Thematic Coverage: Expanding the thematic scope of current quantitative tools to address all components of the European Green Deal, ensuring comprehensive policy impact assessments.

Evidence-Based Policymaking: Providing robust, data-driven insights to aid policymakers in crafting well-informed, effective agri-food policies for the post-2027 landscape.

Consistency with Monitoring Systems: Ensuring that enhanced analytical tools are consistent with existing monitoring systems, facilitating coherent and reliable policy evaluations.

ACT4CAP27 Modular Toolbox: Introducing a modular model infrastructure that fosters innovation and provides a collaborative space for the EU agri-food research community.

Stakeholder Engagement and Dissemination: Establishing an inclusive platform to engage stakeholders, co-create, communicate, and disseminate research results, ensuring broad-based support and understanding.

Interactive Policy Roadmap: Launching an Interactive Roadmap to guide EU, national, and regional policymakers in balancing policy objectives for more sustainable outcomes.

Addressing Policy Challenges: Tackling the challenge of supporting policy impact assessments in the context of new sustainability goals, ensuring that the CAP remains a pivotal tool for the EU.

Long-Term Sustainability Focus: Emphasizing the creation of sustainable food systems, crucial for the long-term resilience and prosperity of the EU agricultural sector.

Innovative Research Community: Facilitating a collaborative and innovative environment for the agri-food research community, driving forward advancements in policy support tools.

Key Messages for Local, Regional, and National Governments, Policymakers, Technical Staff, Regulatory and Managing Authorities, Regional Planning Authorities

By addressing the following key messages, ACT4CAP27 aims to support local, regional, and national governments, policymakers, and related authorities in developing and implementing innovative policies and governance frameworks that promote sustainable, resilient, and equitable agri-food systems.

Enhanced Policy Tools: ACT4CAP27 enhances key analytical tools (CAPRI, GLOBIOM, MAGNET, AGMEMOD) used by policymakers, improving the ability to design and assess agricultural policies with greater precision and reliability.

Evidence-Based Decision Making: The project provides evidence-based knowledge to support informed decision-making, ensuring that policies are grounded in robust data and comprehensive analysis.

Comprehensive Policy Assessment: ACT4CAP27 addresses the need for enhanced thematic coverage in policy tools, enabling comprehensive assessments of economic, social, environmental, and climate impacts of agri-food policies.

Alignment with the European Green Deal: The project supports policies that align with the European Green Deal, helping local, regional, and national governments achieve sustainability goals outlined in the Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategies.

Support for Regional Planning: ACT4CAP27 offers valuable insights for regional planning authorities, enabling the development of region-specific strategies that promote sustainable agriculture and rural development.

Climate Resilience: The project contributes to the creation of climate-resilient policies, helping governments and regulatory authorities mitigate and adapt to the impacts of climate change on the agri-food sector.

Interdisciplinary Framework: ACT4CAP27 develops an interdisciplinary framework that integrates economic, social, environmental, and health dimensions, providing a holistic approach to policy design and impact assessment.

Interactive Roadmap: The project's Interactive Roadmap guides policymakers at all levels in balancing policy objectives and achieving sustainable outcomes, ensuring coherence and coordination across different governance levels.

Stakeholder Engagement: ACT4CAP27 establishes an inclusive engagement platform for stakeholders, facilitating the co-creation and dissemination of research results and fostering collaboration among various actors.

Capacity Building: The project enhances the analytical capacity of technical staff and regulatory authorities, providing training and tools that support their ability to implement and monitor effective policies.

Innovative Governance: ACT4CAP27 promotes innovative governance approaches, encouraging the adoption of best practices and new technologies in the management of agri-food systems.

Economic Stability: By improving policy impact assessments, the project helps ensure economic stability and growth in the agri-food sector, benefiting local and regional economies.

Health and Social Benefits: The project supports the design of policies that improve public health and social welfare, addressing issues such as food security, nutrition, and rural livelihoods.

Transparency and Accountability: ACT4CAP27 enhances transparency and accountability in policy-making, ensuring that policies are developed through an open and participatory process.

Sustainable Development Goals: The project aligns with broader Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), helping governments and policymakers contribute to global efforts in sustainability, poverty reduction, and environmental protection.

Innovation and Collaboration: ACT4CAP27 fosters innovation and collaboration within the EU agri-food research community, creating a modular infrastructure that supports ongoing development and sharing of best practices.

Effective Monitoring Systems: The project ensures consistency with existing monitoring systems, enhancing the ability of governments and regulatory authorities to track and evaluate policy impacts over time.

Key Messages for External Scientific Community and Policy Modelling Professionals, including Early-Career Professionals

The following key messages highlight how the ACT4CAP27 project benefits the external scientific community and policy modelling professionals, emphasizing capacity building, innovation, collaboration, and comprehensive policy support.

Enhanced Analytical Tools: ACT4CAP27 enhances critical policy tools like CAPRI, GLOBIOM, MAGNET, and AGMEMOD, offering advanced capabilities for comprehensive agri-food policy analysis.

Interdisciplinary Framework Development: The project develops an interdisciplinary framework that integrates economic, social, environmental, and climate sustainability aspects, enriching the scope and depth of policy modelling.

Innovation in Modelling: ACT4CAP27 introduces the Modular Toolbox for EU Food System Modelling, fostering innovation and providing a flexible, collaborative infrastructure for the research community.

Capacity Building and Training: Through workshops, seminars, and training programs, ACT4CAP27 supports the development of skills and expertise among early-career professionals and seasoned policy modelling experts.

Collaborative Research Environment: The project creates a collaborative space for the EU agri-food research community, facilitating knowledge sharing, joint research efforts, and interdisciplinary collaboration.

Evidence-Based Insights: ACT4CAP27 provides robust, evidence-based insights to support policy analysis and design, helping researchers and policymakers make informed decisions for sustainable agri-food systems.

Addressing Current Tool Limitations: By addressing the limitations of existing quantitative tools, ACT4CAP27 ensures comprehensive coverage of all components of the European Green Deal, enhancing the reliability and relevance of policy assessments.

Engagement and Dissemination Platform: The project establishes an inclusive platform for engaging stakeholders, co-creating, communicating, and disseminating research results, ensuring widespread impact and understanding.

Interactive Roadmap for Policymakers: ACT4CAP27 launches an Interactive Roadmap to guide policymakers at the EU, national, and regional levels, helping them balance policy objectives towards sustainable outcomes.

Support for the European Green Deal: The project aligns with the European Green Deal, supporting its goals through enhanced analytical capacity and comprehensive policy tool development.

Networking Opportunities: ACT4CAP27 offers networking opportunities for early-career and experienced professionals, fostering connections within the policy modelling and scientific community.

Promoting Sustainable Agri-Food Systems: By developing advanced tools and frameworks, ACT4CAP27 promotes the creation of more sustainable and resilient agri-food systems, contributing to long-term food security and rural development.

Key Messages for Agricultural Sectors and Agri-Food Businesses: Unlocking Innovation through Sustainable Policies and Governance

Enhancing Competitiveness: ACT4CAP27 develops innovative policies that enhance the competitiveness of the agricultural sector and agri-food businesses, ensuring their growth and sustainability in a rapidly changing market.

Supporting Economic Viability: By improving analytical tools, ACT4CAP27 helps design policies that support the economic viability of farms and agri-food enterprises, contributing to long-term profitability and stability.

Facilitating Sustainable Practices: The project promotes the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices through evidence-based policies, helping businesses meet environmental standards and consumer expectations.

Adapting to Market Changes: ACT4CAP27 provides tools and insights that help agri-food businesses adapt to evolving market demands and regulatory changes, ensuring they remain resilient and competitive.

Improving Risk Management: Enhanced policy tools developed by ACT4CAP27 aid in better risk management strategies for agricultural sectors, helping businesses mitigate the impacts of climate change and market fluctuations.

Boosting Innovation: The project fosters innovation by creating a collaborative space and modular infrastructure, encouraging the development and adoption of new technologies and practices within the agri-food sector.

Aligning with the Green Deal: ACT4CAP27 supports policies that align with the European Green Deal, helping businesses transition to more sustainable and environmentally-friendly operations.

Enhancing Policy Impact Assessments: The improved analytical capacity allows for more accurate policy impact assessments, providing businesses with a clearer understanding of how policies will affect their operations and market conditions.

Strengthening Rural Development: The project supports policies that enhance rural development, ensuring that agri-food businesses in these areas benefit from improved infrastructure, services, and economic opportunities.

Promoting Sustainable Food Systems: ACT4CAP27 aids in the creation of policies that promote sustainable food systems, ensuring that agri-food businesses play a key role in achieving food security and environmental goals.

Providing Evidence-Based Insights: The project delivers evidence-based knowledge that helps agri-food businesses make informed decisions and strategies, enhancing their operational effectiveness and sustainability.

Engaging Stakeholders: The Act4CAP27 Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform ensures inclusive engagement with the agricultural sector, allowing businesses to contribute to and benefit from policy development.

Interactive Roadmap for Guidance: The project launches an Interactive Roadmap that guides EU, national, and regional policymakers, providing agri-food businesses with a clear path to navigate future policy landscapes.

Addressing Policy Shortcomings: ACT4CAP27 addresses the main shortcomings of current modelling tools, ensuring that future policies are comprehensive and beneficial for the agricultural sector and agri-food businesses.

Long-Term Strategic Planning: The project supports long-term strategic planning for agri-food businesses, helping them align their operations with sustainable development goals and future policy directions.

Key Messages for Environmental and Community NGOs, Civil Groups

Supporting Sustainable Agriculture: ACT4CAP27 enhances the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) to promote sustainable farming practices that align with environmental conservation goals.

Combating Climate Change: The project strengthens analytical tools to assess and design agricultural policies that mitigate climate change impacts, contributing to global climate action efforts.

Fostering Biodiversity: By aligning with the European Green Deal and Biodiversity Strategy, ACT4CAP27 helps create policies that protect and enhance biodiversity within agricultural landscapes.

Community Engagement and Involvement: The ACT4CAP27 Dissemination and Stakeholder Platform ensures inclusive engagement with environmental NGOs and civil groups, fostering collaboration and incorporating community insights into policy development.

Promoting Food Security: The project supports policies that ensure food security while maintaining ecological balance, benefiting both human communities and natural ecosystems.

Innovative Policy Framework: ACT4CAP27 develops an interdisciplinary framework that integrates economic, social, environmental, and climate aspects, leading to more holistic and effective agricultural policies.

Evidence-Based Advocacy: The project provides NGOs and civil groups with robust, evidence-based knowledge to advocate for stronger environmental and climate-focused agricultural policies.

Addressing Policy Gaps: By identifying and addressing gaps in current modelling tools, ACT4CAP27 ensures comprehensive policy assessments that consider all components of the European Green Deal.

Encouraging Sustainable Practices: ACT4CAP27 promotes sustainable agricultural practices through improved policy tools, benefiting environmental health and community well-being.

Climate Resilience: The project enhances the ability of agricultural systems to adapt to and withstand climate challenges, supporting resilient rural communities.

Collaborative Innovation: ACT4CAP27 fosters a collaborative space for NGOs, civil groups, and researchers to innovate and contribute to sustainable agricultural policy development.

Guiding Policy Decisions: The Interactive Roadmap launched by ACT4CAP27 provides guidance to policymakers, ensuring that environmental and community needs are considered in agricultural policy decisions.

Transparency and Communication: The project emphasizes transparency and effective communication of research results, making information accessible and actionable for NGOs and civil groups.

Long-Term Environmental Benefits: By supporting the design of post-2027 agri-food policies, ACT4CAP27 contributes to long-term environmental sustainability and the protection of natural resources.

Key Messages for EU Citizens, the Public

Ensuring Food Security: ACT4CAP27 enhances the analytical tools used to develop policies that ensure a stable and secure food supply for all EU citizens, safeguarding food availability and affordability.

Promoting Sustainable Agriculture: The project supports the creation of innovative agricultural policies that promote sustainable farming practices, helping to protect the environment and preserve natural resources for future generations.

Combating Climate Change: ACT4CAP27 contributes to policies that address climate change by enhancing the sustainability of the agri-food sector, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and promoting climate-resilient practices.

Supporting Rural Development: By fostering rural development, the project helps improve the quality of life in rural areas, ensuring that all regions of the EU benefit from economic growth and social stability.

Enhancing Policy Effectiveness: ACT4CAP27 improves the effectiveness of agricultural policies, ensuring that taxpayer money is used efficiently to achieve tangible benefits for society, including environmental protection and social welfare.

Boosting Public Health: The project supports policies that promote healthier food systems, contributing to improved public health outcomes through better nutrition and reduced environmental pollution.

Encouraging Innovation: ACT4CAP27 fosters innovation in the agricultural sector, leading to the development of new technologies and practices that benefit the economy and create new job opportunities.

Transparency and Accountability: The project ensures greater transparency and accountability in policy-making, providing EU citizens with evidence-based knowledge and clear information about how agricultural policies are developed and implemented.

Engaging Stakeholders: ACT4CAP27 promotes inclusive engagement with stakeholders, ensuring that the voices of citizens, taxpayers, and civil society are heard and considered in the policy-making process.

Improving Policy Impact Assessments: By enhancing the analytical capacity of policy tools, the project helps policymakers make more informed decisions, leading to policies that better reflect the needs and preferences of the public.

Strengthening Economic Resilience: ACT4CAP27 supports policies that strengthen the economic resilience of the EU's agri-food sector, ensuring stability and growth in the face of global challenges such as market volatility and climate change.

Aligning with the European Green Deal: The project aligns agricultural policies with the objectives of the European Green Deal, promoting a greener and more sustainable future for all EU citizens.

Maximizing Social Benefits: ACT4CAP27 ensures that agricultural policies maximize social benefits, including job creation, rural prosperity, and social inclusion, contributing to a more equitable society.

Interactive Policy Guidance: The project provides an Interactive Roadmap that guides policymakers at all levels, helping to balance policy objectives and achieve more sustainable and socially beneficial outcomes.

Promoting Biodiversity: ACT4CAP27 supports the EU's Biodiversity Strategy, helping to preserve biodiversity and protect ecosystems that are essential for the well-being of current and future generations.

APPENDIX 3 RELATION OF COM CHANNELS SPECIFIED BY EC REPORTING TO THE ACT4CAP27 COMDISS ACTIVITY TYPOLOGY AND TO THE ACT4CAP27 COMDISS KPIS

Relation of COM channels specified by EC reporting to ACT4CAP27 COMDISS activity typology and to ACT4CAP27 COMDISS KPIs

Can the use of the particular COM channel (specified by EC reporting) contribute to the respective act4cap27 COMDISS KPI? Yes-1, No-0

[direct strong link](#)

COM channels specified by EC reporting	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)	C02. Exhibition	C03. Interview	C04. Media article	C05. Newsletter	COM channels specified by EC reporting					C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)
						C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C07. Radio/TV campaign	C08. Social media	C09. Video	C10. Website	
act4cap27 COMDISS activity typology											
measuring partner performance: possible types of activities through these COM channels	C01. 1. act4cap27 event organisation with external audience C01. 2. event participation/networking (with act4cap27 presentation/poster), C01. 3. act4cap27 project representation at event (with act4cap27 project flyer) specific types: C01. 4. act4cap27 cooperation/collaborating with other HE projects: events of info exchange/collaboration activities C01. 5. Policy information event with the EC: events organised by the EC where act4cap27 project and its results are presented	C02. 1. physical exhibition: act4cap27 project appearance with printed materials C02. 2. online exhibition: act4cap27 project appearance with virtual materials (e.g. pdf, video) specific types: C02. 3. cooperation/collaborating with other HE projects: exhibition of act4cap27 project info at other project's event (physical or online) C02. 4. exhibition organised by the EC where act4cap27 project and its results are presented (physical or online)	C03. 1. Interview with act4cap27 project info, appearing in written form: newspaper C03. 2. Interview with act4cap27 project info, appearing in broadcasting: TV/radio C03. 3. Interview with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner SM item C03. 4. Interview with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner video C03. 5. Interview with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website	C04. 1. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in written form: press release, newspaper/popular article C04. 2. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in broadcasting: TV/radio C04. 3. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner SM item C04. 4. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner video C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website	C05. 1. Newsletter: issuing act4cap27 project newsletter C05. 2. Newsletter: act4cap27 project info appearing in partner newsletter	C06. 1. Print materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) physical form: used at events C06. 2. Print materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) physical form: used at exhibitions C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo) C06. 4. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published/echoed on project/partner social media C06. 5. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on project/partner website	C07. 1. Radio/TV campaign: act4cap27 project appearance on radio/TV launched by project partner C08. 1. Social media: act4cap27 project appearance on partner SM channels	C08. 2. Social media: act4cap27 project appearance on partner channels	C09. 1. Video: act4cap27 project video appearance on partner channels C09. 2. Video: act4cap27 project video appearance on partner website	C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)
	8	8	2	5	5	6	9	9	7	10	9
act4cap COMDISS KPIs	act4cap COMDISS KPI targets										
COMDISS KPI_01: N° of policy makers engaged	at least 250;	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	target 600 by the end of the project	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	target 200	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
COMDISS KPI_04: N° of users following social media channels	target 800	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
COMDISS KPI_05: N° of video interviews	target: 20	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
COMDISS KPI_06: N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media	target: 30	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0
COMDISS KPI_07: N° of times datasets and documentation downloaded from Zenodo repository	target 35	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
COMDISS KPI_08: N° of scientific publications in international peer-reviewed publications	target 12 by project end	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
COMDISS KPI_09: scientific conferences - N° of organized sessions	target 3 project organized sessions	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1
COMDISS KPI_10: scientific conferences - N° of presentations	20 presentations by project end	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1
COMDISS KPI_11: N° of newsletter subscribers	act4cap newsletter: 150 by project end act4cap27 project info appearing in partner newsletter	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1

APPENDIX 4 QUARTERLY COMMUNICATION DISSEMINATION ACTIVITY REPORT ONLINE FORMS FOR PROJECT PARTNERS

Reporting ACT4CAP27 Partner Communication Activities

What is Communication?

- its objective is to inform and reach out to society at large, show the activities performed, and highlight the use and the benefits the EU-funded project will have for citizens
- its focus is to Inform, promote and communicate project activities AND its results / achievements with clear messages using the right media channels
- its target audiences are multiple audiences OUTSIDE the project's community, incl. citizens, the media, stakeholders
- its timing: from the start of the project until the end

Please add the communication activity your organisation/team carried out in the context of the project.

IMPORTANT! For reporting purposes, please do not forget to upload any proofs (e.g. photos, presentation/poster file) of your COM activity to the WUR SharePoint into the respective folder of your organisation under WP7/T7.2/05 COMDISS reporting: <https://tinyurl.com/bde9vrj4>

You can download your answers after sending in the record.

The database generated behind will be regularly uploaded to the ACT4CAP27 Sharepoint under

WP7 Stakeholder engagement and dissemination > T7-2-COM-DISS-POS-ECORYS > 05 Partners' COMDISS reporting > 00 database from online COMDISS forms.

1. Select your organisation: partner number and partner abbreviation

- 01-WR
- 02-Thuenen
- 03-EUROCARE
- 04-IIASA
- 05-SLU
- 06-UPM
- 07-WU
- 08-PNU
- 09-UNIROMA3
- 10-ECORYS
- 11-POS
- 12-UCL
- 13-JRC

2. In which project quarter (Q) this COM activity took place?

- Q01: 2024: March, April, May (M01-03)
- Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)
- Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)
- Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)
- Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)
- Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)
- Q07: 2025: Sept, Oct, Nov (M19-21)
- Q08: 2025: Dec, 2026: Jan, Febr (M22-24)
- Q09: 2026: March, April, May (M25-27)
- Q10: 2026: June, July, Aug (M28-30)
- Q11: 2026: Sept, Oct, Nov (M31-33)
- Q12: 2026: Dec, 2027: Jan, Febr (M34-36)
- Q13: 2027: March, April, May (M37-39)
- Q14: 2027: June, July, Aug (M40-42)
- Q15: 2027: Sept, Oct, Nov (M43-45)
- Q16: 2027: Dec, 2028: Jan, Febr (M46-48)
- Q17: 2028: March, April, May (M49-51)
- Q18: 2028: June, July, Aug (M52-54)
- Q19: 2028: Sept, Oct, Nov (M55-57)
- Q20: 2028: Dec, 2029: Jan, Febr (M58-60)

3. What was the date of the COM activity?

Please select from the calendar an exact date, or at least an indicative date of the DIS activity.

! In the case of multiple days please give the start date of the COM activity + give the full date range in the "Description" part under point 5.

4. Who? Target audience

The Grant Management System allows for choosing ONLY ONE of the below categories pre-defined by the EU.

*Please choose "Industry, business partners" or "Innovators" category (depending on the nature of the audiences) if more than one specific audience were targeted at the same time by your communication activity.
You can further describe the types of various audiences under the free text of max. 200 characters in the Description part under point 5.*

- Industry, business partners
- Innovators
- Investors
- EU Institutions
- National authorities
- Regional authorities
- Local authorities
- Civil society
- Citizens
- Research communities

5. Add link related to your COM activity, if appropriate:

6. The status of the COM activity:

- Cancelled
- Delivered
- Ongoing
- Postponed

Categorizing the type of COM channel used and type of COM activity performed

You are required to categorize your COM activity in a 3-step process:

- Step 1: select the type of COM channel used
 - Step 2: select the type of COM activity performed
 - Step 3a: in a max. 200 character description give final details of the COM activity performed
 - Step 3b: give how the COM activity performed contributes to specific act4cap27 COMDISS KPIs
-

Instructions for Step 1: Categorize the type of COM channel used

The EU Grant Management System allows for choosing ONLY ONE of the next **pre-defined main COM channel categories**:

- C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)
- C02. Exhibition
- C03. Interview
- C04. Media article
- C05. Newsletter
- C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)
- C07. Radio/TV campaign
- C08. Social media
- C09. Video
- C10. Website
- C11. Other: public repository at act4cap27 Zenodo community

For the full typology of COM activities under COM channel categories and their relation to the act4cap27 COMDISS KPIs please see this assessment: <https://tinyurl.com/yn2s6tyc>

Instructions for Step 2: Categorize the type of COM activity performed

In the next parts we further broke down this C01-C11 list into all possible subtypes of COM activities to enable a coherent reporting across the consortium.

For this COM activity record please **choose ONLY ONE, the most relevant, of the COM activity types listed**.

! If your activity concerns more of the below categories please add them as separate COM records.

An example:

You presented the act4cap27 project at a conference that you did not organize (1) but also distributed project flyers at the event (2), and related to your conference participation you authored a project website newsitem (3), that also appeared on your organisation's website (4), and your conference participation was also published on social media channels of the project (5), and echoed by the social media channels of your organisation (6), and your conference presentation was reposted to the project's Zenodo community page (7) that counts as seven (!) separate COM activity performed, meaning 7 individual records to be added, one each in the following categories:

- C01. 2. event participation/networking (with act4cap27 presentation/poster)
- C06. 1. Print materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) physical form: used at events
- C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner
- C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website
- C08. 1. Social media: act4cap27 project appearance on project SM channels
- C08. 2. Social media: act4cap27 project appearance on partner SM channels
- C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)

7. Step 1: Categorize the type of COM channel used and type of COM activity performed

Choose ONLY ONE of the next **pre-defined main COM channel categories**.

Once you chose the COM channel, you will be directed to select from the subtypology of COM activities.

- C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)
- C02. Exhibition
- C03. Interview
- C04. Media article
- C05. Newsletter
- C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)
- C07. Radio/TV campaign
- C08. Social media
- C09. Video
- C10. Website
- C11. Other: public repository at act4cap27 Zenodo community

C01. Event with external audience

(conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)

8. **C01. Step 2:** Categorize the type of COM activity performed within **C01. Event with external audience**

! Note: internal project meetings/WP meetings do not count, unless external audience (incl. fellow projects in the case of C01. 4. collaboration) are present

- C01. 1. act4cap27 event organisation with external audience
- C01. 2. event participation/networking (with act4cap27 presentation/poster)
- C01. 3. act4cap27 project representation at event (with act4cap27 project flyer)
- C01. 4. act4cap27 cooperation/collaborating with other HE projects: events of info exchange/collaboration activities
- C01. 5. Policy information event with the EC: events organised by the EC where act4cap27 project and its results are presented

9. **C01. Step 3a:** Description of activity related to **C01. Event with external audience** (max. 200 characters, extra characters are cut) include e.g. as appropriate:

- Event name, Venue/place,
- Author/presenter,
- Language(s) of the activity,
- Types and estimated number of stakeholders addressed
- Countries addressed,
- Type and number of communication materials distributed

10. **C01. Step 3b1: the COM activity's contribution to the COMDISS KPI_01: N° of policy makers engaged**

Give the estimated number of stakeholders addressed in relation to this KPI.

Please enter a number greater than or equal to 0

11. **C01. Step 3b2: the COM activity's contribution to the COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs**

Give the types and estimated number of stakeholders addressed in relation to this KPI.

C02. Exhibition

12. **C02. Step 2:** Categorize the type of COM activity performed within **C02. Exhibition**

- C02. 1. physical exhibition: act4cap27 project appearance with printed materials
- C02. 2. online exhibition: act4cap27 project appearance with virtual materials (e.g. pdf, video)
- C02. 3. cooperation/collaborating with other HE projects: exhibition of act4cap27 project info at other project's event (physical or online)
- C02. 4. exhibition organised by the EC where act4cap27 project and its results are presented (physical or online)

13. **C02. Step 3a:** Description of activity related to **C02. Exhibition** (max. 200 characters, extra characters are cut) include e.g. as appropriate:

- Event name, Venue/place,
- Author/presenter,
- Language(s) of the activity,
- Types and estimated number of stakeholders addressed
- Countries addressed,
- Type and number of communication materials distributed

14. **C02. Step 3b1: the COM activity's contribution to the COMDISS KPI_01: N° of policy makers engaged**

Give the types and estimated number of stakeholders addressed in relation to this KPI.

15. **C02. Step 3b2: the COM activity's contribution to the COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs**

Give the types and estimated number of stakeholders addressed in relation to this KPI.

C03. Interview

16. **C03. Step 2:** Categorize the type of COM activity performed within **C03. Interview**

- C03. 1. Interview with act4cap27 project info, appearing in written form: newspaper
- C03. 2. Interview with act4cap27 project info, appearing in broadcasting: TV/radio
- C03. 3. Interview with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner SM item
- C03. 4. Interview with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner video
- C03. 5. Interview with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website

17. **C03. Step 3a:** Description of activity related to **C03. Interview** (max. 200 characters, extra characters are cut) include e.g. as appropriate:

- Event/source name, Venue/place,
- Author/presenter,
- Language(s) of the activity,
- Countries addressed,
- Type and number of communication materials distributed

18. **C03. Step 3b1: the COM activity's contribution to the COMDISS KPI_05: N° of video interviews**

Is this COM activity contributing to the **COMDISS KPI_05: N° of video interviews**?

- Yes
- No

19. **C03. Step 3b2: the COM activity's contribution to the COMDISS KPI_06: N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media**

Is this COM activity directly contributing to the **COMDISS KPI_06: N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media**?

- Yes
- No

C04. Media article

20. **C04. Step 2:** Categorize the type of COM activity performed within **C04. Media article**

- C04. 1. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in written form: press release, newspaper/popular article
- C04. 2. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in broadcasting: TV/radio
- C04. 3. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner SM item
- C04. 4. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner video
- C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website

21. **C04. Step 3a:** Description of activity related to **C04. Media article** (max. 200 characters, extra characters are cut) include e.g. as appropriate:

- Event/source name, Venue/place,
- Author/presenter,
- Language(s) of the activity,
- Countries addressed,
- Publisher

22. **C04. Step 3b: the COM activity's contribution to the COMDISS KPI_06: N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media**

Is this COM activity directly contributing to the **COMDISS KPI_06: N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media**?

- Yes
- No

C05. Newsletter

23. **C05. Step 2:** Categorize the type of COM activity performed within **C05. Newsletter**

- C05. 1. Newsletter: issuing act4cap27 project newsletter
- C05. 2. Newsletter: act4cap27 project info appearing in partner newsletter

24. **C05. Step 3a:** Description of activity related to **C05. Newsletter** (max. 200 characters, extra characters are cut) include e.g. as appropriate:

- Event/source name, Venue/place,
- Author/presenter,
- Language(s) of the activity,
- Countries addressed,
- Publisher

25. **C05. Step 3b1: the COM activity's contribution to the COMDISS KPI_11: N° of newsletter subscribers**

In the case of activity type **C05. 1. Newsletter: issuing act4cap27 project newsletter**, give the number of project newsletter subscribers in relation to this KPI.

26. **C05. Step 3b2: the COM activity's contribution to the COMDISS KPI_11: N° of newsletter subscribers**

In the case of activity type **C05. 2. Newsletter: act4cap27 project info appearing in partner newsletter**, give the number of newsletter subscribers in relation to this KPI.

C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)

27. **C06. Step 2:** Categorize the type of COM activity performed within **C06. Print materials** (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)

- C06. 1. Print materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) physical form: used at events
- C06. 2. Print materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) physical form: used at exhibitions
- C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)
- C06. 4. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)online form: published/echoed on project/partner social media
- C06. 5. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on project/partner website

28. **C06. Step 3a:** Description of activity within **C06. Print materials** (max. 200 characters, extra characters are cut) include e.g. as appropriate:

- Event/source name, Venue/place,
- Author/presenter,
- Language(s) of the activity,
- Countries addressed,
- Type and number of communication materials distributed

29. **C06. Step 3b: the COM activity's contribution to the COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs**

Give the types and estimated number of stakeholders addressed in relation to this KPI.

C07. Radio/TV campaign

30. **C07. Step 2:** Categorize the type of COM activity performed within **C07. Radio/TV campaign**

- C07. 1. Radio/TV campaign: act4cap27 project appearance on radio/TV launched by project partner

31. **C07. Step 3a:** Description of activity within **C07. Radio/TV campaign** (max. 200 characters, extra characters are cut) include e.g. as appropriate:

- Event/source name, Venue/place,
- Author/presenter,
- Language(s) of the activity,
- Countries addressed,
- Type and number of communication materials distributed

32. **C07. Step 3b: the COM activity's contribution to the COMDISS KPI_06: N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media**

Is this COM activity directly contributing to the **COMDISS KPI_06: N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media?**

Yes

No

C08. Social media

33. **C08. Step 2:** Categorize the type of COM activity performed within **C08. Social media**

- C08. 1. Social media: act4cap27 project appearance on project SM channels
- C08. 2. Social media: act4cap27 project appearance on partner SM channels

34. **C08. Step 3a:** Description of activity within **C08. Social media** (max. 200 characters, extra characters are cut) include e.g. as appropriate:

- Type of social media channel: LinkedIn, Twitter, etc. used
- Topic
- Language(s) of the activity

35. **C08. Step 3b: the COM activity's contribution to the COMDISS KPI_04: N° of users following social media channels**

Is this COM activity directly contributing to the **COMDISS KPI_04: N° of users following social media channels?**

- Yes
- No

C09. Video

36. **C09. Step 2:** Categorize the type of COM activity performed within **C09. Video**

- C09. 1. Video: act4cap27 project video appearance on project channels
- C09. 2. Video: act4cap27 project video appearance on partner channels

37. **C09. Step 3a:** Description of activity within **C09. Video** (max. 200 characters, extra characters are cut) include e.g. as appropriate:

- Event/source name, Venue/place,
- Author/presenter,
- Language(s) of the activity,
- Countries addressed,
- Type of video channel used

38. **C09. Step 3b: the COM activity's contribution to the COMDISS KPI_05: N° of video interviews**

Is this COM activity contributing to the **COMDISS KPI_05: N° of video interviews**?

- Yes
- No

C10. Website

39. **C10. Step 2:** Categorize the type of COM activity performed within **C10. Website**

- C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner
- C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website

40. **C10. Step 3a:** Description of activity within **C10. Website** (max. 200 characters, extra characters are cut) include e.g. as appropriate:

- Event/source name, Venue/place,
- Author/presenter,
- Language(s) of the activity,
- Countries addressed,
- Type and number of communication materials distributed

41. **C09. Step 3b: the COM activity's contribution to the COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website**

Is this COM activity contributing to the **COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website?**

- Yes
- No

C11. Other: public repository: act4cap27 Zenodo community

42. **C11. Step 2:** Categorize the type of COM activity performed within **C11. Other: public repository: act4cap27 Zenodo community**

act4cap27 project item deposited to <https://zenodo.org/communities/act4cap27-eu-project/>

Resource types that can be deposited:

- dataset
- event
- image (diagram, drawing, figure, other, photo, plot)
- lesson
- model
- other
- physical object
- poster
- presentation
- publication (annotation collection, book, book chapter, conference paper, conference proceeding, data paper, dissertation, journal, journal article, other, output management plan, patent, peer review, preprint, project deliverable, project milestone, proposal, report, software documentation, standard, taxonomic treatment, technical note, thesis, working paper)
- software (incl. computational notebook)
- video/audio
- workflow

C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)

43. **C11. Step 3a:** Description of activity within **C11. Other: public repository: act4cap27 Zenodo community** (max. 200 characters, extra characters are cut) include e.g. as appropriate:

- Describe the type of resource deposited (see list under previous question)

give any further details as appropriate:

- Event/source name, Venue/place,
- Author/presenter,
- Language(s) of the activity
- Publisher, DOI etc.

44. **C09. Step 3b1: the COM activity's contribution to the COMDISS KPI_07: N° of times datasets and documentation downloaded from Zenodo repository**

Is this COM activity contributing to the **COMDISS KPI_07: N° of times datasets and documentation downloaded from Zenodo repository?**

Yes

No

45. **C09. Step 3b2: the COM activity's contribution to the COMDISS KPI_08: N° of scientific publications in international peer-reviewed publications**

Is this COM activity contributing to the **COMDISS KPI_08: N° of scientific publications in international peer-reviewed publications?**

Yes

No

46. **C09. Step 3b3: the COM activity's contribution to the COMDISS KPI_10: scientific conferences - N° of presentations**

Is this COM activity contributing to the **COMDISS KPI_10: scientific conferences - N° of presentations**?

Yes

No

Closing Section

47. Any other comments or suggestions to improve reporting.

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Microsoft. The data you submit will be sent to the form owner.

 Microsoft Forms

Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

D7.2 Communication, Dissemination and Impact Strategy and Plan and Reporting

Appendix 5: Visual Identity Guide

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1. COMPLIANCE WITH THE PROJECT VISUAL GUIDELINES

This Visual Identity Guide has been designed to ensure that throughout the 5 years of operation of the ACT4CAP27 project the members of the project consortium can prepare their communication materials in a coherent way. This manual includes the usage rules of the communication elements aimed at promoting the ACT4CAP27 project and acknowledgement of the EU funding.

These visual identity guidelines are in line with the obligations of beneficiaries regarding information and communication, dissemination, open science and visibility measures covered in Articles 16 and 17, and Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement Nr. 101134874.

1.1. Visibility and Disclaimer - European flag and funding statement

The common branding for all EU-funded actions is the EU emblem.

In any ACT4CAP27 related communication activities (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The reference to the European Union under the flag uses the typeface Arial as described in art 4, §4 of the Commission implementing regulation (EU) No 821/2014. This font must not be changed.

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

Rules and downloads for the European Union flag can be found at:

- [Graphics guide to the European flag \(emblem\)](#)
- [The use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes 2021-2027](#)
- [Download the EU emblem and funding statement in different languages](#)

1.2. Project logo and visual identity

1.2.1. The ACT4CAP27 project logo

The logo of the project plays a role of utmost significance in creating brand association regarding visual communication.

The visual appearance of the project logo reflects the multitude and interlinks within the topic that the ACT4CAP27 project investigates.

The project logo must be always included in all communication materials produced. It must be placed in a central and visible top position of the material (in the first/main page).

1.2.1.1. Logo specification

The elements of the logo represent a unit which is defined as invariable. The horizontal and vertical versions of the project logo are both available

1.2.1.2. Logo use

Standard logo / Full colour version

The standard logo is the full colour version. This version should be used whenever possible.

Ideally, the logo should be used on white or light backgrounds.

Figure 1 Horizontal and vertical version of the full colour standard logo

Black and white logo / monochrome logo

For single colour reproductions, black and white / one colour monochrome blue logo version of the logo should be used. These versions should only be used whenever full colour is not available. These versions are recommended when applied through serigraphy and engraving procedures or/and on restrictive surfaces of certain materials - e.g. stickers – whenever the full-colour version of the logo cannot be applied.

Figure 2 Examples of the horizontal and vertical versions of the logo in monochrome

Negative logo

This version of the logo should be used whenever we are using reflex blue background.

Figure 3 Logo in negative

1.2.1. The ACT4CAP27 Symbol

The symbol in the project logo reflects the interconnectedness of topics and economic models.

Symbol use

Standard symbol / Full colour version

The standard symbol is the full colour version. This version should be used whenever possible. It is rarely used without the logo. Contrary to the full colour logo version, the full colour symbol can be used on both white and reflex blue backgrounds.

Greyscale symbol

The greyscale symbol version is used is used partly on printed materials and on internal documents. It is always used on white background.

Negative symbol

This version of the symbol should be used whenever we are using reflex blue background.

Figure 4 Examples of the various versions of the project symbol

Watermark symbol

The light blue symbol version is used when we want to reach a watermark effect.

Figure 5 The watermark version of the project symbol

1.2.2. The project's colour scheme

The colours were chosen to create a harmonic system with colours that match each other.

Figure 6 The project's colour scheme

The various colour code types reflect colour use in different media.

Pantone: Spot colours. For special printing, the PANTONE colour scale will be used.

CMYK: Process-colour printing, 100 colour gradations per channel.

C = cyan, M = magenta, Y = yellow, K = black

The CMYK colours code will be used for all printed materials.

RGB: Colour sample for monitor display with 256 gradations per channel R = red, G = green, B = blue

On the website and other electronic applications, the RGB colour scale, created through graphic software colour conversion, will be used.

Hex: System similar to RGB, however with gradations from "00" to "FF" (hexadecimal) per channel. This system is preferably employed for designing websites.

1.2.2.1. Colours of the ACT4CAP27 project logo and project symbol

The colours of the BrightSpace project logo and project symbol are also based on the light blue and middle blue colours of the project's colour scheme.

1.2.2.2. Graph colours

Recommended colours that can be used in graphs are indicated in the figure below.

Figure 7 Recommended colours to be used in graphs are full colours of the project colour scheme

1.3. Typography

1.3.1. Typeface of the project logo

The typeface of the project name in the project logo is Gil Sans nova.

Gill Sans Nova

Figure 8 Gill Sans Nova typeface

1.3.2. Typeface of other documents

For ease-of-use Microsoft’s most recent typeface Aptos is used in the project for generic text in MS Word, Excel and Powerpoint.

1.3.3. Typefaces used in the project website

With careful and consistent use, our primary typefaces, Montserrat and Open Sans will make our communications recognizable and distinctive in the project website.

Titles and subtitles are typed in Montserrat, and for free-flow text we use the Open Sans typeface.

Optimized for print, web and mobile interfaces, with excellent legibility characteristics in its letterforms, [Open Sans](#) is available free for all mediums and performs well on both Windows and Macintosh operating systems.

Open Sans

Open Sans

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

QRTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

qrstuvwxyz

1234567890

Figure 9 Open Sans typeface

The typefaces in the project website are installed onto the hosting webserver and be loaded to readers' computers from this server to avoid violation of data protection principles.¹

1.4. Don'ts: Improper use of the project logo

Do not make the text disproportionately bigger or smaller compared to the project emblem.

Do not use the project name without the project emblem.

Do not use any colour other than specified in Section 1.2.2.1.

Do not mix up project title and emblem.

¹ When using Google Fonts via the Google Servers, the visitor's browser will download the font files directly from Google. Google therefore will receive the IP, Browser information and more from the visitor and may use this for its own purposes. Various data protection authorities already confirmed that this use of Google Fonts is against the GDPR principles of data minimization.

Do not use coloured logo on dark blue background.

Do not mix up the colours of the logo.

2. APPLICATION OF THE VISUAL IDENTITY

This chapter provides a series of layouts for different communication materials in line with the visual identity rules mentioned in the previous chapter. The list of examples not being exhaustive, the project visual requirements apply to all communication materials produced at project level in written, online, electronic or audio/visual formats. The correct implementation of the guidelines will imply a consistent and coherent visual identity for the ACT4CAP27 project.

2.1. Poster

Size: A/0, 841 x 1189 mm. The generic project poster provides basic information about the project (project title, partners, contacts), including the financial support from the EU, that is aimed to be used for project presentations in general.

2.2. Website

The act4cap27.eu project website fully adheres to the rules laid down in this visual identity guide. WP7 T7.2 COM-DISS leader POS updates the project website regularly with content provided by partners and designed to attract new visitors during the whole project implementation.

The project website includes:

- Information fields with data from the project documentation: project summary, partnership, etc.
- Dynamic information: news and events, project results, etc.

2.3. Newsletter

Newsletters will be issued every 6 months of the project with updated content. A regular newsletter is a key tool to inform the relevant target audiences about the evolution of the ACT4CAP27 project implemented in the framework of the Horizon Europe Programme.

An email ToC alert for subscribers to the newsletter will be sent whenever new issue in pdf will be published on the project website. A layout template has been designed for the pdf version of the newsletter.

The length of newsletters can vary according to the subjects covered, but the header page will clearly identify the Project. In the proposed layout the upper banner and the footer would be constant while the contents are variable.

2.4. Event materials and document templates

The project representatives who organise or participate in events such as conferences and congresses, in connection with the ACT4CAP27 project should display the ACT4CAP27 logo and the EU funding emblem and the funding reference to the Horizon Europe Programme on all the documents, publications, presentations or other materials made available during the event. Moreover, it is highly recommended to take pictures to document the progress of the project and events.

Document template in Word, deliverable report template in Word and PowerPoint template for presentations are available for project partners at the WR SharePoint project site. Further templates are to be created upon need.

2.5. Online communication

The general requirements mentioned in this Visual Identity Guide are applicable to all online communications including social media channels, video and podcast channels.

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<https://act4cap27.eu>

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101134874>

<http://tinyurl.com/ACT4CAP27OpenAIRE>

ACT4CAP²⁷

Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

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PROJECT WEB SITE:	https://act4cap27.eu/

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Deliverable “**D7.2 M18 Update to Deliverable D7.2 (D21) Communication, Dissemination and Impact Reporting**” gives an overview of the communication and dissemination (COMDISS) activities of the ACT4CAP27 consortium in the first 18 months of project duration.

Communication-dissemination activities are under continuous monitoring of the Task 7.2 “Joint project external communication and results dissemination activities” leader POS.

The objectives of project communication and project result dissemination activities are:

- to maximise the visibility of the project to the intended target groups from the agricultural, environmental policy- and decision-making stakeholder community, administrations, and scientific community;
- to disseminate project outcomes to stakeholders, key actors and end-users; and
- to support implementation of
 - Task 7.1 by facilitating outreach and engagement of key actors, and potential users of project results; and
 - Task 7.3 by promoting the exploitation of project results and coordinate preparations for post-project exploitation.

Communication and dissemination activities are carefully planned, continuously implemented and regularly monitored during the whole duration of the project. All project partners are involved in dissemination and exploitation in order to foster awareness and transfer results for impact at European, Member State and regional levels and in their own communities.

Communication and dissemination activities are carried out according to **Communication, Dissemination and Impact Strategy and Plan** (Deliverable 7.2, M6) which analysed the dissemination target groups and matched them with the most appropriate channels, key messages for communication, and external partners with whom to cooperate on co-dissemination whenever relevant.

One representative of each consortium partner team was assigned as Communication-Dissemination- Officer (COMDISS Officers) after the project kick-off meeting in month 5.

Communication and dissemination (COMDISS) Officers continuously keep records of partner’s Communication and dissemination activities in online forms developed for this purpose. With regular intervals POS summarizes and analyses partner’s communication and dissemination efforts by communication channels and modes of dissemination which is then presented at meetings of the Executive Board and at project annual meetings.

A multi-platform outreach approach to dissemination brings ACT4CAP27 results close to end users, highlighting why and how outcomes will benefit target audiences. All non-confidential products generated are made freely and openly available through multiple channels. An essential activity is the design and running of a Europe-wide dissemination campaign with the aims of:

- creating stakeholder awareness of the project as a whole;
- disseminating results;
- promoting capacity building and developing the AMYRN network of a new generation of policy modelling professionals;
- creating the basis for a significant legacy of project outcomes;
- disseminating success stories of achievements of ACT4CAP27 to promote adoption of the approaches to sharing knowledge, add value, lever resources and promote project innovations amongst end-user and stakeholder communities.

The strategy and plan for documenting, monitoring and evaluation of COMDISS activities performed by the project consortium were set out **in M6 in Section 7 of D7.2.**

In this document we report about the performance of these procedures undertaken during the first 18 months of the project, including:

- COMDISS as a regular agenda point at monthly Executive Board meetings;
- COMDISS activity reports by all partners delivered in every project quarter,
- impact assessment of:
 - central COMDISS channels of the project: statistics on the use, reach and engagement of the website and social networks,
 - partners' COMDISS activities: multiplication of central channels' messages through their own networks, and performing own activities e.g. organizing and participating in relevant events.

The **impact assessment** is made against:

- the Interval 1 (M1-18) of the COMDISS Implementation Plan that was set out **in M6 in Section 6 of D7.2.,**
- COMDISS KPIs that were set out **in M6 in Section 7.3.1 of D7.2.**

1. MONITORING AND PRESENTATION OF COMDISS ACTIVITIES

The strategy and plan for documenting, monitoring and evaluation of COMDISS activities performed by the project consortium were set out *in M6 in Section 6 of D7.2*.

In this section we report about the performance of these procedures undertaken during the first 18 months of the project, including:

- COMDISS as a regular agenda point at monthly Executive Board meetings;
- COMDISS activity reports by all partners delivered in every project quarter,
- impact assessment of:
 - central COMDISS channels of the project: statistics on the use, reach and engagement of the website and social networks,
 - partners' COMDISS activities: multiplication of central channels' messages through their own networks and performing own activities, e.g. participation in relevant events.

1.1. COMDISS at Executive Board meetings and at Annual meetings

COMDISS is a fixed topic on the agenda of monthly Executive Board meetings, where COMDISS task leader POS reports about the most recent activities and upcoming campaigns.

Task leader POS informs the whole consortium about the performance of COMDISS also at annual meetings.

1.2. COMDISS activity reports of partners

COMDISS Officers are in charge of keeping track of, and documenting each partner's COMDISS activities in quarterly COMDISS reports in online forms and deposit proofs of activities at the project's SharePoint system, to enable assessment of performance, and as an input to the central technical reporting on the communication and dissemination activities performed by the consortium.

COMDISS activity reports of partners are aggregated and analysed by COMDISS Task Leader POS, and used for the impact assessment of the relevant sections of this report. The aggregated tables of partners' COMDISS Progress Reports are available in **Appendix 1**.

1.3. Communication and dissemination channels

A set of specific communication-dissemination channels were set up at the beginning of the project based on the principles of:

- adaptability (to address the project's research themes and stakeholder communities),
- flexibility (a responsive framework to changing needs and challenges),
- tailored messages in appropriate language,
- exploitation of synergies (cross-fertilisation with existing communication and dissemination activities).

These principles are to ensure that the project can fully exploit its strengths and opportunities, while limiting and managing its weakness and threats.

1.3.1. Project website

The communication-dissemination of the project is organised using several different channels. One of the main communication-dissemination channels is the project website operating under the domain: act4cap27.eu (Error! Reference source not found.). The www site was set up at the beginning of the project and went online in July 2024.

The ACT4CAP27 project website is a key tool for communicating information about project activities, news and events, as well as to convey results to target groups and interested audience.

The website was created in line with the visual identity and is continuously maintained by POS with contributions from all partners.

Figure1. Start page of the act4cap27.eu website

The website covers the following main sections:

- **About:** introduction to the ACT4CAP27, its work packages, project partners and the Scientific and Policy Advisory Board (SPAB)
- **News:** items about project activities and results
- **Events:** upcoming and past events that are relevant for ACT4CAP27's audiences
- **Platform:** is a highlight page for fostering *stakeholder engagement*, with contact form and specific news about stakeholder events.
- **Capacity building:** is a highlight page for presenting ACT4CAP27's training sessions on modelling, and the Agri-Food Modelling Young Researcher Network (AMYRN) with specific news sections
- **Resources:** is a section for all project results and outputs including publications, newsletters, videos, deliverables, etc. and other useful links.
- **Newsletters:** is a page containing a form for subscribers and also enlists published editions.

Google Analytics was set up right at the launch of the project website at the end of July 2024 to track the website traffic. The analytics for the website performance are detailed in **Appendix 2**.

1.3.2. Communication of ACT4CAP27 on partner websites

Partners use their own organisation websites as communication channels. All partners that have separate websites have uploaded basic information about ACT4CAP27 project in English or in the relevant national language. Partners also use their webpages news sections to announce the news about the project (e.g. release of newsletters). Examples of ACT4CAP27 project information on the partners’ website in English or in national language:

- <https://www.wur.nl/en/project/advancing-capacity-and-analytical-tools-for-supporting-common-agricultural-policies-post-2027-act4cap27.htm>
- <https://www.thuenen.de/en/newsroom/news/detail/neues-eu-projekt-act4cap27-gestartet-1>
- <https://www.thuenen.de/de/institutsuebergreifende-projekte/modellierung-der-gemeinsamen-agrarpolitik-politiken-nach-2027>
- <https://agmemod.eu/projects/ongoing-projects>
- http://www.eurocare-bonn.de/projects/cap_trade/Act4CAP27/Act4CAP27.htm
- <https://iiasa.ac.at/projects/act4cap2027>
- <https://agrifood.se/engProject.aspx?fKeyID=279>
- <https://ceigram.upm.es/en/noticia/the-act4cap27-project-is-launched-designing-more-sustainable-european-agricultural-policies/>
- <https://economia.uniroma3.it/ricerca/progetti-di-ricerca/progetti-europei/>
- <https://possessio-ltd.eu/>

1.3.3. Social media channels

Communication and dissemination activities are actively carried out through project social media channels. A LinkedIn company page is used to reach the professional audience, X and Bluesky are aimed at reaching both professionals and the general public.

The X (formerly Twitter) channel was first established in March 2024 through which posts are provided right from the beginning of the project’s launch. As the growing importance of other social media platforms and the diminishing importance of X as social media platform among the project’s target audiences were acknowledged were the LinkedIn account and latest the BlueSky account established. **Figure 2** shows the home page of the ACT4CAP27 Bluesky account.

Key data of these channels are summarized in **Table 1**, the detailed analytics for LinkedIn are in **Appendix 3**. The analytic data collection for the Bluesky account has been recently set (ref. <https://bsky-analytics.com/profiles/act4cap27.eu>) therefore no meaningful data is yet available. X analytics is no longer available for free and we do not have subscription for Premium.

Table 1 Summary of key data of ACT4CAP27 social media channels

SM account name	SM account address	date of account opening	number of followers as of 12/08/2025
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/act4cap27-eu-project/	09/2024	140
BlueSky	https://bsky.app/profile/act4cap27.eu	02/2025	30
X	https://x.com/ACT4CAP27	03/2024	51

Figure 2. Headers of social media accounts on LinkedIn, Bluesky and X all follow the project’s visual identity and convey key information including EU funding acknowledging

Social media posts on LinkedIn with engaging video content include:

- 🚀 ACT4CAP2 Annual Meeting – Day 1 in Rome! (views: 320)
<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7300314869294129152>
- Driving EU Agricultural Policy Forward 🌱 EU: ACT4CAP27, BrightSpace, and Lamasus Collaborate 🤝 (views: 165)
<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7288298967308636161>
- 🙌 Many thanks to all participants of the 1st Stakeholder Meeting of ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project for their valuable contributions! (views: 239)
<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7254857886504247297>
- 📺 #ACT4CAP27 was introduced to EC officers & representatives of fellow projects today at the European Research Executive Agency (REA) Horizon EU projects Cluster meeting in Brussels (views: 274)
<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7254583594025689089>

Cross promotion between the project’s social media channels is also regularly issued to increase number of followers (Figure 3).

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7296910972877729793>

Figure 3. Example of cross promoting the project’s social media channels

1.3.4. Communication on partner social media channels

Partners effectively use their social media accounts to help multiply central messages thereby to reach their networks with project information, and also various forms of communications are made, including original posts, reposts, replies to relevant posts with ACT4CAP27 mention (Figure 4).

<https://x.com/ACT4CAP27/status/1948459027463065766>

<https://x.com/ACT4CAP27/status/1933465482339799191>

<https://www.linkedin.com/embed/feed/update/urn:li:share:7339235375439065089>

Figure 4. Examples of partner communications through their social media accounts

1.3.5. Open Access repositories

ACT4CAP27 's OpenAIRE page

<https://tinyurl.com/act4cap27-OpenAIRE>

ACT4CAP27 's Zenodo Community site

<https://zenodo.org/communities/act4cap27-eu-project/>

The ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community page is indexed in OpenAIRE and is part of the EU Open Research Repository Zenodo Community.

All partners are welcome to contribute with uploads to the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community repository page. All uploads will receive a DOI. Any uploads will appear publicly on the page, once it is authorised by the page's current curator POS.

In line with the D8.2 Data Management Plan Zenodo is used in the project to provide open access to project results and databases. The Zenodo community site of ACT4CAP27 is now widely promoted through our website and also through our social media channels (Figure 5).

<https://zenodo.org/communities/act4cap27-eu-project/>
<https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-zenodo-community/>
<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7361115161404825600>
<https://bsky.app/profile/act4cap27.eu/post/3lw7zr7v6is2i>
<https://x.com/ACT4CAP27/status/1955348473701654959>

Figure 5. The ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community page and its promotion banner used on all project communication channels

Records at the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community page with view and download statistics - as of 12 August 2025 - are listed in **Appendix 4**.

1.3.6. Project newsletters

The electronic newsletter (Figure 6) is published every 6 months.

The generic structure of the newsletters includes various sections:

- an editorial article from the project coordinator addressed in a format of a letter to the ACT4CAP27 Community with highlights of activities and results of the project period covered
- latest news from the project
- thematic focus articles, e.g. highlights from Ukraine, capacity building & AMYRN, networking and cooperation with other Horizon Europe projects
- highlights from our fellow projects
- upcoming events

In the first 18 months of the project **two issues of project newsletter were published in December 2024 and in June 2025**, that were deposited to the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community page, but also listed on the project website's Newsletters page <https://act4cap27.eu/newsletters/> and also under the Resources section of the website <https://act4cap27.eu/resources/newsletters/>.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14290353

Figure 6. Sample pages of the 1st project newsletter

The newsletter is promoted through all digital communication channels of the project (Figure 7), but also during on-site events. An announcement about the release and readers to subscribe is published on the News section of the project website and through social media channels. Invitation is sent to all project partners to publish on their organization’s web sites and social media accounts.

<https://act4cap27.eu/newsletters/>

<https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-mid-year-newsletter-coming-soon-catch-up-on-our-2025-highlights/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7339235376592486402>

Figure 7. Promotion campaign for the 2nd project newsletter on LinkedIn and Newsletters subscription page on project website

Subscription to the project newsletters is possible through filling in the form on the bottom of the project webpage, and also in the specific page dedicated to project newsletters. Subscription to the newsletter is regularly promoted through the project’s website and social media channels.

Newsletter subscriptions are handled in MailerLite. Subscribers received the following invitation to their inboxes for the first two issues of the newsletter:

- <https://preview.mailerlite.io/preview/1035168/emails/140054440646280942>
- <https://preview.mailerlite.io/preview/1035168/emails/157029634603484271>

The total number of active subscribers is 96 as of 12 August 2025.

The 3rd newsletter will be issued in winter 2025. The 6-monthly newsletters are compiled and edited by POS with contributions of all partners.

1.4. Dissemination Materials and Publications

1.4.1. Project flyer

The initial version of the project flyer in EN was specifically developed for and distributed at the EU Agricultural Outlook Conference (6-7 December 2023) with assistance from the BrightSpace project (Figure 8).

Source: BrightSpace:
<https://brightspace-project.eu/brightspace-was-represented-at-the-eu-agricultural-outlook-conference/>

Figure 8. Communication of the then soon starting ACT4CAP27 at the EC Agri Outlook Conference

Based on the initial prototype the operational project flyer in EN has been finalized in 2024, and then updated in 2025. **Appendix 5.** A template for assisting partner language translations was also developed.

During the 2nd Annual meeting the EN version of the project flyer was distributed among partners (20 pcs per partner) for use during their upcoming project communication activities.

A major campaign within the consortium to get the flyer translated into the consortium’s languages was agreed at the 1st annual meeting, and by mid-June in 2025 the project flyer in digital pdf format was made available also in DE, ES, HU, IT, NL, SV, UA national languages through the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community page, and under the Other publications of the Resources menu of the project website: <https://act4cap27.eu/resources/other-publications/>

The launch of the national versions was accompanied by a promotion campaign through the project's central channels (Figure 9).

<https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-project-flyers-now-available-in-all-consortium-languages/>

Figure 9. Promotion campaign of the national language versions of the project flyer

Partners can print national language flyers according to their needs.

1.4.2. Press releases, non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publications, popular articles

Press releases (**Appendix 6**) issued during each of the General Assembly meetings that are also available on the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community page.

Press releases are promoted through all the digital channels of the project (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Promotion of press releases and news items about project annual meetings

1.4.3. Open Access Scientific publications

ACT4CAP27 results are about to emerge from month 18 onwards. Currently there is one OA scientific publication available, listed on the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community page and also promoted through all the central communication channels of the project (Figure 11):

Nicola Caravaggio, Giuliano Resce, Cristina Vaquero-Piñeiro, Predicting policy funding allocation with Machine Learning, Socio-Economic Planning Sciences, Volume 98, April 2025, 102175, ISSN 0038-0121 DOI [10.1016/j.seps.2025.102175](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seps.2025.102175)

<https://zenodo.org/records/14879592>

<https://act4cap27.eu/new-open-access-article-from-act4cap27-in-socio-economic-planning-sciences/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7296944110790205440>

<https://bsky.app/profile/act4cap27.eu/post/3licrds6q722d>

<https://x.com/ACT4CAP27/status/1891179364194177398>

Figure 11. Example of promoting open access results

1.4.4. Infographics

Based on inputs from partners COMDISS Task Leader Possessio designed A0 size infographic posters (**Appendix 7**) that were used at the 1st stakeholder meeting to assist an easy understanding of ACT4CAP27 scenarios during the discussions with stakeholders (Figure 17).

Furthermore, Possessio also assists partners with revising presentation slides and giving suggestions for better visual interpretations (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Example of a suggestion for better visual interpretation

1.4.5. Policy briefs

Annual Policy briefs are planned in ACT4CAP27 as specific deliverables.

D7.5 Policy brief 1 was submitted in Month 9 [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14290211](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14290211) , and D7.6 Policy brief 2 is due in Month 18, see **Appendix 8**.

Policy briefs are deposited to the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community page as deliverables, and also referenced in the Policy briefs section of the Resources page on the project website: <https://act4cap27.eu/resources/policy-briefs/>

The issue of policy briefs is also accompanied by a promotion campaign (Figure 13).

<https://act4cap27.eu/1st-act4cap27-policy-brief-is-out/>

Figure 13. Promotion of the 1st policy brief

1.4.6. Rollup banner and digital backdrop

A printed roll-up banner **Appendix 9** and specific projected screens are used as backdrop for documenting at in-person project events. Example of digital backdrop used at the kick-off meeting in 03/2024, and at the annual meeting in 02/2025 (Figure 14).

Group photo at the Kick-off Meeting, 18-19 March, 2024, The Hague

Figure 14. Digital backdrops and rollup banner used at project meetings

1.4.7. Promotional items

At the annual meeting in Rome 02/2025 enamel pins (26*14 mm) and thermos bottles (Figure 15) with the project logo and EU funding acknowledgement were distributed among project partners, for further use at physical events to promote the project. The correct use of EU emblem with funding statement on these project promo objects was consulted with and approved by the Visual Identity Communications service of the EC (comm-visual-identity@ec.europa.eu) in an email exchange.

Figure 15. Promotional items used by project partners

1.5. Events: participation

All project partners are very active in presenting the ACT4CAP27 project to peer groups, including science, policy and practice. Some examples are presented in Figure 16.

Presentation materials, as appropriate, are uploaded to the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo community page.

<https://act4cap27.eu/roma-tre-university-act4cap27-team-presented-cometogether-cooperation-as-a-sustainable-economic-driver-in-italian-wine-industry/>

<https://act4cap27.eu/roma-tre-university-represented-act4cap27-at-the-joint-workshop-of-european-association-of-wine-economists-university-of-tokaj/>

<https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-contribution-highlights-dutch-livestock-policy-challenges-at-188th-eaae-seminar-in-crete/>

<https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-represented-at-188th-eaae-seminar-by-thunen-team/>

<https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-presented-at-the-65th-annual-scientific-meeting-of-the-italian-society-of-economics/>

<https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-project-spotlighted-at-green-digital-polissia-agriculture-forum/>

Figure 16. Examples of ACT4CAP27 presented or represented at external events

1.6. Events: organisation

1.6.1. Organisation of stakeholder meetings

Task 7.1 Stakeholders’ engagement led by Ecorys is to ensure the co-creation of knowledge between intended groups of stakeholders and project partners, and maintaining continuous dialogue with the EC and support stakeholder involvement at all stages of the ACT4CAP27 project in the forms of organising physical stakeholder meetings (Figure 17) and on-line stakeholder consultations (Figure 18).

<https://act4cap27.eu/1st-stakeholder-meeting-of-the-act4cap27-project-23-october-2024-brussels-be/>

Figure 17. Post-event communication item of the 1st stakeholder meeting displaying infographic posters used at the event

<https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-stakeholder-consultation-on-the-future-of-the-cap/>

Figure 18. Communication item of an online stakeholder consultation

1.6.2. Organisation of capacity building activities

Task 5.4 Capacity building on modelling led by UPM, modelling partners organize trainings to ensure the future generations of agricultural policy modellers. These events are also supported by project communications campaigns on all central project channels, and also via a dedicated section on the project website. <https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building/> This highlights page hosts two subsections:

- training sessions on modelling (Figure 19) <https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building/training-sessions-on-modelling/>
- promoting the activities of the AMYRN: Agri-Food Modelling Young Researcher Network (Figure 20) <https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building/amyrn/>

<https://act4cap27.eu/workshop-recap-agmemod-june-2025/>

<https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building-capri-course-2025-open-for-registration/>

<https://act4cap27.eu/capri-gitlab-training-10-june-2025/>

<https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building-capri-developer-seminar-11-12-march-2025-berlin-germany-2/>

Figure 19. Examples of communication items about capacity building events

<https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building-act4cap27-amyrn/>

Figure 20. Promoting AMYRN

1.6.3. Organisation of side-event workshops

The ACT4CAP27 project hosted a hybrid workshop on modelling the future of EU-Ukraine relations on 18 September 2024 at the Warsaw University of Life Sciences (SGGW), Poland. Organized by the Thünen Institute of Market Analysis (Germany), Wageningen Economic Research (Netherlands), and Polissia National University (Ukraine), this workshop was a side event to the 189th EAAE Seminar, titled “EU Enlargement by (Post)-War Ukraine: Implications for the Agri-Food Markets” (Figure 21).

<https://act4cap27.eu/wp6-workshop-on-modelling-the-future-of-eu-ukraine-relationship-18-september-2024/>

Figure 21. ACT4CAP27 Workshop banner as a side event to the 189th EAAE Seminar

1.7. Cooperation and collaborating with other Horizon projects

Synergies are sought with a number of fellow projects through

- i) participation at each other’s project meetings and exchange of materials,
- ii) organizing joint events,
- iii) harmonizing dissemination actions,
- iv) joint communication and dissemination campaigns,
- v) cross referencing in project newsletters,
- vi) establishing links between websites and social media channels.

Contact with the Horizon Europe project BrightSpace is well established. BrightSpace project coordinator Marc Müller from WSER took part in the ACT4CAP27 project kick-off meeting, and complementarities of the two projects, as well as opportunities of shared activities were discussed (Figure 22).

<https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-collaborates-with-fellow-project-brightspace/>

Figure 22. Fields of collaboration were discussed with BrightSpace at the ACT4CAP27 kick-off meeting

A good working contact was established with the Tools4CAP HE project. Topics of cooperation focus on organizing joint events (e.g. see AGMEMOD 2025 training in Figure 19), harmonizing dissemination actions, cross referencing in project newsletters, establishing links between websites and social media channels.

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_agrifooddays-policymodelling-horzoneurope-activity-7272281334738280448-G2WT

Figure 23. Communicating about ACT4CAP27 at the Agri-food Days in 2024 together with LAMASUS, BrightSpace and MINDSTEP

A remarkable example of collaboration result with HE projects is the perspective paper jointly developed by colleagues from the ACT4CAP27, BrightSpace and LAMASUS projects. This joint work was communicated in several items over time, and the paper launch also covered in a joint press release (Figure 24).

<https://act4cap27.eu/driving-eu-agricultural-policy-forward-act4cap27-brightspace-and-lamasus-collaborate/>

<https://act4cap27.eu/perspective-paper-on-the-future-of-agriculture-presented-at-dg-agri/>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.16413131

<https://act4cap27.eu/perspective-paper-launch/>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.16413127

Figure 24. Communication items about the joint paper development and launch

1.8. Participation at policy information events organised by the EC and international organizations

Communication channels supported by the European Commission are used for news about events and results. ACT4CAP27 is proactive in utilizing the various opportunities of engagement with actors from the EC and world-wide, as well as responding to requests for information or invitations for participation in events (Figure 25 / Figure 26).

<https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-presented-at-horizon-projects-clustering-workshop/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7272651418056998915>

<https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-at-the-eu-vision-conference-on-agriculture-and-food-8-may-2025-brussels-be/>

Figure 25. Examples of ACT4CAP27 project communications at EC organised events

<https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-at-oecd-conference-28-october-paris-fr/>

Figure 26. ACT4CAP27 represented at OECD conference

2. IMPACT ASSESSMENT

The **impact assessment** is made against:

- the Interval 1 (M1-18) of the COMDISS Implementation Plan that was set out *in M6 in Section 6 of D7.2.*,
- COMDISS KPIs that were set out *in M6 in Section 7.3.1 of D7.2.*

2.1. Assessment against Interval 1 (M1-18) of the COMDISS Plan

The project communication activities within Interval 1 include:

- initializing the development of communication and media tools,
- general communications about the project (its ambition, aims, objectives, expected results, targeted messages for awareness raising of stakeholders) and its implementation (including due milestones reached) through e.g. press releases, project newsletter, popular articles, events.
- supporting other WPs with communicating about their activities,
- initialising networking activities with relevant projects, and initiatives at national and EU levels.

Project communication and media tools planned and made available within Interval 1 are listed in Table 2.

Table 2 Project communication and media tools planned and made available within Interval 1

Nr	Item name	month of delivery planned	actual month of delivery	further info
1	project visual identity – logo, project message, templates	08/2024	03/2024	D7.2 M6 Appendix 5
2	social media accounts: LinkedIn, X, YouTube	08/2024	08/2024 + Bluesky in 02/2025	D7.2 M18 Section 1.3.3.
3	project website (D7.4)	08/2024	07/2024	D7.4
4	ACT4CAP27 Zenodo community	03/2024	03/2024	D7.2 M18 Section 1.3.5.
5	press-release on 1st General Assembly	03/2024	03/2024	10.5281/zenodo.10828112
6	project rollup	03/2024	03/2024	D7.2 M18 Section 1.4.6.
7	project general flyer prototype in English, subsequent language versions	EN:03/2024	EN:03/2024 other languages: 06/2025	D7.2 M18 Section 1.4.1.
8	6-monthly newsletters	10/2024 04/2025	12/2024 06/2025	10.5281/zenodo.14290353 10.5281/zenodo.15652506
9	press-release on 2 nd General Assembly	03/2025	02/2025	10.5281/zenodo.14922040
10	communications about M1 milestone (of WP1, WP2) reached: conceptual framework and sustainable food system dimensions/indicators discussed and validated in 1 st Stakeholder Meeting	M9: 11/ 2024	10/ 2024 05/ 2025	website link website link

Dissemination activities within Interval 1 have not much relevance, as the first deliverable (D4.1) is due in month 15, and more to come in Interval 2. Dissemination of deliverables may start after

being submitted to the EC, and the open release of public deliverables before the EC's approval is contingent on the decision of the project's management board.

2.2. Evaluation of activities against COMDISS Key Performance Indicators

Data are as of 17 August 2025.

Table 3 Evaluation of activities against COMDISS Key Performance Indicators

Impact Nr	Indicator	Means of monitoring and evaluating	Targets for the project lifetime	Actual value for the reporting period
KPI_01	N° of policy makers engaged	this is a stakeholder engagement indicator Numbers reached at C01. Event with external audience	at least 250;	see activities reported under T7.1 153
KPI_02	N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Numbers reached at C01. Event with external audience Number of views (V) + downloads (D) of policy briefs from Zenodo	target 600 by the end of the project	260 policy brief #01: V: 44 + D: 46 total: 350
KPI_03	N° of users accessing project website	Number of website hits (cumulative). Metrics from website analytics tool	target 200	210
KPI_04	N° of users following social media channels	Number of followers on LinkedIn + Bluesky + X	target 800	264 + 141 + 51= 456
KPI_05	N° of video interviews	Number of video interviews available on the project's communication channels	target: 20	0 video interviews 4 social media posts with video
KPI_06	N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media	Number of views (V) + downloads (D) of press release items from Zenodo	target: 30	project kick-off V:266 +D:160 annual meeting 2025: V:33+D:41 joint paper: V:96+D:75
KPI_07	N° of times datasets and documentation downloaded from Zenodo repository	Number of views (V) + downloads (D) of project deliverables / working paper / presentations from Zenodo	target 35	deliverable: V: 44 + D: 46 working paper: V:320 +D:247 presentations: V:275+D:221
KPI_08	N° of scientific publications in international peer-reviewed publications		target 12 by project end	1
KPI_09	scientific conferences - N° of organised sessions		target 3 project organized sessions	0
KPI_10	scientific conferences - N° of presentations		20 presentations by project end	15
KPI_11	N° of newsletter subscribers	number of subscribers in Mailer Lite	act4cap newsletter: 150 by project end	96

APPENDIX 1 AGGREGATED TABLES OF PARTNERS' COMDISS PROGRESS REPORTS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
01-WSER	COM-001	Q01: 2024: Mar ch, April, May (M01-03)	3-xx-2024	Civil society	https://www.wur.nl/en/project/advancing-capacity-and-analytical-tools-for-supporting-common-agricultural-policies-post-2027-act4cap27.htm	Delivered	C10. Website	C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website	Act4CAP27 project reference on partner website	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	No	No
01-WSER	COM-002	Q01: 2024: Mar ch, April, May (M01-03)	3-18-2024	Media representatives	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10828112	Delivered	C04. Media article	C04. 1. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in written form: press release, newspaper/popular article	Press release: Launch of the ACT4CAP27project	COMDISS KPI_06: N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media	Zenodo views: 270 Zenodo downloads: 162	POS
01-WSER	COM-003	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)	7-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/read-our-press-release-launch/ https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-kick-off-in-the-hague/ https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-collaborates-with-fellow-project-brightspace/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-003 POS, WSER Read our press release: Launch of the ACT4CAP27 Project to Shape Future EU Agri-Food Policies WEB-004 POS, WSER ACT4CAP27 Kick-off in The Hague WEB-005 POS, WSER ACT4CAP27 collaborates with fellow project BrightSpace	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website		POS, WSER
01-WSER	COM-004	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)	7-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/planning-the-1st-stakeholder-meeting/ https://act4cap27.eu/save-the-date-act4cap27-projects-1st-stakeholder-meeting/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-009 ECORYS, POS, WSER Planning the 1st stakeholder meeting WEB-011 ECORYS, POS ACT4CAP27 Project's 1st Stakeholder Meeting, 23 October 2024, Brussels, BE – save the date	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS, ECORYS
01-WSER	COM-005	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	9-18-2024	Research communities	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14292596	Delivered	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	presentation material	Current situation and implications of a Ukraine accession to the EU - JONGENEEL, R., VAN LEEUWEN, M., GONZALEZ, A. This material was presented at the ACT4CAP27 WP6 Workshop on Modelling the Future of EU-Ukraine Relationship	COMDISS KPI_10: scientific conferences - N° of presentations	Zenodo views: 39 Zenodo downloads: 40	
01-WSER	COM-006	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	9-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/wp6-workshop-on-modelling-the-future-of-eu-ukraine-relationship-18-september-2024/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-019 THÜNEN, WSER, POLISSIA, POS WP6 Workshop on Modelling the Future of EU-Ukraine Relationship 18 September 2024	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	THÜNEN , WSER, POLISSIA , POS
01-WSER	COM-007	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct,	10-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/clustering-workshop-22-october-brussels-be/	Delivered	C04. Media article	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in	WEB-020 POS, WSER Clustering workshop, 22 October, Brussels, BE	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users	yes	WSER, POS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
		Nov (M07-09)					C10. Website	act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner		accessing project website		
01-WSER	COM-008	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	10-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-presented-at-horizon-projects-clustering-workshop/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-022 POS, WSER ACT4CAP27 presented at Horizon projects' Clustering Workshop	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WSER, POS
01-WSER	COM-009	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	10-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/1st-stakeholder-meeting-of-the-act4cap27-project-23-october-2024-brussels-be/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-023 ECORYS, POS, WSER 1st Stakeholder Meeting of the ACT4CAP27 Project, 23 October 2024, Brussels BE	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	ECORYS, POS, WSER
01-WSER	COM-010	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	11-25-2024	Policy stakeholders	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14290211	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Deliverable D7.5 Policy brief: Advancing Capacity & Analytical Tools for Supporting Common Agricultural Policies Post-2027	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 44 Zenodo downloads: 46	POS
01-WSER	COM-011	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	12-07-2024	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14290353	Delivered	C05. Newsletter	C05. 1. Newsletter: issuing act4cap27 project newsletter	ACT4CAP27 Project Newsletter / Edition 1 / December 2024	COMDISS KPI_11: N° of newsletter subscribers	Zenodo views: 109 Zenodo downloads: 112	POS
01-WSER	COM-012	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	12-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/1st-act4cap27-policy-brief-is-out/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-031 POS, WSER 1st ACT4CAP27 Policy Brief is Out	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS, WSER
01-WSER	COM-013	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	01-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/wp8-workpackage-leaders-meeting-14-january-2025	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website	WEB-034 WSER, POS WP8 work package leaders' meeting 14 January 2025	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WSER, POS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
								C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner				
01-WSER	COM-014	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	02-25-2025	Media representatives	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14922040	Delivered	C04. Media article	C04. 1. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in written form: press release, newspaper/popular article	Press release: ACT4CAP27 Annual Consortium Meeting 2025	COMDISS KPI_06: N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media	Zenodo views: 36 Zenodo downloads: 43	POS
01-WSER	COM-015	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	02-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/read-our-press-release-act4cap27-annual-consortium-meeting-25-26-february-2025-rome-italy/ https://act4cap27.eu/annual-meeting-2025-summary-day-1/ https://act4cap27.eu/annual-meeting-2025-summary-day-2/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-043 WSER, POS, UNIROMA3 Read our press release: ACT4CAP27 Annual Consortium Meeting, 25-26 February 2025, Rome, Italy WEB-044 POS, WSER, UNIROMA3 Annual Meeting 2025 – Summary Day 1 WEB-045 POS, WSER, UNIROMA3 Annual Meeting 2025 – Summary Day 2	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WSER, POS, UNIROMA3
01-WSER	COM-016	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	02-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building-act4cap27-amyrn/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-047 WSER, POS Capacity Building: ACT4CAP27 Agricultural Model Young Researcher Network (AMYRN)	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WSER, POS
01-WSER	COM-017	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	03-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/wp8-workpackage-leaders-meeting-18-march-2025/ https://act4cap27.eu/agmemod-training-2025/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-050 WSER, POS WP8 work package leaders' meeting 18 March 2025 WEB-051 WUR, POS Capacity building: AGMEMOD Training Course, 17-20 June, 2025, The Hague, NL	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WSER, POS
01-WSER	COM-018	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	05-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/wp8-workpackage-leaders-meeting-15-april-2025/ https://act4cap27.eu/in-memoriam-professor-luca-salvatici/ https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-at-the-eu-vision-conference-on-agriculture-and-food-8-may-2025-brussels-be/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-055 WSER, POS WP8 work package leaders' meeting 15 April 2025 WEB-059 WSER, POS In memoriam Professor Luca Salvatici WEB-061 POS, WSER ACT4CAP27 at the EU Vision Conference on Agriculture and Food, 8 May 2025, Brussels, BE WEB-062 WSER, POS WP8 work package leaders' meeting 20 May 2025, online WEB-063 WSER, POS Meet the Scientific & Policy Advisory Board of ACT4CAP27	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WSER, POS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
					https://act4cap27.eu/wp8-workpackage-leaders-meeting-20-may-2025-online/ https://act4cap27.eu/meet-the-scientific-policy-advisory-board-of-act4cap27/							
01-WSER	COM-019	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15652506	Delivered	C05. Newsletter	C05. 1. Newsletter: issuing act4cap27 project newsletter	ACT4CAP27 Project Newsletter / Edition 2 / June 2025	COMDISS KPI_11: N° of newsletter subscribers	Zenodo views: 64 Zenodo downloads: 52	POS
01-WSER	COM-020	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655078	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Projektflyer: ACT4CAP27: Weiterentwicklung von Kapazitäten und Analyseinstrumenten zur Unterstützung der Gemeinsamen Agrarpolitik nach 2027	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 11 Zenodo downloads: 10	Thünen, POS
01-WSER	COM-021	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655264	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Folleto del proyecto: ACT4CAP27: Mejora de la capacitación y de las herramientas analíticas para el apoyo de la Política Agraria Común a partir de 2027	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 10 Zenodo downloads: 9	UPM, POS
01-WSER	COM-022	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655340	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Projektismertető: AT4CAP27: Elemzési eszközök fejlesztése és modellezési kapacitás építése a 2027 utáni Közös Agrárpolitika támogatásához	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 12 Zenodo downloads: 8	POS
01-WSER	COM-023	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655467	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Volantino del progetto: ACT4CAP27: Competenze e strumenti analitici per supportare la Política Agrícola Comune dopo il 2027	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 9 Zenodo downloads: 9	UNIROM A3, POS
01-WSER	COM-024	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655532	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Projectfolder: ACT4CAP27: Bevordering van de capaciteit en analytische instrumenten ter ondersteuning van het Gemeenschappelijk Landbouwbeleid na 2027	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 12 Zenodo downloads: 12	WSER, POS
01-WSER	COM-025	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655609	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Projektbroschyr: ACT4CAP27: Förbättra kapacitet och analytiska verktyg för att stödja den gemensamma jordbrukspolitiken efter 2027	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 9 Zenodo downloads: 10	SLU, POS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
01-WSER	COM-026	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655672	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Буклет проекту: ACT4CAP27: Розвиток потенціалу аналітичних інструментів для підтримки спільної сільськогосподарської політики після 2027 року	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 10 Zenodo downloads: 11	PNU, POS
01-WSER	COM-027	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655760	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Project flyer: ACT4CAP27: Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 65 Zenodo downloads: 54	POS
01-WSER	COM-028	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-24-2025	Policy stakeholders	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413131	Delivered	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	working paper	Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security	COMDISS KPI_07: N° of times datasets and documentation downloaded from Zenodo repository	Zenodo views: 332 Zenodo downloads: 261	IIASA, WSER, JRC, Thünen, EuroCAR E, POS
01-WSER	COM-029	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-24-2025	Policy stakeholders	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413133	Delivered	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	working paper	Executive summary: Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security	COMDISS KPI_07: N° of times datasets and documentation downloaded from Zenodo repository	Zenodo views: 103 Zenodo downloads: 90	IIASA, WSER, JRC, Thünen, EuroCAR E, POS
01-WSER	COM-030	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-24-2025	Media representatives	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413127	Delivered	C04. Media article	C04. 1. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in written form: press release, newspaper/popular article	Press release: Sustainable Agriculture: A Cornerstone of Europe's Economic Prosperity and Strategic Security	COMDISS KPI_06: N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media	Zenodo views: 101 Zenodo downloads: 77	WS IIASA, WSER, JRC, Thünen, EuroCAR E, ER, POS
01-WSER	COM-031	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/workshop-recap-agmemod-june-2025/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-078 WSER, POS Workshop Recap: AGMEMOD Model & Scenario Building 17-20 June 2025, The Hague	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WSER, POS
01-WSER	COM-032	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	07-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/perspective-paper-launch/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-080 POS, WSER New Joint Paper Highlights Role of Sustainable Agriculture in Securing Europe's Future	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS, WSER

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
01-WSER	COM-033	Q1-Q6		Social media audiences		Delivered	C08. Social media	C08. 2. Social media: act4cap27 project appearance on partner SM channels	<p>Reposting of ACT4CAP27 social media items</p> <p>Hans van Meijl reposts with own comments on LinkedIn https://www.linkedin.com/in/hans-van-meijl-abb25125/recent-activity/all/</p> <p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-ugcPost-7254583499360247810-LRxw/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/hans-van-meijl-abb25125_agrifooddays-policymodelling-horizoneurope-activity-7272377329786535936-SutV/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/hans-van-meijl-abb25125_euagrifooddays-activity-7272681414330920961-zV8m/</p> <p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/hans-van-meijl-abb25125_shaping-the-future-of-eu-agri-food-policy-activity-7300164041652461568-WCC5/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/hans-van-meijl-abb25125_act4cap2-sustainablefoodsystems-collaboration-activity-7300585200109903874-ZJ0O/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/hans-van-meijl-abb25125_act4cap27-agrifoodmodelling-youngresearchers-activity-7310302108291874816-nr3y/</p>	COMDISS KPI_04: N° of users following social media channels	Yes	No
02-Thuenen	COM-001	Q01: 2024: Mar ch, April, May (M01-03)	3-21-2024	Civil society	https://www.thuenen.de/en/institutes/market-analysis/service/detail-news/neues-eu-projekt-act4cap27-gestartet	Delivered	C10. Website	C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website	Act4CAP27 Kick-off meeting and project launch announced. In the news side of https://www.thuenen.de/en/institutes/market-analysis/news and https://www.thuenen.de/en/institutes/farm-economics-in-German-and-English .	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	No	No
02-Thuenen	COM-002	Q01: 2024: Mar ch, April, May (M01-03)	3-22-2024	Research communities	https://www.linkedin.com/analytcs/post-summary/urn:li:activity:7176809331181445120/	Delivered	C08. Social media	C08. 2. Social media: act4cap27 project appearance on partner SM channels	Reposting and commenting on kick-off meeting post	COMDISS KPI_04: N° of users following social media channels	Yes	No
02-Thuenen	COM-003	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)	8-1-2024	Citizens	https://www.thuenen.de/en/cross-institutional-projects/modelling-of-the-common-agricultural-policies-post-2027	Delivered	C10. Website	C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website	Presentation of project on Thünen homepage in German (https://www.thuenen.de/de/institutsuebergreifende-projekte/modellierung-der-gemeinsamen-agrarpolitik-politiken-nach-2027) and English (https://www.thuenen.de/en/cross-institutional-projects/modelling-of-the-common-agricultural-policies-post-2027)	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	Yes	No
02-Thuenen	COM-004	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)	8-1-2024	Research communities	https://agmemod.eu/projects/ongoing-projects	Delivered	C10. Website	C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website	Presentation of project on the AGMEMOD homepage target to all internet users but especially to researchers interested in AGMEMOD. English.	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	No	No

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
02-Thuenen	COM-005	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	9-13-2024	Research communities		Delivered	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)	C01. 2. event participation/networking (with act4cap27 presentation/poster)	Conference presentation titled "Bridging Gaps: Linking Sectoral Models and Individual Dietary Behaviour" by Ferike Thom and Alexander Gocht at 188th EAAE (European Association of Agricultural Economists) Seminar. Reorienting agri-food chains to hinder climate change and food security threats. Chania, Greece, 12.09. – 13.09.2024	'COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	other researchers	No
02-Thuenen	COM-006	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	9-17-2024	Research communities		Delivered	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)	C01. 1. act4cap27 event organisation with external audience	ACT4CAP27 WP6 WORKSHOP: MODELLING OF FUTURE OF EU-UKRAINE RELATIONSHIP as side event to the 189th EAAE seminar in Warschau, Poland. 29 Participants, mainly scientists but also 2 from business and 2 from policy	COMDISS KPI_01: N° of policy makers engaged COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	2 2	PNU
02-Thuenen	COM-007	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	9-18-2024	Citizens	https://www.thuenen.de/de/newsroom/veranstaltungen/details/agrar-und-lebensmittelketten-zukunftssicher-aufstellen	Delivered	C10. Website	C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website	News about participation at 188th EAAE seminar with presentations linked to Act4CAP27	COMDISS KPI_04: N° of users following social media channels	Yes	No
02-Thuenen	COM-008	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	9-18-2024	Research communities	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7242797978103496704/	Delivered	C08. Social media	C08. 2. Social media: act4cap27 project appearance on partner SM channels	repost of Act4CAP27 info of stakeholder workshop in Warsaw regarding Ukraine accession scenarios with comment in LinkedIn	COMDISS KPI_04: N° of users following social media channels	Yes	
02-Thuenen	COM-009	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	9-27-2024	Research communities		Delivered	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)	C01. 2. event participation/networking (with act4cap27 presentation/poster)	Conference presentation titled "Bridging Gaps: Linking Sectoral Models and Individual Dietary Behaviour" by Ferike Thom and Alexander Gocht at 64. GEWISOLA-annual meeting, Gießen, Germany, 25.09. – 27.09.2024	'COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	other researchers	No
02-Thuenen	COM-010	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	09-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-represented-at-188th-eaae-seminar-by-thunen-team/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-018 THÜNEN, POS ACT4CAP27 represented at 188th EAAE Seminar by Thünen team	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	Thünen, POS
02-Thuenen	COM-011	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	09-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/wp6-workshop-on-modelling-the-future-of-eu-ukraine-relationship-18-september-2024/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website	WEB-019 THÜNEN, WSER, POLISSIA, POS WP6 Workshop on Modelling the Future of EU-Ukraine Relationship 18 September 2024	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	THÜNEN, WSER, POLISSIA, POS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
								C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner				
02-Thuenen	COM-012	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	10-23-2024	EU Institutions	https://act4cap27.eu/1st-stakeholder-meeting-of-the-act4cap27-project-23-october-2024-brussels-be/	Delivered	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)	C01. 1. act4cap27 event organisation with external audience	-1st Stakeholder Meeting of the ACT4CAP27 Project -Davit Stepanyan -English -40 -Policymakers, national representatives, practitioners	COMDISS KPI_01: N° of policy makers engaged 'COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	20 20	all partners
02-Thuenen	COM-013	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	10-29-2024	Research communities		Delivered	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)	C01. 3. act4cap27 project representation at event (with act4cap27 project flyer)	AGMEMOD network meeting; online; short presentation of Act4CAP27 and foreseen role of AGMEMOD in Act4CAP27, presenter: Verena Laquai; 27 AGMEMOD users (researchers) from 10 countries; only short presentation no material distributed	'COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	27	No
02-Thuenen	COM-014	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	11-1-2024	Research communities	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7258131699203489792/	Delivered	C08. Social media	C08. 2. Social media: act4cap27 project appearance on partner SM channels	LinkedIn: Posting of AGMEMOD network meeting. Act4CAP27 was briefly presented there and is also on posted picture.	COMDISS KPI_04: N° of users following social media channels	Yes	No
02-Thuenen	COM-015	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	11-5-2024	Civil society	https://agmemod.eu/events	Delivered	C10. Website	C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website	AGMEMOD network meeting posting with Act4CAP on picture. Was briefly presented at the meeting. English. All AGMEMOD interested persons	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	No	No
02-Thuenen	COM-016	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	11-5-2024	Civil society	https://www.thuenen.de/en/institutes/market-analysis/service/detail-news/agmemod-network-meeting-AND https://www.thuenen.de/de/fachinstitute/marktanalyse/service/detail-aktuelles/agmemod-netzwerktreffen	Delivered	C10. Website	C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website	Post about AGMEMOD network meeting (online), English and German	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	No	No
02-Thuenen	COM-017	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	11-6-2024	Research communities		Delivered	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)	C01. 4. act4cap27 cooperation/collaborating with other HE projects: events of info exchange/collaboration activities	-Brightspace annual meeting, Seville -Davit Stepanyan -English -Researchers and other stakeholders, about 50 participants -Presentation and discussion of possible collaboration with Brightspace and LAMASUS projects designing the policy scenarios	COMDISS KPI_01: N° of policy makers engaged 'COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy	10 50	WSER

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
										and methodological briefs		
02-Thuenen	COM-008	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	2-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building-capri-developer-seminar-11-12-march-2025-berlin-germany/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-038 THÜNEN, POS Upcoming: CAPRI Developer Seminar, 11-12 March 2025, Berlin, Germany	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	THÜNEN, POS
02-Thuenen	COM-019	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	3-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building-capri-developer-seminar-11-12-march-2025-berlin-germany-2/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-046 THÜNEN, POS Capacity Building: CAPRI Developer Seminar, 11-12 March 2025, Berlin, Germany	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	THÜNEN, POS
02-Thuenen	COM-020	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	3-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building-capri-course-2025-open-for-registration/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-052 THÜNEN, POS Capacity Building: CAPRI Course 2025 – Open for Registration!	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	THÜNEN, POS
02-Thuenen	COM-021	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	5-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/wp6-meeting-on-fast-track-scenarios/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-060 THÜNEN, POS WP6 meeting on fast track scenarios	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	Thünen, POS
02-Thuenen	COM-022	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/upcoming-gitlab-training-for-capri-10-june-2025-online/ https://act4cap27.eu/capri-gitlab-training-10-june-2025/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-065 UPM, THÜNEN, POS Upcoming GitLab Training for CAPRI – 10 June 2025, online WEB-066 UPM, THÜNEN, POS CAPRI GitLab Training – 10 June 2025	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	UPM, THÜNEN, POS
02-Thuenen	COM-023	Q06: 2025: June, July,	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655078	Delivered	C06. Print materials	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters,	Projektflyer: ACT4CAP27: Weiterentwicklung von Kapazitäten und Analyseinstrumenten zur	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners	Zenodo views: 11	POS, WSER

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
		Aug (M16-18)					(brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Unterstützung der Gemeinsamen Agrarpolitik nach 2027	reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo downloads: 10	
02-Thuenen	COM-024	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-24-2025	Policy stakeholders	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413131	Delivered	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	working paper	Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security	COMDISS KPI_07: N° of times datasets and documentation downloaded from Zenodo repository	Zenodo views: 332 Zenodo downloads: 261	IIASA, WSER, JRC, Thünen, EuroCAR E, POS
02-Thuenen	COM-025	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-24-2025	Policy stakeholders	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413133	Delivered	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	working paper	Executive summary: Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security	COMDISS KPI_07: N° of times datasets and documentation downloaded from Zenodo repository	Zenodo views: 103 Zenodo downloads: 90	IIASA, WSER, JRC, Thünen, EuroCAR E, POS
02-Thuenen	COM-026	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-24-2025	Media representatives	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413127	Delivered	C04. Media article	C04. 1. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in written form: press release, newspaper/popular article	Press release: Sustainable Agriculture: A Cornerstone of Europe's Economic Prosperity and Strategic Security	COMDISS KPI_06: N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media	Zenodo views: 101 Zenodo downloads: 77	WS, IIASA, WSER, JRC, Thünen, EuroCAR E, POS
02-Thuenen	COM-027	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	07-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/building-capacity-for-evidence-based-policy-capri-training-session-2025-recap/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-079 THÜNEN, POS Building Capacity for Evidence-Based Policy: CAPRI Training Session 2025 Recap	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	THÜNEN, POS
09-UNIROM A3	COM-028	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	07-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-heads-to-the-eaae-congress-in-bonn-%e2%94%b2-26-29-august-2025/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-082 THÜNEN, UNIROMA3, POS ACT4CAP27 Heads to the EAAE Congress in Bonn 26–29 August 2025	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	THÜNEN, UNIROM A3, POS
02-Thuenen	COM-029	Q1-Q6		Social media audiences		Delivered	C08. Social media	C08. 2. Social media: act4cap27 project appearance on partner SM channels	Reposting of ACT4CAP27 social media items by Davit Stepanyan on LinkedIn https://www.linkedin.com/in/davit-stepanyan-dr-067a1555/recent-activity/all/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_on-5-june-wp-leaders-discussed-ideas-of-the-activity-7204849357227982848-DU_9/	COMDISS KPI_04: N° of users following social media channels	Yes	No

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
									https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-horizoneu-europeangreendeal-activity-7237354524921741313-v9dF/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_competitiveness-sustainability-ugcPost-7288298882306916355-hpKF/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-agriculture-sustainability-activity-7296909972674633728-2rQQ/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-agrifoodmodelling-youngresearchers-activity-7310216644499283968-z2_9/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_horizoneurope-cap-visionforagriculture-activity-7354216483343761408-6_7U/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_horizoneurope-act4cap27-capri-activity-7362827102028541953-nvfc/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-at-the-18th-eaae-congress-activity-7362836597546926080-7vnG/ by Verena Laquai https://www.linkedin.com/in/verena-laquai-6051a1300/recent-activity/all/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-ugcPost-7254583499360247810-LRxw/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap2-sustainablefoodsystems-collaboration-ugcPost-730031484888807424-D7OJ/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_shaping-the-future-of-eu-agri-food-policy-activity-730090663004479488-sA5V/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_agmemod-capacitybuilding-economicmodelling-activity-7310590095298904064-5WFL/			

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
03-EuroCAR E	COM-001	Q01: 2024: Mar ch, April, May (M01-03)	3-xx-2024	Civil society	http://www.eurocare-bonn.de/projects/cap_trade/Act4CAP27/Act4CAP27.htm	Delivered	C10. Website	C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website	Act4CAP27 project reference on partner website	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	No	No
03-EuroCAR E	-	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)										
03-EuroCAR E	-	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)										
03-EuroCAR E	-	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)										
03-EuroCAR E	-	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)										
03-EuroCAR E	COM-002	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-24-2025	Policy stakeholders	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413131	Delivered	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	working paper	Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security	COMDISS KPI_07: N° of times datasets and documentation downloaded from Zenodo repository	Zenodo views: 332 Zenodo downloads: 261	IIASA, WSER, JRC, Thünen, EuroCAR E, POS
03-EuroCAR E	COM-003	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-24-2025	Policy stakeholders	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413133	Delivered	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	working paper	Executive summary: Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security	COMDISS KPI_07: N° of times datasets and documentation downloaded from Zenodo repository	Zenodo views: 103 Zenodo downloads: 90	IIASA, WSER, JRC, Thünen, EuroCAR E, POS
03-EuroCAR E	COM-004	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-24-2025	Media representatives	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413127	Delivered	C04. Media article	C04. 1. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in written form: press release, newspaper/popular article	Press release: Sustainable Agriculture: A Cornerstone of Europe's Economic Prosperity and Strategic Security	COMDISS KPI_06: N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media	Zenodo views: 101 Zenodo downloads: 77	WS IIASA, WSER, JRC, Thünen, EuroCAR E, POS
04-IIASA	COM-001	Q01: 2024: Mar ch, April, May (M01-03)	3-xx-2024	Civil society	https://iiasa.ac.at/projects/act4cap2027	Delivered	C10. Website	C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website	Act4CAP27 project reference on partner website	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	No	No
04-IIASA	-	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)										
04-IIASA	-	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)										

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
04-IIASA	-	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)										
04-IIASA	-	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)										
04-IIASA	COM-002	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-24-2025	Policy stakeholders	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413131	Delivered	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	working paper	Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security	COMDISS KPI_07: N° of times datasets and documentation downloaded from Zenodo repository	Zenodo views: 332 Zenodo downloads: 261	IIASA, WSER, JRC, Thünen, EuroCAR E, POS
04-IIASA	COM-003	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-24-2025	Policy stakeholders	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413133	Delivered	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	working paper	Executive summary: Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security	COMDISS KPI_07: N° of times datasets and documentation downloaded from Zenodo repository	Zenodo views: 103 Zenodo downloads: 90	IIASA, WSER, JRC, Thünen, EuroCAR E, POS
04-IIASA	COM-004	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-24-2025	Media representatives	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413127	Delivered	C04. Media articles	C04. 1. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in written form: press release, newspaper/popular article	Press release: Sustainable Agriculture: A Cornerstone of Europe's Economic Prosperity and Strategic Security	COMDISS KPI_06: N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media	Zenodo views: 101 Zenodo downloads: 77	WS IIASA, WSER, JRC, Thünen, EuroCAR E ER, POS
05-SLU	COM-001	Q01: 2024: March, April, May (M01-03)	3-xx-2024	Civil society	https://agrifood.se/engProject.aspx?fKeyID=279	Delivered	C10. Website	C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website	Act4CAP27 project reference on partner website	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	No	No
05-SLU	-	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)										
05-SLU	-	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)										
05-SLU	-	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)										
05-SLU	-	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)										
05-SLU	COM-002	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655609	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Projektbroschyr: ACT4CAP27: Förbättra kapacitet och analytiska verktyg för att stödja den gemensamma jordbrukspolitiken efter 2027	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and	Zenodo views: 9 Zenodo downloads: 10	POS, WSER

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
										methodological briefs		
06- UPM	COM-001	Q01: 2024: March, April, May (M01-03)	3-xx-2024	Civil society	https://ceigram.upm.es/en/noticia/the-act4cap27-project-is-launched-designing-more-sustainable-european-agricultural-policies/	Delivered	C10. Website	C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website	Act4CAP27 project reference on partner website	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	No	No
06- UPM	-	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)										
06- UPM	-	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)										
06- UPM	-	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)										
06- UPM	COM-002	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	04-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-task-5-4-planning-training-activities-for-2025/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-053 UPM, POS ACT4CAP27 Task 5.4 – Planning Training Activities for 2025	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	UPM, POS
06- UPM	-	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)										
06- UPM	COM-003	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/upcoming-gitlab-training-for-capri-10-june-2025-online/ https://act4cap27.eu/capri-gitlab-training-10-june-2025/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-065 UPM, THÜNEN, POS Upcoming GitLab Training for CAPRI – 10 June 2025, online WEB-066 UPM, THÜNEN, POS CAPRI GitLab Training – 10 June 2025	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	UPM, THÜNEN, POS
06- UPM	-	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)										
06- UPM	COM-004	Q1-Q6		Social media audiences		Delivered	C08. Social media	C08. 2. Social media: act4cap27 project appearance on partner SM channels	Reposting of ACT4CAP27 social media items by Maria Blanco on LinkedIn https://www.linkedin.com/in/blancomaria/recent-activity/all/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/blancomaria_act4cap27-euagrifood-sustainability-activity-7174893324087009281-o6aG/	COMDISS KPI_04: N° of users following social media channels	Yes	No

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
									https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-horizoneu-europeangreendeal-ugcPost-7175440464282607616-H9eH/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/hans-van-meijl-abb25125_act4cap27-euagrifood-sustainability-activity-7175906682399543296-sbSL/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-horizoneu-europeangreendeal-activity-7237354524921741313-v9dF/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-horizoneu-europeangreendeal-activity-7250436279337635840-70sl/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/blancomaria-many-thanks-to-all-participants-of-the-activity-7255279979926605825-VIMv/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-ugcPost-7254583499360247810-LRxw/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ceigram-upm_act4cap27-newsletter-december-2024-ugcPost-7272213195698692097-Gjbo/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_agrifooddays-activity-7272260040240091139-0OnY/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap2-sustainablefoodsystems-collaboration-ugcPost-730031484888807424-D7OJ/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/hans-van-meijl-abb25125_act4cap2-sustainablefoodsystems-collaboration-ugcPost-7300585199547875329-OSoS/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-agrifoodmodelling-youngresearchers-activity-731021664499283968-z2_9/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_agmemod-capacitybuilding-economicmodelling-activity-7310590095298904064-5WFL/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_capri-capacitybuilding-agrifoodmodelling-activity-7311347690263502848-Fqiw/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_capri-agmemod-act4cap27-activity-7313880598715031553-LwYp/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/hans-van-meijl-abb25125_act4cap27-agrifoodmodelling-youngresearchers-activity-7310302108291874816-nr3y/			

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
									<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_cap-euagripolicy-euagrivision-activity-7328733409323671553-pvQ8/</p> <p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-horizoneurope-agrifoodpolicy-activity-7339235376592486402-t5o-/</p> <p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-horizoneurope-agrifoodpolicy-activity-7339229625102884865-QuVw/</p> <p>by CEIGRAM-UPM on LinkedIn https://www.linkedin.com/company/ceigram-upm/posts/</p> <p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-horizoneu-europeangreendeal-activity-7237354524921741313-v9dF/</p> <p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_many-thanks-to-all-participants-of-the-ugcPost-7254857831558864896-u9jc/</p> <p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-ugcPost-7254583499360247810-LRxw/</p> <p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_policy-machinelearning-sustainability-activity-7296944110790205440-tVv0/</p> <p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-horizoneurope-agrifoodpolicy-activity-7333121924371316737-R49I/</p>			
07-WU	COM-001	Q01: 2024: Mar ch, April, May (M01-03)	3-xx-2024	Civil society	https://www.wur.nl/en/project/advancing-capacity-and-analytical-tools-for-supporting-common-agricultural-policies-post-2027-act4cap27.htm	Delivered	C10. Website	C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website	Act4CAP27 project reference on partner website	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	No	No
07-WU	-	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)										
07-WU	COM-002	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	09-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-contribution-highlights-dutch-livestock-policy-challenges-at-188th-eaae-seminar-in-crete//	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website	WEB-017 WU, POS ACT4CAP27 Contribution Highlights: Dutch Livestock Policy Challenges at 188th EAAE Seminar in Crete	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WU, POS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
								C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner				
07-WU	-	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)										
07-WU	-	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)										
07-WU	COM-003	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655532	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Projectfolder: ACT4CAP27: Bevordering van de capaciteit en analytische instrumenten ter ondersteuning van het Gemeenschappelijk Landbouwbeleid na 2027	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 12 Zenodo downloads: 12	POS, WSER
08-PNU	-	Q01: 2024: March, April, May (M01-03)										
08-PNU	-	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)										
08-PNU	COM-001	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	09-18-2024	Research communities	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14292802	Delivered	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	presentation material	Ukraine in AGMEMOD and future assumptions regarding policies, demographics, macro economics, production capacities - Bogonos, M, Nazarkina, R., Nykolyuk, O., Pyvovar, P., Rozhkov, O., Stolnikovych, H., Topolnytskiy, P. This material was presented at the ACT4CAP27 WP6 Workshop on Modelling the Future of EU-Ukraine Relationship	COMDISS KPI_10: scientific conferences - N° of presentations	Zenodo views: 22 Zenodo downloads: 18	No
08-PNU	COM-002	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	09-18-2024	Research communities	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14292887	Delivered	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	presentation material	Scenario in AGMEMOD: Ukrainian Producers Separation - Pyvovar,P., Rozhkov, O., Stolnikovych, H. This material was presented at the ACT4CAP27 WP6 Workshop on Modelling the Future of EU-Ukraine Relationship	COMDISS KPI_10: scientific conferences - N° of presentations	Zenodo views: 27 Zenodo downloads: 27	No
08-PNU	COM-003	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	09-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/wp6-workshop-on-modelling-the-future-of-eu-ukraine-relationship-18-september-2024/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-019 THÜNEN,WSER, POLISSIA, POS WP6 Workshop on Modelling the Future of EU-Ukraine Relationship 18 September 2024	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	THÜNEN ,WSER, POLISSIA , POS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
08-PNU	COM-004	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	11-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-presented-at-horizon-europe-cluster-6-information-day-in-ukraine/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-027 POLISSIA, POS ACT4CAP27 presented at Horizon Europe Cluster 6 information day in Ukraine	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	PNU, POS
08-PNU	COM-005	Q04: 2024: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	01-16-2025	Research communities	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14796062	Delivered	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	presentation material	Розвиток потенціалу та аналітичних інструментів для підтримки спільної аграрної політики після 2027 року (Capacity building and analytical tools to support the Common Agricultural Policy after 2027) - Nykolyuk, Olga This material was presented at the forum "GREEN & DIGITAL POLISSIA: AGRICULTURE" on 16 January 2025 at the European Digital Innovation Hub "POLIDIH" at Polissya National University (Ukraine).	COMDISS KPI_10: scientific conferences - N° of presentations	Zenodo views: 77 Zenodo downloads: 53	No
08-PNU	COM-006	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	01-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-project-spotlighted-at-green-digital-polissia-agriculture-forum/	Delivered	C04. Media article	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website	WEB-036 POLISSIA, POS ACT4CAP27 Project Spotligthed at "GREEN & DIGITAL POLISSIA: AGRICULTURE" Forum	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	PNU, POS
08-PNU	COM-007	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	04-24-2025	Research communities	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15465142	Delivered	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	presentation material	Розвиток потенціалу та аналітичних інструментів для підтримки спільної аграрної політики після 2027 року (Development of capacities and analytical tools to support the Common Agricultural Policy after 2027)	COMDISS KPI_10: scientific conferences - N° of presentations	Zenodo views: 33 Zenodo downloads: 27	No
08-PNU	COM-008	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	05-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-presented-at-zhytomyr-dialogue-event/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-057 POLISSIA, POS Strengthening Regional Cooperation: ACT4CAP27 presented at Zhytomyr Dialogue Event 24 April 2025	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	PNU, POS
08-PNU	COM-009	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655672	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Буклет проекту: ACT4CAP27: Розвиток потенціалу аналітичних інструментів для підтримки спільної сільськогосподарської політики після 2027 року	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 10 Zenodo downloads: 11	POS, WSER
09-UNIROM A3	COM-001	Q01: 2024: March, April, May (M01-03)	3-xx-2024	Civil society	https://economia.uniroma3.it/ricerca/progetti-di-ricerca/progetti-europei/	Delivered	C10. Website	C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website	Act4CAP27 project reference on partner website	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	No	No

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
09-UNIROM A3	COM-002	Q01: 2024: Mar ch, April, May (M01-03)	4-xx-2024	Research communities		Delivered	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)	C01. 2. event participation/networking (with act4cap27 presentation/poster)	EUAWE - University of Tokaj Workshop. Joint Workshop of European Association of Wine Economists & University of Tokaj, April 2024, Tokaj, Hungary Presentation of "Come together! Cooperation as a sustainable economic driver in Italian wine industry", Luca Salvatici (Department of Economics, Rossi-Doria Centre, Roma Tre University, Rome, Italy), Cristina Vaquero-Piñeiro (Department of Economics, Rossi-Doria Centre, Roma Tre University, Rome, Italy), Angelo Zago (Department of Economics, Verona University, Italy) Presenting author: Cristina Vaquero-Piñeiro	COMDISS KPI_01: N° of policy makers engaged 'COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	5 5	No
09-UNIROM A3	COM-003	Q01: 2024: Mar ch, April, May (M01-03)	4-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/roma-tre-university-represented-act4cap27-at-the-joint-workshop-of-european-association-of-wine-economists-university-of-tokaj/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-007 UNIROMA3, POS Roma Tre University represented ACT4CAP27 at the Joint Workshop of European Association of Wine Economists & University of Tokaj	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	UNIROM A3, POS
09-UNIROM A3	COM-004	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)	6-20-2024	Research communities		Delivered	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)	C01. 2. event participation/networking (with act4cap27 presentation/poster)	13th AIEAA Conference, June 2024 Bari Italy Presentation of "Come together! Cooperation as a sustainable economic driver in Italian wine industry", Luca Salvatici (Department of Economics, Rossi-Doria Centre, Roma Tre University, Rome, Italy), Cristina Vaquero-Piñeiro (Department of Economics, Rossi-Doria Centre, Roma Tre University, Rome, Italy), Angelo Zago (Department of Economics, Verona University, Italy) Presenting author: Cristina Vaquero-Piñeiro	COMDISS KPI_01: N° of policy makers engaged 'COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	2 10	No
09-UNIROM A3	COM-005	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)	7-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/roma-tre-university-act4cap27-team-presented-cometogether-cooperation-as-a-sustainable-economic-driver-in-italian-wine-industry/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-010 UNIROMA3, POS Roma Tre University ACT4CAP27 Team presented "Come together! Cooperation as a sustainable economic driver in Italian wine industry"	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	UNIROM A3, POS
09-UNIROM A3	COM-006	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	10-24-2024	Research communities		Delivered	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate,	C01. 2. event participation/networking (with act4cap27 presentation/poster)	65th SIE Conference, October 2024 Urbino Italy. Presentation of "Predicting Policy Funding Allocation with Machine Learning". Nicola Caravaggio, Giuliano Resce and Cristina Vaquero-Piñeiro. Presenting author: Cristina Vaquero-Piñeiro	COMDISS KPI_01: N° of policy makers engaged 'COMDISS KPI_02: N° of	10 10	No

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
							round table, group discussion etc.)			practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs		
09-UNIROM A3	COM-007	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	10-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-presented-at-the-65th-annual-scientific-meeting-of-the-italian-society-of-economics/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-025 UNIROMA3, POS ACT4CAP27 Presented at the 65th Annual Scientific Meeting of the Italian Society of Economics	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	UNIROM A3, POS
09-UNIROM A3	COM-008	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	1-30-2025	Research communities		Delivered	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)	C01. 2. event participation/networking (with act4cap27 presentation/poster)	XXIII SIEPI Workshop, January 2024 Bologna Italy. Presentation of "Predicting EU funding success with Machine Learning", Nicola Caravaggio, Giuliano Resce and Cristina Vaquero-Piñero. Presenting author: Cristina Vaquero-Piñero	COMDISS KPI_01: N° of policy makers engaged COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	5 5	No
09-UNIROM A3	COM-009	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	1-31-2025	Research communities	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14835906	Delivered	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	presentation material	XXIII SIEPI Workshop, January 2024 Bologna Italy. Presentation of "Predicting EU funding success with Machine Learning", Nicola Caravaggio, Giuliano Resce and Cristina Vaquero-Piñero. Presenting author: Cristina Vaquero-Piñero	COMDISS KPI_10: scientific conferences - N° of presentations	Zenodo views: 77 Zenodo downloads: 55	
09-UNIROM A3	COM-010	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	01-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-work-presented-at-at-xxiii-siepi-workshop-31-january-2025-bologna-it/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-037 POS, UNIROMA3 ACT4CAP27 work presented at XXIII SIEPI Workshop, 31 January 2025, Bologna, IT	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	UNIROM A3, POS
09-UNIROM A3	COM-011	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	1-31-2025	Research communities	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seps.2025.102175 https://zenodo.org/records/14879592		C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	peer reviewed OA research article	Predicting policy funding allocation with Machine Learning	COMDISS KPI_08: N° of scientific publications in international peer-reviewed publications	Zenodo views: 24 Zenodo downloads: 25	No
09-UNIROM A3	COM-012	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025:	2-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/new-open-access-article-from-	Delivered	C04. Media article	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in	WEB-040 UNIROMA3, POS New Open access Article from	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users	yes	UNIROM A3, POS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
		Jan, Febr (M10-12)			act4cap27-in-socio-economic-planning-sciences/		C10. Website	act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	ACT4CAP27 in Socio-Economic Planning Sciences	accessing project website		
09-UNIROM A3	COM-0013	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	2-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/read-our-press-release-act4cap27-annual-consortium-meeting-25-26-february-2025-rome-italy/ https://act4cap27.eu/annual-meeting-2025-summary-day-1/ https://act4cap27.eu/annual-meeting-2025-summary-day-2/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-043 WSER, POS, UNIROMA3 Read our press release: ACT4CAP27 Annual Consortium Meeting, 25-26 February 2025, Rome, Italy WEB-044 POS, WSER, UNIROMA3 Annual Meeting 2025 – Summary Day 1 WEB-045 POS, WSER, UNIROMA3 Annual Meeting 2025 – Summary Day 2	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WSER, POS, UNIROM A3
09-UNIROM A3	COM-014	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	4-14-2025	Research communities		Delivered	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)	C01. 2. event participation/networking (with act4cap27 presentation/poster)	The 99th Annual Conference of The Agricultural Economics Society. Presentation "The sustainability of agri-food systems: is organic production part of the solution? Presenting author: Cristina Vaquero-Piñeiro	COMDISS KPI_01: N° of policy makers engaged COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	20 30	No
09-UNIROM A3	COM-015	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655467	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Volantino del progetto: ACT4CAP27: Competenze e strumenti analitici per supportare la Politica Agricola Comune dopo il 2027	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 9 Zenodo downloads: 9	POS, WSER
09-UNIROM A3	COM-016	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	07-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-heads-to-the-eaae-congress-in-bonn-%e2%94%82-26-29-august-2025/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-082 THÜNEN, UNIROMA3, POS ACT4CAP27 Heads to the EAAE Congress in Bonn 26–29 August 2025	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	THÜNEN , UNIROM A3, POS
09-UNIROM A3	COM-017	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	8-26-2025	Research communities		Ongoing	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate,	C01. 2. event participation/networking (with act4cap27 presentation/poster)	EAAE Conference. Presentation: The impact of agriculture on climate change: a review of approaches to modelling agricultural emissions Presenting author: Cristina Vaquero-Piñeiro	COMDISS KPI_01: N° of policy makers engaged	50 50	No

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
							round table, group discussion etc.)			'COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs		
10-ECORYS	-	Q01: 2024: March, April, May (M01-03)										
10-ECORYS	COM-001	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)	07-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/planning-the-1st-stakeholder-meeting/ https://act4cap27.eu/save-the-date-act4cap27-projects-1st-stakeholder-meeting/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-009 ECORYS, POS, WSER Planning the 1st stakeholder meeting WEB-011 ECORYS, POS ACT4CAP27 Project's 1st Stakeholder Meeting, 23 October 2024, Brussels, BE – save the date	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS, ECORYS
10-ECORYS	COM-002	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	10-23-2024	Industry, business partners	https://act4cap27.eu/1st-stakeholder-meeting-of-the-act4cap27-project-23-october-2024-brussels-be/	Delivered	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)	C01. 1. act4cap27 event organisation with external audience	Event name: First Stakeholder Meeting Venue: Thon Hotel EU in Brussels, Rue de la Loi 75 1040 Brussels Language: English Types + estimated number of stakeholders: 35 participants in total (from which 17 'external' participants) Countries addressed: number not known Type and number of communication materials distributed: Brochures (number distributed not known), 1 banner shown 17 'externals' = 13 policymakers, 2 business/agri-food association representatives, 2 NGO representatives	COMDISS KPI_01: N° of policy makers engaged 'COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	13 17	all partners
10-ECORYS	COM-003	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	10-23-2024	Industry, business partners		Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 1. Print materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) physical form: used at events	- event: First stakeholder meeting - venue: Thon hotel EU, Rue de la Loi 75, 1040 Brussels - language: English	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	17	No
10-ECORYS	COM-004	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	10-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/1st-stakeholder-meeting-of-the-act4cap27-project-23-october-2024-brussels-be/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-023 ECORYS, POS, WSER 1st Stakeholder Meeting of the ACT4CAP27 Project, 23 October 2024, Brussels BE	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	ECORYS, POS, WSER

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
10-ECORYS	5	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)										
10-ECORYS	COM-004	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	5-6-2025	Industry, business partners	https://act4cap27.eu/upcoming-act4cap27-stakeholder-consultation-6-may-2025-online/	Delivered	C01. Event with external audience (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion etc.)	C01. 1. act4cap27 event organisation with external audience	Event name: Online stakeholder consultation Venue: online Language: English Types and estimated number of stakeholders addressed (34 external participants, 26 internal participants) Countries addressed: 19 countries 34 external participants: 16 policymakers, 1 agri-food chain association representative, 14 (national) research institutes + universities, 2 NGO representatives, 1 other (networking platform)	COMDISS KPI_01: N° of policy makers engaged COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	16 34	all partners
10-ECORYS	COM-006	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	05-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/wp7-preparation-meeting-for-online-stakeholder-consultation/ https://act4cap27.eu/upcoming-act4cap27-stakeholder-consultation-6-may-2025-online/ https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-stakeholder-consultation-on-the-future-of-the-cap/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-054 ECORYS, POS WP7 Preparation meeting for online stakeholder consultation WEB-056 ECORYS, POS Upcoming: ACT4CAP27 Stakeholder Consultation 6 May 2025, online WEB-058 ECORYS, POS ACT4CAP27 Stakeholder Consultation on the Future of the CAP 6 May 2025, online	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	ECORYS, POS
10-ECORYS	-	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)										
11-POS	COM-001	Q01: 2024: March, April, May (M01-03)	3-xx-2024	Civil society	https://possessio-td.eu/	Delivered	C10. Website	C10. 2. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on partner website	Act4CAP27 project reference on partner website	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	No	No
11-POS	COM-002	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)	3-18-2024	Media representatives	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10828112	Delivered	C04. Media article	C04. 1. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in written form: press release, newspaper/popular article	Press release: Launch of the ACT4CAP27project	COMDISS KPI_06: N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media	Zenodo views: 270 Zenodo downloads: 162	WSER
11-POS	COM-003	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)	7-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/read-our-press-release-launch/ https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-kick-off-in-the-hague/ https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-collaborates-with-fellow-project-brightspace/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-003 POS, WSER Read our press release: Launch of the ACT4CAP27 Project to Shape Future EU Agri-Food Policies WEB-004 POS, WSER ACT4CAP27 Kick-off in The Hague WEB-005 POS, WSER ACT4CAP27 collaborates with fellow project BrightSpace	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS, WSER

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
11-POS	COM-004	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)	7-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/icae-2024-2-7-august-2024-new-delhi-india/ https://act4cap27.eu/63rd-ersa-congress/ https://act4cap27.eu/reecap-6th-annual-meeting-24-26-september-2024-cordoba-spain/ https://act4cap27.eu/13th-aieaa-conference-20-21-june-2024-bari-italy/ https://act4cap27.eu/188th-eaae-seminar12-13-september-2024-ciheam-mai-kania-crete-greece/ https://act4cap27.eu/189th-eaae-seminar-18-20-september-2024-warsaw-poland-sggw/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-001 POS ICAE 2024, 2-7 August 2024, New Delhi, India WEB-002 POS 63rd ERSA Congress, 26 – 30 August 2024 Onsite in Terceira Island, Azores, Portugal & Virtual WEB-006 POS REECAP 6th ANNUAL MEETING, 24-26 September 2024, Cordoba, Spain WEB-008 POS 13th AIEAA Conference, 20-21 June 2024, Bari, Italy WEB-012 POS 188th EAAE Seminar, 12-13 September 2024, CIHEAM MAI.Chania, Crete, Greece WEB-013 POS 189th EAAE Seminar, 18-20 September 2024, Warsaw, Poland SGGW	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS
11-POS	COM-005	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)	7-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/roma-tre-university-represented-act4cap27-at-the-joint-workshop-of-european-association-of-wine-economists-university-of-tokaj/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-007 UNIROMA3, POS Roma Tre University represented ACT4CAP27 at the Joint Workshop of European Association of Wine Economists & University of Tokaj	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	UNIROM A3, POS
11-POS	COM-006	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)	7-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/planning-the-1st-stakeholder-meeting/ https://act4cap27.eu/save-the-date-act4cap27-projects-1st-stakeholder-meeting/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-009 ECORYS, POS, WSER Planning the 1st stakeholder meeting WEB-011 ECORYS, POS ACT4CAP27 Project's 1st Stakeholder Meeting, 23 October 2024, Brussels, BE – save the date	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS, ECORYS
11-POS	COM-007	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)	7-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/roma-tre-university-act4cap27-team-presented-come-together-cooperation-as-a-sustainable-economic-driver-in-italian-wine-industry/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-010 UNIROMA3, POS Roma Tre University ACT4CAP27 Team presented “Come together! Cooperation as a sustainable economic driver in Italian wine industry”	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	UNIROM A3, POS
11-POS	COM-008	Q02: 2024: June, July, Aug (M04-06)	8-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/188th-eaae-seminar12-13-september-2024-ciheam-mai-kania-crete-greece/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website	WEB-012 POS 188th EAAE Seminar, 12-13 September 2024, CIHEAM MAI.Chania, Crete, Greece	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
					https://act4cap27.eu/189th-eaae-seminar-18-20-september-2024-warsaw-poland-sggw/			C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-013 POS 189th EAAE Seminar, 18-20 September 2024, Warsaw, Poland SGGW			
11-POS	COM-009	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	9-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/190th-eaae-seminar-13-14-november-2024-wageningen-the-netherlands/ https://act4cap27.eu/191th-eaae-seminar10-14-february-2025-garmisch-partenkirchen-germany/ https://act4cap27.eu/2025-eaae-congress-26-29-august-2025-bonn-germany/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-014 POS 190th EAAE seminar, 13-14 November 2024, Wageningen, the Netherlands WEB-015 POS 191th EAAE Seminar, 10-14 February 2025, Garmisch-Partenkirchen, Germany WEB-016 POS 2025 EAAE Congress, 26-29 August 2025, Bonn, Germany	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS
11-POS	COM-010	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	9-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-contribution-highlights-dutch-livestock-policy-challenges-at-188th-eaae-seminar-in-crete/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-017 WU, POS ACT4CAP27 Contribution Highlights: Dutch Livestock Policy Challenges at 188th EAAE Seminar in Crete	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WU, POS
11-POS	COM-011	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	9-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-represented-at-188th-eaae-seminar-by-thunen-team/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-018 THÜNEN, POS ACT4CAP27 represented at 188th EAAE Seminar by Thünen team	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	Thünen, POS
11-POS	COM-012	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	9-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/wp6-workshop-on-modelling-the-future-of-eu-ukraine-relationship-18-september-2024/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-019 THÜNEN, WSER, POLISSIA, POS WP6 Workshop on Modelling the Future of EU-Ukraine Relationship 18 September 2024	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	THÜNEN ,WSER, POLISSIA , POS
11-POS	COM-013	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	10-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/clusterin-g-workshop-22-october-brussels-be/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27	WEB-020 POS, WSER Clustering workshop, 22 October, Brussels, BE	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WSER, POS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
								project website authored by partner				
11-POS	COM-014	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	10-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-presented-at-horizon-projects-clustering-workshop/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-022 POS, WSER ACT4CAP27 presented at Horizon projects' Clustering Workshop	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WSER, POS
11-POS	COM-015	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	10-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/oecd-conference-28-october-paris-fr/ https://act4cap27.eu/esas-living-planet-symposium-2025-23-27-june-2025-vienna-austria/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-021 POS OECD Conference, 28 October, Paris, FR WEB-024 POS ESA's Living Planet Symposium 2025, 23–27 June 2025 Vienna, Austria	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS
11-POS	COM-016	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	10-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/1st-stakeholder-meeting-of-the-act4cap27-project-23-october-2024-brussels-be/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-023 ECORYS, POS, WSER 1st Stakeholder Meeting of the ACT4CAP27 Project, 23 October 2024, Brussels BE	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	ECORYS, POS, WSER
11-POS	COM-017	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	10-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/clusterin-g-workshop-22-october-brussels-be/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-025 UNIROMA3, POS ACT4CAP27 Presented at the 65th Annual Scientific Meeting of the Italian Society of Economics	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	UNIROMA3, POS
11-POS	COM-018	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	11-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-at-oecd-conference-28-october-paris-fr/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-026 POS ACT4CAP27 at OECD Conference, 28 October, Paris, FR	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS
11-POS	COM-019	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct,	11-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-presented-at-horizon-	Delivered	C04. Media article	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in	WEB-027 POLISSIA, POS ACT4CAP27 presented at	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users	yes	PNU, POS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
		Nov (M07-09)			europa-cluster-6-information-day-in-ukraine/		C10. Website	act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	Horizon Europe Cluster 6 information day in Ukraine	accessing project website		
11-POS	COM-020	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	11-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/1st-act4cap27-newsletter-is-out-soon-subscribe-to-our-newsletter/ https://act4cap27.eu/ffa-conference-1-april-2025-brussels-be/ https://act4cap27.eu/2025-aes-conference-14-16-april-2025-bordeaux-fr/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-028 POS 1st ACT4CAP27 Newsletter Is Out Soon – Subscribe To Our Newsletter WEB-029 POS FFA Conference, 1 April 2025, Brussels, BE WEB-030 POS 2025 AES Conference, 14-16 April 2025, Bordeaux, FR	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS
11-POS	COM-021	Q03: 2024: Sept, Oct, Nov (M07-09)	11-25-2024	Policy stakeholders	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14290211	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Deliverable D7.5 Policy brief: Advancing Capacity & Analytical Tools for Supporting Common Agricultural Policies Post-2027	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 44 Zenodo downloads: 46	WSER
11-POS	COM-022	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	12-07-2024	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14290353	Delivered	C05. Newsletter	C05. 1. Newsletter: issuing act4cap27 project newsletter	ACT4CAP27 Project Newsletter / Edition 1 / December 2024	COMDISS KPI_11: N° of newsletter subscribers	Zenodo views: 109 Zenodo downloads: 112	WSER
11-POS	COM-023	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	12-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/1st-act4cap27-policy-brief-is-out/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-031 POS, WSER 1st ACT4CAP27 Policy Brief is Out	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS, WSER
11-POS	COM-024	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	12-xx-2024	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/eu-agri-food-days-10-12-december-2024-brussels-be/ https://act4cap27.eu/1st-issue-of-newsletter-is-out/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-032 POS EU Agri-Food Days, 10-12 December 2024, Brussels BE WEB-033 POS 1st Issue Of Newsletter Is Out	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS
11-POS	COM-025	Q04: 2024: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	01-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/wp8-workpackage-leaders-meeting-14-january-2025	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website	WEB-034 WSER, POS WP8 workpackage leaders' meeting 14 January 2025	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WSER, POS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* {Specific Key Performance Indicators}	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
								C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner				
11-POS	COM-026	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	01-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/driving-eu-agricultural-policy-forward-act4cap27-brightspace-and-lamasus-collaborate/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-035 POS Driving EU Agricultural Policy Forward: ACT4CAP27, BrightSpace, and LAMASUS Collaborate	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS
11-POS	COM-027	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	01-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-project-spotlighted-at-green-digital-polissia-agriculture-forum/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-036 POLISSIA, POS ACT4CAP27 Project Spotlighted at "GREEN & DIGITAL POLISSIA: AGRICULTURE" Forum	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	PNU, POS
11-POS	COM-028	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	01-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-work-presented-at-xxiii-siepi-workshop-31-january-2025-bologna-it/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-037 POS, UNIROMA3 ACT4CAP27 work presented at XXIII SIEPI Workshop, 31 January 2025, Bologna, IT	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	UNIROM A3, POS
11-POS	COM-029	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	02-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building-capri-developer-seminar-11-12-march-2025-berlin-germany/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-038 THÜNEN, POS Upcoming: CAPRI Developer Seminar, 11-12 March 2025, Berlin, Germany	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	THÜNEN , POS
11-POS	COM-030	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	02-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-annual-meeting-25-26-february-2025-rome-it/ https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-is-now-also-on-bluesky/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-039 POS ACT4CAP27 Annual Meeting, 25-26 February 2025, Rome, IT WEB-042 POS ACT4CAP27 is now also on Bluesky!	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* {Specific Key Performance Indicators}	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
11-POS	COM-031	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	02-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/new-open-access-article-from-act4cap27-in-socio-economic-planning-sciences/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-040 UNIROMA3, POS New Open access Article from ACT4CAP27 in Socio-Economic Planning Sciences	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	UNIROMA3, POS
11-POS	COM-032	Q04: 2024: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	02-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/wp8-workpackage-leaders-meeting-11-february-2025/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-041 WSER, POS WP8 workpackage leaders' meeting 11 February 2025	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WSER, POS
11-POS	COM-033	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	02-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/read-our-press-release-act4cap27-annual-consortium-meeting-25-26-february-2025-rome-italy/ https://act4cap27.eu/annual-meeting-2025-summary-day-1/ https://act4cap27.eu/annual-meeting-2025-summary-day-2/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-043 WSER, POS, UNIROMA3 Read our press release: ACT4CAP27 Annual Consortium Meeting, 25-26 February 2025, Rome, Italy WEB-044 POS, WSER, UNIROMA3 Annual Meeting 2025 – Summary Day 1 WEB-045 POS, WSER, UNIROMA3 Annual Meeting 2025 – Summary Day 2	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WSER, POS, UNIROMA3
11-POS	COM-034	Q04: 2024: Dec, 2025: Jan, Febr (M10-12)	02-25-2025	Media representatives	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14922040	Delivered	C04. Media article	C04. 1. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in written form: press release, newspaper/popular article	Press release: ACT4CAP27 Annual Consortium Meeting 2025	COMDISS KPI_06: N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media	Zenodo views: 36 Zenodo downloads: 43	WSER
11-POS	COM-035	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	03-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building-capri-developer-seminar-11-12-march-2025-berlin-germany-2/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-046 THÜNEN, POS Capacity Building: CAPRI Developer Seminar, 11-12 March 2025, Berlin, Germany	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	THÜNEN, POS
11-POS	COM-036	Q05: 2025: April, May (M13-15)	03-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building-act4cap27-amyrn/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27	WEB-047 WSER, POS Capacity Building: ACT4CAP27 Agricultural Model Young Researcher Network (AMYRN)	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WSER, POS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
								project website authored by partner				
11-POS	COM-037	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	03-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/euractiv-event-agrifood-policy-25-march-2025-brussels-be/ https://act4cap27.eu/ec-conference-on-the-vision-for-agriculture-and-food-8-may-2025-brussels-be/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-048 POS Euractiv Event: AgriFood Policy, 25 March 2025, Brussels, BE WEB-049 POS Upcoming: EC Conference on the Vision for Agriculture and Food, 8 May 2025, Brussels, BE)	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS
11-POS	COM-038	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	03-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/wp8-workpackage-leaders-meeting-18-march-2025/ https://act4cap27.eu/agmemod-training-2025/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-050 WSER, POS WP8 work package leaders' meeting 18 March 2025 WEB-051 WUR, POS Capacity building: AGMEMOD Training Course, 17-20 June, 2025, The Hague, NL	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WSER, POS
11-POS	COM-039	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	03-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building-capri-course-2025-open-for-registration/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-052 THÜNEN, POS Capacity Building: CAPRI Course 2025 – Open for Registration!	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	THÜNEN, POS
11-POS	COM-040	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	04-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-task-5-4-planning-training-activities-for-2025/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-053 UPM, POS ACT4CAP27 Task 5.4 – Planning Training Activities for 2025	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	UPM, POS
11-POS	COM-041	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	05-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/wp7-preparation-meeting-for-online-stakeholder-consultation/ https://act4cap27.eu/upcoming-act4cap27-stakeholder-consultation-6-may-2025-online/ https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-stakeholder-consultation-on-the-future-of-the-cap/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-054 ECORYS, POS WP7 Preparation meeting for online stakeholder consultation WEB-056 ECORYS, POS Upcoming: ACT4CAP27 Stakeholder Consultation 6 May 2025, online WEB-058 ECORYS, POS ACT4CAP27 Stakeholder Consultation on the Future of the CAP 6 May 2025, online	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	ECORYS, POS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
11-POS	COM-042	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	05-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/wp8-workpackage-leaders-meeting-15-april-2025/ https://act4cap27.eu/in-memoriam-professor-luca-salvatici/ https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-at-the-eu-vision-conference-on-agriculture-and-food-8-may-2025-brussels-be/ https://act4cap27.eu/wp8-workpackage-leaders-meeting-20-may-2025-online/ https://act4cap27.eu/meet-the-scientific-policy-advisory-board-of-act4cap27/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-055 WSER, POS WP8 work package leaders' meeting 15 April 2025 WEB-059 WSER, POS In memoriam Professor Luca Salvatici WEB-061 POS, WSER ACT4CAP27 at the EU Vision Conference on Agriculture and Food, 8 May 2025, Brussels, BE WEB-062 WSER, POS WP8 work package leaders' meeting 20 May 2025, online WEB-063 WSER, POS Meet the Scientific & Policy Advisory Board of ACT4CAP27	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WSER, POS
11-POS	COM-042	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	05-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-presented-at-zhytomyr-dialogue-event/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-057 POLISSIA, POS Strengthening Regional Cooperation: ACT4CAP27 presented at Zhytomyr Dialogue Event 24 April 2025	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	PNU, POS
11-POS	COM-044	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	05-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/wp6-meeting-on-fast-track-scenarios/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-060 THÜNEN, POS WP6 meeting on fast track scenarios	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	Thünen, POS
11-POS	COM-045	Q05: 2025: March, April, May (M13-15)	05-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-mid-year-newsletter-coming-soon-catch-up-on-our-2025-highlights/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-064 POS ACT4CAP27 Mid-Year Newsletter Coming Soon – Catch Up on Our 2025 Highlights!	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS
11-POS	COM-046	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/upcomin-g-gitlab-training-for-capri-10-june-2025-online/ https://act4cap27.eu/capri-gitlab-training-10-june-2025/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27	WEB-065 UPM, THÜNEN, POS Upcoming GitLab Training for CAPRI – 10 June 2025, online WEB-066 UPM, THÜNEN, POS CAPRI GitLab Training – 10 June 2025	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	UPM, THÜNEN, POS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
								project website authored by partner				
11-POS	COM-047	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/iamo-forum-18-20-june-2025-halle-de/ https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-project-flyers-now-available-in-all-consortium-languages/ https://act4cap27.eu/14th-aieaa-conference-18-20-june-2025-pisa-it/ https://act4cap27.eu/summer-school-on-risk-analysis-risk-management-and-resilience-in-agriculture-23-27-june-2025-wageningen-nl/ https://act4cap27.eu/7th-international-school-for-advanced-training-23-june-4-july-2025-online/ https://act4cap27.eu/executive-course-on-vision-for-agriculture-and-food/ https://act4cap27.eu/xv-aeaa-congress-3-5-september-2025-granada-es/ https://act4cap27.eu/21st-erdn-conference-23-25-september-2025-bucharest-ro/ https://act4cap27.eu/oecd-green-growth-sustainable-development-forum-2025-2-3-july-2025-paris-fr-online/ https://act4cap27.eu/2nd-issue-of-newsletter-is-out/ https://act4cap27.eu/perspective-paper-on-the-future-of-agriculture-presented-at-dg-agri/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-067 POS IAMO Forum, 18-20 June 2025, Halle, DE WEB-068 POS ACT4CAP27 Project Flyer Now Available in All Consortium Languages WEB-069 POS 14th AIEAA Conference 18–20 June 2025, Pisa, IT WEB-070 POS Summer School on Risk Analysis, Risk Management, and Resilience in Agriculture 23–27 June 2025, Wageningen, NL WEB-071 POS 7th International School for Advanced Training 23 June – 4 July 2025, Online WEB-072 POS Executive Course on the Vision for Agriculture and Food 25-27 June 2025, Online WEB-073 POS XV AEEA Congress 3–5 September 2025, Granada, ES WEB-074 POS 21st ERDN Conference 23–25 September 2025, Bucharest, RO WEB-075 POS OECD Green Growth & Sustainable Development Forum 2025 2–3 July 2025 Paris, FR & Online WEB-076 POS 2nd Issue Of Newsletter Is Out WEB-077 POS Perspective Paper on the Future of Agriculture Presented at DG AGRI	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS
11-POS	COM-048	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/workshop-recap-agmemod-june-2025/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-078 WSER, POS Workshop Recap: AGMEMOD Model & Scenario Building 17–20 June 2025, The Hague	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	WSER, POS
11-POS	COM-049	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15652506	Delivered	C05. Newsletter	C05. 1. Newsletter: issuing act4cap27 project newsletter	ACT4CAP27 Project Newsletter / Edition 2 / June 2025	COMDISS KPI_11: N° of newsletter subscribers	Zenodo views: 64	WSER

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
											Zenodo downloads: 52	
11-POS	COM-050	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655078	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Projektflyer: ACT4CAP27: Weiterentwicklung von Kapazitäten und Analyseinstrumenten zur Unterstützung der Gemeinsamen Agrarpolitik nach 2027	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 11 Zenodo downloads: 10	Thünen, WSER
11-POS	COM-051	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655264	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Folleto del proyecto: ACT4CAP27: Mejora de la capacitación y de las herramientas analíticas para el apoyo de la Política Agraria Común a partir de 2027	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 10 Zenodo downloads: 9	UPM, WSER
11-POS	COM-052	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655340	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Projektismertető: AT4CAP27: Elemzési eszközök fejlesztése és modellezési kapacitás építése a 2027 utáni Közös Agrárpolitika támogatásához	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 12 Zenodo downloads: 8	WSER
11-POS	COM-053	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655467	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Volantino del progetto: ACT4CAP27: Competenze e strumenti analitici per supportare la Politica Agricola Comune dopo il 2027	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 9 Zenodo downloads: 9	UNIROM A3, WSER
11-POS	COM-054	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655532	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Projectfolder: ACT4CAP27: Bevordering van de capaciteit en analytische instrumenten ter ondersteuning van het Gemeenschappelijk Landbouwbeleid na 2027	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 12 Zenodo downloads: 12	WSER, WU
11-POS	COM-055	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655609	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Projektbroschyr: ACT4CAP27: Förbättra kapacitet och analytiska verktyg för att stödja den gemensamma jordbrukspolitiken efter 2027	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 9 Zenodo downloads: 10	SLU, WSER
11-POS	COM-056	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655672	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online form: published on public repository (Zenodo)	Буклет проекту: ACT4CAP27: Розвиток потенціалу аналітичних інструментів для підтримки сільської сільськогосподарської політики після 2027 року	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo views: 10 Zenodo downloads: 11	PNU, WSER
11-POS	COM-057	Q06: 2025: June, July,	06-12-2025	General public	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655760	Delivered	C06. Print materials (brochure,	C06. 3. Materials (act4cap27 brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.) online	Project flyer: ACT4CAP27: Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027	COMDISS KPI_02: N° of practitioners reached with	Zenodo views: 65	WSER

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
		Aug (M16-18)					leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	form: published on public repository (Zenodo)		practice, policy and methodological briefs	Zenodo downloads: 54	
11-POS	COM-058	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-24-2025	Policy stakeholders	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413131	Delivered	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	working paper	Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security	COMDISS KPI_07: N° of times datasets and documentation downloaded from Zenodo repository	Zenodo views: 332 Zenodo downloads: 261	IIASA, WSER, JRC, Thünen, EuroCAR E, POS
11-POS	COM-059	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-24-2025	Policy stakeholders	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413133	Delivered	C11. Other: public repository (act4cap27 Zenodo community)	working paper	Executive summary: Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security	COMDISS KPI_07: N° of times datasets and documentation downloaded from Zenodo repository	Zenodo views: 103 Zenodo downloads: 90	IIASA, WSER, JRC, Thünen, EuroCAR E, POS
11-POS	COM-060	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	06-24-2025	Media representatives	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413127	Delivered	C04. Media article	C04. 1. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in written form: press release, newspaper/popular article	Press release: Sustainable Agriculture: A Cornerstone of Europe's Economic Prosperity and Strategic Security	COMDISS KPI_06: N° of articles and interviews in local and national press and media	Zenodo views: 101 Zenodo downloads: 77	WS IIASA, WSER, JRC, Thünen, EuroCAR E ER, POS
11-POS	COM-061	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	07-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/building-capacity-for-evidence-based-policy-capri-training-session-2025-recap/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-079 THÜNEN, POS Building Capacity for Evidence-Based Policy: CAPRI Training Session 2025 Recap	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	THÜNEN, POS
11-POS	COM-062	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	07-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/perspective-paper-launch/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-080 POS, WSER New Joint Paper Highlights Role of Sustainable Agriculture in Securing Europe's Future	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS, WSER
11-POS	COM-063	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	08-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-zenodo-community/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form: in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-081 POS ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	POS

Pner Nr	Record Nr	Project Quarter	WHEN? (mm-dd-yyyy)	TO WHO? Target audience*	link if appropriate	Status	HOW? Communication channel*	Type of COM activity	Description	Outcome* (Specific Key Performance Indicators)	Outcome value for the related KPI	WHO? Partners involved in the COM action
11-POS	COM-064	Q06: 2025: June, July, Aug (M16-18)	08-xx-2025	website readers	https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-heads-to-the-eaae-congress-in-bonn-%e2%94%82-26-29-august-2025/	Delivered	C04. Media article C10. Website	C04. 5. Media article with act4cap27 project info, appearing in online form; in act4cap27 project/partner website C10. 1. Website: act4cap27 project newsitem appearance on act4cap27 project website authored by partner	WEB-082 THÜNEN, UNIROMA3, POS ACT4CAP27 Heads to the EAAE Congress in Bonn 26–29 August 2025	COMDISS KPI_03: N° of users accessing project website	yes	THÜNEN , UNIROM A3, POS

APPENDIX 2 ANALYTICS OF PROJECT WEBSITE

Performance overview Time range: July 1, 2024 - August 12, 2025

Table A2.1 Website performance

	average value per week	total value over 12 months
Visitors	4.375	210
Page views	22.73	1,091

Table A2.2 Top countries in Europe where website visitors came

country	number of users / page views	country	number of users / page views
NL	25 (11.9%) / 203 (18.61%)	ES	13 (6.19%) / 62 (5.68%)
IT	21 (10%) / 86 (7.88%)	UA	13 (6.19%) / 149 (13.66%)
BE	20 (9.52%) / 57 (5.22%)	AT	11 (5.24%) / 49 (4.49%)
DE	19 (9.05%) / 82 (7.52%)	FR	8 (3.81%) / 22 (2.02%)
CR	18 (8.57%) / 76 (6.97%)	UK	5 (2.38%) / 25 (2.29%)
HU	18 (8.57%) / 111 (10.17%)	DK	4 (1.9%) / 4 (0.37%)

Table A2.3 Most consulted pages

Page title and screen name	Views	Active users
Total	1,091 100% of total	210 100% of total
Home - ACT4CAP27	268 (24.56%)	139 (66.19%)
About - ACT4CAP27	114 (10.45%)	74 (35.24%)
Platform - ACT4CAP27	74 (6.78%)	48 (22.86%)
News - ACT4CAP27	56 (5.13%)	27 (12.86%)
Events - ACT4CAP27	49 (4.49%)	23 (10.95%)
Partners - ACT4CAP27	47 (4.31%)	37 (17.62%)
Capacity building - ACT4CAP27	28 (2.57%)	20 (9.52%)
Resources - ACT4CAP27	27 (2.47%)	23 (10.95%)
Project Advisory Board - ACT4CAP27	25 (2.29%)	16 (7.62%)
Capacity Building: CAPRI Course 2025 – Open for Registration! - ACT4CAP27	21 (1.92%)	13 (6.19%)
Work packages - ACT4CAP27	21 (1.92%)	17 (8.1%)
Capacity Building: ACT4CAP27 Agricultural Model Young Researcher Network (AMYRN) - ACT4CAP27	17 (1.56%)	16 (7.62%)
Annual Meeting 2025 - Summary Day 1 - ACT4CAP27	16 (1.47%)	16 (7.62%)
Stichting Wageningen Research (WR) - ACT4CAP27	16 (1.47%)	9 (4.29%)
Why ACT4CAP27	13 (1.19%)	12 (5.71%)
Capacity building: AGMEMOD Training Course, 17-20 June, 2025, The Hague, NL - ACT4CAP27	12 (1.1%)	8 (3.81%)

Table A2.4 Value of the project website as a communication channel

Impact Nr	Indicators	Means of monitoring and evaluating	Targets for the project lifetime	Actual value for the reporting period
KPI_03	N° of users accessing project website	Number of website hits (cumulative). Metrics from website analytics tool	target 200	210

Table A2.5 Database of news/events items on project website

ID	partners involved	title and link	website section	month published (project quarter)
WEB-001	POS	ICAE 2024, 2-7 August 2024, New Delhi, India https://act4cap27.eu/icae-2024-2-7-august-2024-new-delhi-india/	Events	07/2024 (Q2)
WEB-002	POS	63rd ERSAs Congress, 26 – 30 August 2024 Onsite in Terceira Island, Azores, Portugal & Virtual https://act4cap27.eu/63rd-ersa-congress/	Events	07/2024 (Q2)
WEB-003	POS, WSER	Read our press release: Launch of the ACT4CAP27 Project to Shape Future EU Agri-Food Policies https://act4cap27.eu/read-our-press-release-launch/	News	07/2024 (Q2)
WEB-004	POS, WSER	ACT4CAP27 Kick-off in The Hague https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-kick-off-in-the-hague/	News	07/2024 (Q2)
WEB-005	POS, WSER	ACT4CAP27 collaborates with fellow project BrightSpace https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-collaborates-with-fellow-project-brightspace/	News	07/2024 (Q2)
WEB-006	POS	REECAP 6th ANNUAL MEETING, 24-26 September 2024, Cordoba, Spain https://act4cap27.eu/reecap-6th-annual-meeting-24-26-september-2024-cordoba-spain/	Events	07/2024 (Q2)
WEB-007	UNIROMA3, POS	Roma Tre University represented ACT4CAP27 at the Joint Workshop of European Association of Wine Economists & University of Tokaj https://act4cap27.eu/roma-tre-university-represented-act4cap27-at-the-joint-workshop-of-european-association-of-wine-economists-university-of-tokaj/	News	07/2024 (Q2)
WEB-008	POS	13th AIEAA Conference, 20-21 June 2024, Bari, Italy https://act4cap27.eu/13th-aieaa-conference-20-21-june-2024-bari-italy/	Events	07/2024 (Q2)
WEB-009	ECORYS, POS, WSER	Planning the 1st stakeholder meeting https://act4cap27.eu/planning-the-1st-stakeholder-meeting/	News	07/2024 (Q2)
WEB-010	UNIROMA3, POS	Roma Tre University ACT4CAP27 Team presented “Come together! Cooperation as a sustainable economic driver in Italian wine industry” https://act4cap27.eu/roma-tre-university-act4cap27-team-presented-cometogether-cooperation-as-a-sustainable-economic-driver-in-italian-wine-industry/	News	07/2024 (Q2)
WEB-011	ECORYS, POS	ACT4CAP27 Project’s 1st Stakeholder Meeting, 23 October 2024, Brussels, BE – save the date https://act4cap27.eu/save-the-date-act4cap27-projects-1st-stakeholder-meeting/	Events	08/2024 (Q2)
WEB-012	POS	188th EAAE Seminar, 12-13 September 2024, CIHEAM MAI.Chania, Crete, Greece https://act4cap27.eu/188th-eaae-seminar12-13-september-2024-ciheam-mai-kania-crete-greece/	Events	08/2024 (Q2)
WEB-013	POS	189th EAAE Seminar, 18-20 September 2024, Warsaw, Poland SGGW https://act4cap27.eu/189th-eaae-seminar-18-20-september-2024-warsaw-poland-sggw/	Events	08/2024 (Q2)
WEB-014	POS	190th EAAE seminar, 13-14 November 2024, Wageningen, the Netherlands https://act4cap27.eu/190th-eaae-seminar-13-14-november-2024-wageningen-the-netherlands/	Events	09/2024 (Q3)
WEB-015	POS	191th EAAE Seminar, 10-14 February 2025, Garmisch-Partenkirchen, Germany https://act4cap27.eu/191th-eaae-seminar10-14-february-2025-garmisch-partenkirchen-germany/	Events	09/2024 (Q3)
WEB-016	POS	2025 EAAE Congress, 26-29 August 2025, Bonn, Germany https://act4cap27.eu/2025-eaae-congress-26-29-august-2025-bonn-germany/	Events	09/2024 (Q3)
WEB-017	WU, POS	ACT4CAP27 Contribution Highlights: Dutch Livestock Policy Challenges at 188th EAAE Seminar in Crete https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-contribution-highlights-dutch-livestock-policy-challenges-at-188th-eaae-seminar-in-crete/	News	09/2024 (Q3)
WEB-018	THÜNEN, POS	ACT4CAP27 represented at 188th EAAE Seminar by Thünen team https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-represented-at-188th-eaae-seminar-by-thunen-team/	News	09/2024 (Q3)
WEB-019	THÜNEN, WSER, POLISSIA, POS	WP6 Workshop on Modelling the Future of EU-Ukraine Relationship 18 September 2024 https://act4cap27.eu/wp6-workshop-on-modelling-the-future-of-eu-ukraine-relationship-18-september-2024/	News	09/2024 (Q3)
WEB-020	POS, WSER	Clustering workshop, 22 October, Brussels, BE https://act4cap27.eu/clustering-workshop-22-october-brussels-be/	News	10/2024 (Q3)

ID	partners involved	title and link	website section	month published (project quarter)
WEB-021	POS	OECD Conference, 28 October, Paris, FR https://act4cap27.eu/oeed-conference-28-october-paris-fr/	Events	10/2024 (Q3)
WEB-022	POS, WSER	ACT4CAP27 presented at Horizon projects' Clustering Workshop https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-presented-at-horizon-projects-clustering-workshop/	News	10/2024 (Q3)
WEB-023	ECORYS, POS, WSER	1st Stakeholder Meeting of the ACT4CAP27 Project, 23 October 2024, Brussels BE https://act4cap27.eu/1st-stakeholder-meeting-of-the-act4cap27-project-23-october-2024-brussels-be/	News	10/2024 (Q3)
WEB-024	POS	ESA's Living Planet Symposium 2025, 23–27 June 2025 Vienna, Austria https://act4cap27.eu/esas-living-planet-symposium-2025-23-27-june-2025-vienna-austria/	Events	10/2024 (Q3)
WEB-025	UNIROMA3, POS	ACT4CAP27 Presented at the 65th Annual Scientific Meeting of the Italian Society of Economics https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-presented-at-the-65th-annual-scientific-meeting-of-the-italian-society-of-economics/	News	10/2024 (Q3)
WEB-026	POS	ACT4CAP27 at OECD Conference, 28 October, Paris, FR https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-at-oeed-conference-28-october-paris-fr/	News	11/2024 (Q3)
WEB-027	POLISSIA, POS	ACT4CAP27 presented at Horizon Europe Cluster 6 information day in Ukraine https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-presented-at-horizon-europe-cluster-6-information-day-in-ukraine/	News	11/2024 (Q3)
WEB-028	POS	1st ACT4CAP27 Newsletter Is Out Soon – Subscribe To Our Newsletter https://act4cap27.eu/1st-act4cap27-newsletter-is-out-soon-subscribe-to-our-newsletter/	News	11/2024 (Q3)
WEB-029	POS	FFA Conference, 1 April 2025, Brussels, BE https://act4cap27.eu/ffa-conference-1-april-2025-brussels-be/	Events	11/2024 (Q3)
WEB-030	POS	2025 AES Conference, 14-16 April 2025, Bordeaux, FR https://act4cap27.eu/2025-aes-conference-14-16-april-2025-bordeaux-fr/	Events	11/2024 (Q3)
WEB-031	POS, WSER	1st ACT4CAP27 Policy Brief is Out https://act4cap27.eu/1st-act4cap27-policy-brief-is-out/	News	12/2024 (Q4)
WEB-032	POS	EU Agri-Food Days, 10-12 December 2024, Brussels BE https://act4cap27.eu/eu-agri-food-days-10-12-december-2024-brussels-be/	Events	12/2024 (Q4)
WEB-033	POS	1st Issue Of Newsletter Is Out https://act4cap27.eu/1st-issue-of-newsletter-is-out/	News	12/2024 (Q4)
WEB-034	WSER, POS	WP8 work package leaders' meeting 14 January 2025 https://act4cap27.eu/wp8-workpackage-leaders-meeting-14-january-2025/	News	01/2025 (Q4)
WEB-035	POS	Driving EU Agricultural Policy Forward: ACT4CAP27, BrightSpace, and LAMASUS Collaborate https://act4cap27.eu/driving-eu-agricultural-policy-forward-act4cap27-brightspace-and-lamasus-collaborate/	News	01/2025 (Q4)
WEB-036	POLISSIA, POS	ACT4CAP27 Project Spotlited at "GREEN & DIGITAL POLISSIA: AGRICULTURE" Forum https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-project-spotlighted-at-green-digital-polissia-agriculture-forum/	News	01/2025 (Q4)
WEB-037	POS, UNIROMA3	ACT4CAP27 work presented at XXIII SIEPI Workshop, 31 January 2025, Bologna, IT https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-work-presented-at-xxiii-siepi-workshop-31-january-2025-bologna-it/	News	01/2025 (Q4)
WEB-038	THÜNEN, POS	Upcoming: CAPRI Developer Seminar, 11-12 March 2025, Berlin, Germany https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building-capri-developer-seminar-11-12-march-2025-berlin-germany/	News	02/2025 (Q4)
WEB-039	POS	ACT4CAP27 Annual Meeting, 25-26 February 2025, Rome, IT https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-annual-meeting-25-26-february-2025-rome-it/	News	02/2025 (Q4)
WEB-040	UNIROMA3, POS	New Open access Article from ACT4CAP27 in Socio-Economic Planning Sciences https://act4cap27.eu/new-open-access-article-from-act4cap27-in-socio-economic-planning-sciences/	News	02/2025 (Q4)
WEB-041	WSER, POS	WP8 work package leaders' meeting 11 February 2025 https://act4cap27.eu/wp8-workpackage-leaders-meeting-11-february-2025/	News	02/2025 (Q4)
WEB-042	POS	ACT4CAP27 is now also on Bluesky! https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-is-now-also-on-bluesky/	News	02/2025 (Q4)
WEB-043	WSER, POS, UNIROMA3	Read our press release: ACT4CAP27 Annual Consortium Meeting, 25-26 February 2025, Rome, Italy https://act4cap27.eu/read-our-press-release-act4cap27-annual-consortium-meeting-25-26-february-2025-rome-italy/	News	02/2025 (Q4)

ID	partners involved	title and link	website section	month published (project quarter)
WEB-044	POS, WSER, UNIROMA3	Annual Meeting 2025 – Summary Day 1 https://act4cap27.eu/annual-meeting-2025-summary-day-1/	News	02/2025 (Q4)
WEB-045	POS, WSER, UNIROMA3	Annual Meeting 2025 – Summary Day 2 https://act4cap27.eu/annual-meeting-2025-summary-day-2/	News	02/2025 (Q4)
WEB-046	THÜNEN, POS	Capacity Building: CAPRI Developer Seminar, 11-12 March 2025, Berlin, Germany https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building-capri-developer-seminar-11-12-march-2025-berlin-germany-2/	News	03/2025 (Q5)
WEB-047	WSER, POS	Capacity Building: ACT4CAP27 Agricultural Model Young Researcher Network (AMYRN) https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building-act4cap27-amyrn/	News	03/2025 (Q5)
WEB-048	POS	Euractiv Event: AgriFood Policy, 25 March 2025, Brussels, BE https://act4cap27.eu/euractiv-event-agrifood-policy-25-march-2025-brussels-be/	Event	03/2025 (Q5)
WEB-049	POS	Upcoming: EC Conference on the Vision for Agriculture and Food, 8 May 2025, Brussels, BE https://act4cap27.eu/ec-conference-on-the-vision-for-agriculture-and-food-8-may-2025-brussels-be/	Event	03/2025 (Q5)
WEB-050	WSER, POS	WP8 work package leaders' meeting 18 March 2025 https://act4cap27.eu/wp8-workpackage-leaders-meeting-18-march-2025/	Event	03/2025 (Q5)
WEB-051	WSER, POS	Capacity building: AGMEMOD Training Course, 17-20 June, 2025, The Hague, NL https://act4cap27.eu/agmemod-training-2025/	Event	03/2025 (Q5)
WEB-052	THÜNEN, POS	Capacity Building: CAPRI Course 2025 – Open for Registration! https://act4cap27.eu/capacity-building-capri-course-2025-open-for-registration/	Event	03/2025 (Q5)
WEB-053	UPM, POS	ACT4CAP27 Task 5.4 – Planning Training Activities for 2025 https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-task-5-4-planning-training-activities-for-2025/	News	04/2025 (Q5)
WEB-054	ECORYS, POS	WP7 Preparation meeting for online stakeholder consultation https://act4cap27.eu/wp7-preparation-meeting-for-online-stakeholder-consultation/	News	04/2025 (Q5)
WEB-055	WSER, POS	WP8 work package leaders' meeting 15 April 2025 https://act4cap27.eu/wp8-workpackage-leaders-meeting-15-april-2025/	News	04/2025 (Q5)
WEB-056	ECORYS, POS	Upcoming: ACT4CAP27 Stakeholder Consultation 6 May 2025, online https://act4cap27.eu/upcoming-act4cap27-stakeholder-consultation-6-may-2025-online/	Events	04/2025 (Q5)
WEB-057	POLISSIA, POS	Strengthening Regional Cooperation: ACT4CAP27 presented at Zhytomyr Dialogue Event 24 April 2025 https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-presented-at-zhytomyr-dialogue-event/	News	05/2025 (Q5)
WEB-058	ECORYS, POS	ACT4CAP27 Stakeholder Consultation on the Future of the CAP 6 May 2025, online https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-stakeholder-consultation-on-the-future-of-the-cap/	News	05/2025 (Q5)
WEB-059	WSER, POS	In memoriam Professor Luca Salvatici https://act4cap27.eu/in-memoriam-professor-luca-salvatici/	News	05/2025 (Q5)
WEB-060	THÜNEN, POS	WP6 meeting on fast track scenarios https://act4cap27.eu/wp6-meeting-on-fast-track-scenarios/	News	05/2025 (Q5)
WEB-061	POS, WSER	ACT4CAP27 at the EU Vision Conference on Agriculture and Food, 8 May 2025, Brussels, BE https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-at-the-eu-vision-conference-on-agriculture-and-food-8-may-2025-brussels-be/	News	05/2025 (Q5)
WEB-062	WSER, POS	WP8 work package leaders' meeting 20 May 2025, online https://act4cap27.eu/wp8-workpackage-leaders-meeting-20-may-2025-online/	News	05/2025 (Q5)
WEB-063	WSER, POS	Meet the Scientific & Policy Advisory Board of ACT4CAP27 https://act4cap27.eu/meet-the-scientific-policy-advisory-board-of-act4cap27/	News	05/2025 (Q5)
WEB-064	POS	ACT4CAP27 Mid-Year Newsletter Coming Soon – Catch Up on Our 2025 Highlights! https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-mid-year-newsletter-coming-soon-catch-up-on-our-2025-highlights/	News	05/2025 (Q5)
WEB-065	UPM, THÜNEN, POS	Upcoming GitLab Training for CAPRI – 10 June 2025, online https://act4cap27.eu/upcoming-gitlab-training-for-capri-10-june-2025-online/	News	06/2025 (Q6)
WEB-066	UPM, THÜNEN, POS	CAPRI GitLab Training – 10 June 2025 https://act4cap27.eu/capri-gitlab-training-10-june-2025/	News	06/2025 (Q6)

ID	partners involved	title and link	website section	month published (project quarter)
WEB-067	POS	IAMO Forum, 18-20 June 2025, Halle, DE https://act4cap27.eu/iamo-forum-18-20-june-2025-halle-de/	Events	06/2025 (Q6)
WEB-068	POS	ACT4CAP27 Project Flyer Now Available in All Consortium Languages https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-project-flyers-now-available-in-all-consortium-languages/	News	06/2025 (Q6)
WEB-069	POS	14th AIEAA Conference 18–20 June 2025, Pisa, IT https://act4cap27.eu/14th-aieaa-conference-18-20-june-2025-pisa-it/	Event	06/2025 (Q6)
WEB-070	POS	Summer School on Risk Analysis, Risk Management, and Resilience in Agriculture 23–27 June 2025, Wageningen, NL https://act4cap27.eu/summer-school-on-risk-analysis-risk-management-and-resilience-in-agriculture-23-27-june-2025-wageningen-nl/	Event	06/2025 (Q6)
WEB-071	POS	7th International School for Advanced Training 23 June – 4 July 2025, Online https://act4cap27.eu/7th-international-school-for-advanced-training-23-june-4-july-2025-online/	Event	06/2025 (Q6)
WEB-072	POS	Executive Course on the Vision for Agriculture and Food 25-27 June 2025, Online https://act4cap27.eu/executive-course-on-vision-for-agriculture-and-food/	Event	06/2025 (Q6)
WEB-073	POS	XV AEEA Congress 3–5 September 2025, Granada, ES https://act4cap27.eu/xv-aeea-congress-3-5-september-2025-granada-es/	Event	06/2025 (Q6)
WEB-074	POS	21st ERDN Conference 23–25 September 2025, Bucharest, RO https://act4cap27.eu/21st-erdn-conference-23-25-september-2025-bucharest-ro/	Event	06/2025 (Q6)
WEB-075	POS	OECD Green Growth & Sustainable Development Forum 2025 2–3 July 2025 Paris, FR & Online https://act4cap27.eu/oecd-green-growth-sustainable-development-forum-2025-2-3-july-2025-paris-fr-online/	Event	06/2025 (Q6)
WEB-076	POS	2nd Issue Of Newsletter Is Out https://act4cap27.eu/2nd-issue-of-newsletter-is-out/	News	06/2025 (Q6)
WEB-077	POS	Perspective Paper on the Future of Agriculture Presented at DG AGRI https://act4cap27.eu/perspective-paper-on-the-future-of-agriculture-presented-at-dg-agri/	News	06/2025 (Q6)
WEB-078	WSER, POS	Workshop Recap: AGMEMOD Model & Scenario Building 17–20 June 2025, The Hague https://act4cap27.eu/workshop-recap-agmemod-june-2025/	News	06/2025 (Q6)
WEB-079	THÜNEN, POS	Building Capacity for Evidence-Based Policy: CAPRI Training Session 2025 Recap https://act4cap27.eu/building-capacity-for-evidence-based-policy-capri-training-session-2025-recap/	News	07/2025 (Q6)
WEB-080	POS, WSER	New Joint Paper Highlights Role of Sustainable Agriculture in Securing Europe's Future https://act4cap27.eu/perspective-paper-launch/	News	07/2025 (Q6)
WEB-081	POS	ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-zenodo-community/	News	08/2025 (Q6)
WEB-082	THÜNEN, UNIROMA3, POS	ACT4CAP27 Heads to the EAAE Congress in Bonn 26–29 August 2025 https://act4cap27.eu/act4cap27-heads-to-the-eaae-congress-in-bonn-%e2%94%82-26-29-august-2025/	News	08/2025 (Q6)

APPENDIX 3 ANALYTICS OF PROJECT SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS

A3.1. Analytics of LinkedIn account

Data for 12/08/2024 - 11/08/2025

DEFINITIONS

Visitor metrics	Traffic metrics for your LinkedIn page. Shows aggregated metrics across all tabs and metrics for individual tabs.
Visitor highlights	Total number of page views and unique visitors over time. Data is measured across desktop and mobile for logged in LinkedIn members. Unique visitors are calculated daily and are not de-duplicated over multiple days
Visitor metrics	Traffic metrics for unique visitors and page views over time. Mobile metrics include LinkedIn native apps and mobile web browsers. Unique visitors are calculated daily and are not de-duplicated over multiple days.
Visitor demographics	Aggregated demographics of LinkedIn members when they visit our LI page.
Update analytics	Engagement metrics for our organic and sponsored updates over time. Shows aggregated metrics across all updates and metrics for individual updates.
Update highlights	Total number of likes, comments, and shares on your updates in the last 30 days. Data is measured across organic and sponsored updates, including Direct Sponsored Content
Update metrics	Update metrics - Aggregated engagement metrics for your organic and sponsored updates over time. Sponsored metrics include Sponsored Updates and Direct Sponsored Content. Time range filter applies to dates when your updates were viewed by LinkedIn members.
Impressions	Views when an update is at least 50% on screen for at least 300 ms, or when it is clicked, whichever comes first.
Engagement rate	Calculated as: (Clicks + Likes + Comments + Shares + Follows) / Impressions.
Update engagement	Engagement metrics for individual updates. Data is updated in real time and is limited to the last 500 updates. Data for Sponsored Updates is total of organic and sponsored engagement. Time range filter applies to the dates when your updates were created. All dates and times are in UTC.
Follower analytics	All analytics dates and times are displayed in UTC
Follower metrics	Number of new followers. Sponsored data shows followers acquired through Ads and Sponsored Content.
Follower demographics	Aggregated demographics of LinkedIn members who follow your page. % shown is calculated as: Followers with this demographic / Total followers with standardized demographics.

A3.1.1. Performance overview

Topics covered

Project meetings

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap2-sustainablefoodsystems-collaboration-activity-7300314869294129152-lx-7

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-horizoneurope-agrifoodpolicy-activity-7333109123577700352-RjF8

Project activities

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-horizoneu-europeangreendeal-activity-7250436279337635840-70sl

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_wp6-workshop-on-modelling-the-future-of-eu-ukraine-activity-7242797300970868736-tQF4

Emerging project results

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_openaccess-activity-7361115161404825600-gLA9

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_policy-machinelearning-sustainability-activity-7296944110790205440-tVv0

Promoting capacity building

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_recap-agmemod-model-scenario-building-activity-7348287191955005441-7XPC

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_capri-capacitybuilding-agrifoodmodelling-activity-7311347690263502848-Fqiw

Stakeholder & Policy Advisory Board interactions

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-horizoneurope-sustainableagriculture-activity-7333116566722494465-y4ks

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_many-thanks-to-all-participants-of-the-activity-7254857886504247297-IGC3

Participation at EC and international events

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-activity-7254583594025689089-SMwg

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_possessio-was-representing-the-act4cap27-activity-7258782742874574850-UWen

Participation at events

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-horizoneurope-digitaleurope-activity-7330254406849859584-kTQj

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_machinelearning-eufunding-policyinnovation-activity-7293926745685024770-c2V8

Collaborations with other projects

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_competitiveness-sustainability-activity-7288298967308636161-Gwpe

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_euagrisjos-brightspaceeuresults-brightspaceeu-activity-7259509875062296577-JbQZ

Project newsletters

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-horizoneurope-agrifoodpolicy-activity-7339235376592486402-t5o-

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/act4cap27-eu-project_act4cap27-euagrifood-sustainability-activity-7267120944207339520-Tuc9

A3.1.2. CONTENT

Impressions

Impressions refers to the total number of views when the content is at least 50% on screen for at least 300ms, or the total number of times the content is clicked on, whichever comes first.

Engagement rate

Engagement rate is calculated as: (Clicks + Reactions + Comments + Shares + Follows) / Impressions.

A3.1.3. VISITORS

Visitor highlights

Analytics are based on the total number of Page Views, unique visitors over time, and unique custom button clicks over time. Unique visitors are calculated daily and are not de-duplicated over multiple days. Data is measured across desktop and mobile for logged in LinkedIn members.

Visitor metrics

Traffic metrics for unique visitors and page views over time. Unique visitors are calculated daily and are not de-duplicated over multiple days. Mobile metrics include LinkedIn native apps and mobile web browsers.

Unique visitors

Page views

Visitor demographics

Aggregated demographics of LinkedIn members when they visit the ACT4CAP27 page.

Visitor demographics by industry

Visitor demographics by location

A3.1.4. FOLLOWERS

Follower metrics

Line graph of new followers in the past 365 days. This does not include followers who are other Pages.

Follower metrics ?

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	— Sponsored	0
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	- - - Organic	166

Follower demographics

Follower demographics by industry

Followers by location

A3.1.4. VALUE OF LINKEDIN AS A COMMUNICATION CHANNEL

Impact Nr	Indicator	Means of monitoring and evaluating	Targets for the project lifetime	Actual value for the reporting period
KPI_04	N° of users following social media channels	Number of followers on LinkedIn + Bluesky + X	target 800	264 + 141 + 51= 456

Table A3.1 Database of ACT4CAP27 original posts on LinkedIn (as of 16/08/2025)

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p>Did you know that as part of our dedication to #OpenAccess, we have a specific community page for ACT4CAP27 at Zenodo?</p> <p>Why is this important? Disseminating our research through open access ensures that valuable insights and advancements are freely accessible to the global community. By regularly updating and making our emerging project outputs available on the ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project Zenodo Community page – that is also part of the EU Open Research Repository – we aim to foster collaboration, encourage dialogue among stakeholders, and contribute to the collective progress of policy research and development.</p> <p>How can you stay updated? We invite you to follow and regularly check the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo community page for the latest updates, publications, and findings from our project.</p> <p>Visit the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo community page: https://lnkd.in/gHxQfv5Z</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7361115161404825600	08/12/2025	All followers	54		0	0	0	0	0	
<p> New Joint Perspective Paper: Why Sustainable Agriculture Matters for Europe's Future 🌱</p> <p>The Horizon Europe projects ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project, BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project, and LAMASUS have released a joint perspective paper highlighting how a sustainable agricultural sector is essential to the EU's economic prosperity, food security, and environmental sustainability.</p> <p>With agriculture underpinning a €1 trillion agrifood supply chain and playing a key role in climate and trade policy, the paper identifies five Priority Action Areas (PAAs) to strengthen Europe's future:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✅ PAA1. Fostering income and resilience through result-based policies that integrate economic and environmental performance. ✅ PAA2. Integrated nutrient management to enhance strategic autonomy. ✅ PAA3. Enhancing the agrifood sector competitiveness and food security through level-playing field trade agreements. ✅ PAA4. Strengthening innovation leadership in the new bioeconomy ✅ PAA5. Democratizing digitalization to ensure agricultural sector attractiveness and technological innovation. <p>Backed by decades of modelling expertise, the authors call for updated tools to better connect economics, environment, and innovation — laying the groundwork for smarter, more impactful policies beyond 2027.</p> <p>👉 Read how economic modelling is shaping the next generation of EU agri-food policy:</p> <p>📄 Executive summary (pdf on Zenodo): https://lnkd.in/d4k4tPR8</p> <p>📄 Full perspective paper (pdf on Zenodo): https://lnkd.in/df_TkN8N</p> <p>📄 Press release (pdf / text-only version on Zenodo): https://lnkd.in/d48tNhMp</p> <p>Authors: Petr Havlik, Hans Van Meijl, Tamás Krisztin, Marc Müller, Siemen Van Berkum, Thomas Fellmann, Alexander Gocht, Hervé Guyomard, Tassos Haniotis, Alan Matthews, Paolo Scokoi, Davit Stepanyan, Dr. , Peter Witzke, Katalin Balázs, Dylan Bos</p> <p>International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen Social & Economic Research, Joint Research Centre – European Commission, Seville , Thünen Institute, Trinity College Dublin, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Planslab Kft., POSSESSIO Ltd.</p> <p>#HorizonEurope #CAP #VisionForAgriculture, #EUagriculture, #FutureOfFood, and #SustainableFoodSystem #SustainableAgriculture #Bioeconomy #DigitalFarming #FoodSecurity #EUGreenDeal #ACT4CAP27 #BrightSpace #LAMASUS #WeCooperate</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7354216483343761408	07/24/2025	All followers	721		33	0.045769766	20	3	0.077669904	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p> https://agmemod.eu/</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7348287191955005441</p>	07/08/2025	All followers	382		35	0.091623038	12	0	0.123036653	
<p> Learn more about the project: https://act4cap27.eu/</p> <p>#ACT4CAP27 #HorizonEurope #AgriFoodPolicy #SustainableAgriculture #PolicyModelling #ScienceToPolicy #AMYRN #EURResearch #NewsletterUpdate</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7339235376592486402</p>	06/13/2025	All followers	295		15	0.050847456	7	3	0.091525421	
<p> Check out the flyers on Zenodo:</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7339229625102884865</p>	06/13/2025	All followers	178		2	0.011235955	4	1	0.039325844	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p>https://lnkd.in/dEfdZnKu Let's build a sustainable and inclusive future for European agriculture, together. #ACT4CAP27 #HorizonEurope #AgrifoodPolicy #EUProjects #StakeholderEngagement #ProjectCommunication #SustainableAgriculture #ScienceToPolicy</p>											
<p> Don't miss out — subscribe now to receive our 6-monthly newsletters and stay updated on research, events, and project insights! https://lnkd.in/d7n2wyBK</p> <p>#ACT4CAP27 #HorizonEurope #AgrifoodPolicy #SustainableAgriculture #PolicyModelling #StakeholderEngagement #EUResearch #Newsletter #CAP27</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7333121924371316737	05/27/2025	All followers	156		4	0.025641026	2	1	0.044871796	
<p> Get to know the SPAB members: https://lnkd.in/dbivyeEq</p> <p>#ACT4CAP27 #HorizonEurope #SustainableAgriculture #FoodSystems #AgriFoodPolicy #ScienceToPolicy #StakeholderEngagement #ResearchImpact</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7333116566722494465	05/27/2025	All followers	952		57	0.05987395	27	1	0.089285716	
<p>ACT4CAP27 WP Leaders' Meeting: Progress, Planning & Policy Insights</p> <p>On 20 May, the ACT4CAP27 WP leads met to reflect on recent milestones —including an online stakeholder meeting with 60+ participants — and to coordinate the next steps across all work streams. From finalizing the Fast Track Scenarios to expanding modelling collaborations and launching the AMYRN Young Researcher Network, the project continues to advance its mission of delivering cutting-edge tools for EU agri-food policy modelling beyond 2027.</p> <p> Read the full news post for more insights: https://lnkd.in/dJjMqUcp</p> <p>#ACT4CAP27 #HorizonEurope #AgrifoodPolicy #SustainableAgriculture #ResearchImpact #AMYRN #ModelingEUFoodSystems #StakeholderEngagement #CAP27</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7333109123577700352	05/27/2025	All followers	293		37	0.126279861	6	0	0.146757677	
<p>On 24 April, the ACT4CAP27 project was presented at a dialogue event hosted by Polissia National University and organised by ULEAD with Europe. Local leaders, researchers, and innovators came together to explore how Horizon Europe and Digital Europe programmes can support communities in the Zhytomyr region.</p> <p> Read the full story: https://lnkd.in/dBg9aVTN</p> <p>#ACT4CAP27 #HorizonEurope #DigitalEurope #EUFunded #RegionalDevelopment #Ukraine #CAPreform #Innovation #PolissiaUniversity #EUResearch</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7330254406849859584	05/19/2025	All followers	86		0	0	5	0	0.058139537	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p>🗣️ On 6 May, ACT4CAP27 hosted its second stakeholder consultation, bringing together researchers, policymakers, and agri-food sector voices from across Europe to explore priorities for the Common Agricultural Policy post-2027. From result-based income support to private financing options and eligibility conditions — the discussions were rich, diverse, and future-focused.</p> <p>👏 We would like to thank also here to all stakeholders for their contributions!</p> <p>🔍 Curious about the key insights and what comes next?</p> <p>👉 Read the full recap on our website: https://lnkd.in/dVXHwdSN</p> <p>#CAP #EUAgriPolicy #EUAgriVision #ACT4CAP27 #SustainableFarming #StakeholderEngagement #HorizonEurope</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7328733409323671553	05/15/2025	All followers	238		15	0.063025214	4	1	0.084033616	
<p>ACT4CAP27 Training Activities for 2025 – Planning & Collaboration</p> <p>On 4 April 2025, an online meeting was held to discuss Task 5.4 – Planning Training Activities for 2025 as part of ACT4CAP27's ongoing capacity-building efforts. Convened by WP5 leader Universidad Politécnica de Madrid and moderated by Maria Blanco, the session outlined upcoming training initiatives, collaboration opportunities, and budget considerations.</p> <p>🔑 Key Discussion Points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✅ Training Plans for 2025 – Overview of past and upcoming training events: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ #CAPRI Developer Seminar (11-12 March 2025, Berlin) ◆ CAPRI Course 2025 – Now open for registration! ◆ #AGMEMOD Training Course (17-20 June 2025, The Hague) ✅ Collaboration with Fellow Projects – Strengthening synergies with BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project and Tools4CAP to enhance knowledge exchange and capacity-building efforts. ✅ Training Budget & Technicalities – Reviewing procedures to ensure efficient use of the ACT4CAP27 training budget. <p>📌 Stay updated on ACT4CAP27's capacity-building activities here: https://lnkd.in/dhu6z5N2</p> <p>🔗 Read more about the meeting: https://lnkd.in/dXbtdZja</p> <p>#ACT4CAP27 #CapacityBuilding #AgriFoodModelling #Training #Collaboration</p> <p>Thünen Institute, Wageningen Social & Economic Research, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Università degli studi Roma TRE</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7313880598715031553	04/04/2025	All followers	245		27	0.110204078	8	1	0.146938771	
<p>Capacity Building: CAPRI Course 2025: Applied Data Analysis – Now Open for Registration! https://lnkd.in/dDP4DmYC</p> <p>🏠 Organized by the Thünen Institute with support from the CAPRI consortium, this course provides hands-on training in the CAPRI partial equilibrium model, widely used for market and policy analysis.</p> <p>📅 April 17 – July 17, 2025 🕒 Every Thursday 12:00 – 16:00 CET 📍 Hybrid format Humboldt University of Berlin</p> <p>As part of ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project and BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project, the course is open to external participants and Master's students in Agricultural Economics at Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin.</p> <p>💡 Led by Alexander Gocht (Thünen) with support of Davit Stepanyan, Dr., Davide Pignotti, Ferike Thom, Dr. Jörg Rieger, and with contributions of core developers of the CAPRI network such as Maria Blanco, Torbjörn Jansson, Caetano Luiz Beber, the course covers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔑 Introduction to the GAMS modelling language 🔑 Overview of the CAPRI modelling system 🔑 Hands-on exercises & deep dives into model components 	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7311347690263502848	03/28/2025	All followers	366		45	0.122950822	10	3	0.158469945	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p>This is a unique opportunity to develop practical skills in agri-food policy modelling.</p> <p>📌 Register now: Moodle Registration https://lnkd.in/eUgBkm</p> <p>📄 Course details: CAPRI Course Webpage https://lnkd.in/eWuzYb88</p> <p>#CAPRI #CapacityBuilding #AgriFoodModelling #EconomicModelling #PolicyAnalysis #ACT4CAP27 #BrightSpaceEU</p>											
<p>📌 Capacity Building: AGMEMOD Training Course, 17-20 June 2025, The Hague, NL https://lnkd.in/dyqdHkW5</p> <p>Wageningen University & Research (WUR) and the Thünen Institute (THÜNEN) invite researchers, policymakers, and professionals to the upcoming AGMEMOD Training Course, taking place June 17-20, 2025, in The Hague.</p> <p>🔍 About AGMEMOD AGMEMOD is a key partial equilibrium model used for agricultural economic analysis across the EU. This training will equip new modellers with essential skills and foster collaboration within the AGMEMOD consortium and beyond.</p> <p>🎯 Course Highlights:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 Applications of AGMEMOD – Research & policy relevance 🔴 Data requirements & processing 🔴 Model structure & equations 🔴 Scenario modelling & analysis <p>💡 Who should attend?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✅ Researchers & analysts in agricultural policy modelling ✅ Early-career professionals in economic modelling ✅ AGMEMOD consortium members & partners <p>📄 Participation & Registration The course is free, supported by Horizon Europe projects Tools4CAP, BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project, and ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project, but participants must cover their own travel, accommodation, and meals.</p> <p>📧 For inquiries, contact Ana Gonzalez Martinez at ana.gonzalezmartinez (at) wur.nl.</p> <p>We look forward to welcoming you to The Hague for this exciting training opportunity!</p> <p>#AGMEMOD #CapacityBuilding #EconomicModelling #AgriculturalPolicy #BrightSpaceEU #Tools4CAP #ACT4CAP27</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7310590095298904064	03/25/2025	All followers	241		9	0.0373444	6	2	0.070539422	
<p>ACT4CAP27 WP8 Work Package Leaders' Meeting – 18 March 2025 https://lnkd.in/d6eA3h2b</p> <p>On 18 March 2025, the ACT4CAP27 WP8 leads met online to align priorities and drive forward key project activities. Key updates from the meeting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 DG AGRI Vision Conference (8 May, Brussels & online) <p>Work is underway to finalize the Vision100 paper in collaboration with the BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project and LAMASUS projects, ahead of the conference.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 Fast-Track Scenarios A consolidated report is nearing completion and will soon be shared internally for review and discussion. 🔴 WP2 Follow-Up Rome meeting documentation is being finalized to ensure action points are effectively tracked. 🔴 Stakeholder Engagement The 2nd stakeholder meeting is planned for early May 2025, focusing on Vision100 and post-CAP27 themes. 🔴 Agri-Food Modelling Young Researcher Network (#AMYRN) Funding opportunities for early - career researchers to collaborate across ACT4CAP27 partners - first expressions of interest have already been received! 	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7310219592293875712	03/25/2025	All followers	85		1	0.011764706	3	0	0.047058824	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p>📌 First Reporting Period The timeline for the first reporting period (March 2024 – August 2025) was presented, ensuring smooth documentation and reporting processes.</p> <p>📅 Next WP8 meeting: 15 April 2025</p> <p>Looking forward to continued progress in the coming months! #ACT4CAP27 #AgriFoodPolicy #ResearchCollaboration #ClimateResilience</p>											
<p>🌱 Supporting the Next Generation of Agri-Food Modellers 🌱</p> <p>As part of ACT4CAP27, the Agri-Food Model Young Researcher Network (AMYRN) is fostering a new wave of expertise in simulation modelling for agri-food policy within the ACT4CAP27 partner organisations.</p> <p>Economic models like AGMEMOD, CAPRI, GLOBIOM, and MAGNET play a crucial role in assessing land use, biodiversity, climate change, and food security. Mastering these models requires specialized knowledge, from using software like GAMS and GEMPACK to handling large geospatial datasets.</p> <p>🎓 AMYRN is open to PhDs and early-career postdocs already engaged in ACT4CAP27 research, helping them gain practical experience and build future modelling capacity.</p> <p>👉 Are you a young ACT4CAP27 researcher interested in joining? The AMYRN call will soon be published!</p> <p>Keep being informed and learn more here: https://lnkd.in/dRb6VjBN</p> <p>#ACT4CAP27 #AgriFoodModelling #YoungResearchers #CapacityBuilding</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7310216644499283968	03/25/2025	All followers	582		39	0.067010306	22	5	0.113402061	
<p>🎉 ACT4CAP2 Annual Meeting – Day 1 in Rome!</p> <p>A day full of insightful discussions, innovative ideas, and great collaboration! 🌱💡 Here's a visual summary capturing the highlights of our first day. 📸</p> <p>For more details, check out the full summary here: https://lnkd.in/dg-b7nMC</p> <p>Looking forward to another productive day tomorrow!</p> <p>#ACT4CAP2 #SustainableFoodSystems #Collaboration #Innovation #EUAgri</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7300314869294129152	02/26/2025	All followers	334	320	41	0.122754492	12	5	0.173652694	Video
<p>🌱🌱 Shaping the Future of EU Agri-Food Policy 🌱🌱</p> <p>We're excited to kick off the ACT4CAP27 Annual Consortium Meeting 2025 at the Università degli studi Roma TRE! This gathering brings together our project partners to review progress and map out the next steps in supporting EU agri-food policies beyond 2027.</p> <p>Our focus?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✅ Strengthening analytical tools ✅ Refining research methodologies ✅ Enhancing collaboration to address future challenges <p>With the evolving European Green Deal and CAP post-2027, we're working to improve policy impact assessments and develop better modelling frameworks to support evidence-based decision-making.</p> <p>📰 Read our press release https://lnkd.in/dUKqE94e</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7300090663004479488	02/25/2025	All followers	238		10	0.042016808	8	3	0.088235296	
<p>📰 New Open Access Article: Optimizing Policy Funding Allocation with Machine Learning</p> <p>We're proud to share that Cristina Vaquero Piñeiro from the ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project contributed to the new open-access article, "Predicting Policy Funding Allocation with Machine Learning", published in Socio-Economic Planning Sciences. This work, partly funded by ACT4CAP27, explores how machine learning can improve the efficiency of agricultural policy funding, ensuring resources are allocated where they will have the most impact.</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7296944110790205440	02/16/2025	All followers	625		26	0.0416	16	1	0.068800002	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p>Key takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accurate Predictions: Machine learning models forecast policy funding allocation with greater precision. Data-Driven Decisions: Using insights from large datasets, policymakers can optimize their funding strategies. Supporting Sustainability: This research helps align funding with sustainable agricultural goals. <p>Read the full article here: https://lnkd.in/duF2BvVs</p> <p>#Policy #MachineLearning #Sustainability #Agriculture #ACT4CAP27 #DataScience</p>											
<p>Summer School 2025: Applications Open until February 28, 2025! Land Management for Sustainability June 2-6, 2025 Laxenburg, Austria</p> <p>The LAMASUS / BrightSpace Summer School 2025 is now accepting applications! This unique one-week program offers an immersive deep dive into advanced land-use and policy modelling, equipping participants with cutting-edge tools to assess the impacts of European agricultural policies.</p> <p>Why Join?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learn from leading researchers at IIASA, BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project, and LAMASUS Gain hands-on experience with econometric, biophysical, and integrated modelling Explore policy pathways, land-use dynamics, and sustainability challenges Engage in interactive workshops and real-world applications of policy analysis <p>Who Should Apply? This summer school is ideal for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> PhD students & early-career researchers Policy analysts supporting ministries & EU institutions Experts working in land-use, climate, and sustainability sectors <p>Trainers The course will be taught by experienced International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA) scientists working in the LAMASUS project and BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project: Tamás Krisztin, Petr Havlik, Tassos Haniotis, Linda See, Michael Wögerer, Juraj Balkovic, Richard Cornford, Felicity Addo</p> <p>Application Deadline: February 28, 2025</p> <p>Don't miss this opportunity to enhance your expertise in sustainable land management and policy evaluation!</p> <p>Apply Now & Learn More: https://lnkd.in/d6cg-Nqe</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7296911549208657920	02/16/2025	All followers	192		5	0.026041666	2	0	0.036458332	
<p>ACT4CAP27 is now also on Bluesky!</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stay updated on the latest in agricultural sustainability, policy insights, and policy modelling research — now on Bluesky! Follow us for project updates, events, and key discussions shaping the future of European food systems. Join the conversation & follow us today! <p>https://lnkd.in/d5NtuGee</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7296910972877729793	02/16/2025	All followers	122		7	0.057377048	5	0	0.098360658	
<p>WP8 Leaders Prepare for the ACT4CAP27 Annual Consortium Meeting</p> <p>On 11 February 2025, the WP8 work package leaders met online to refine the agenda for the Annual Consortium Meeting, taking place on 25-26 February in Rome, Italy. This key event will set the course for the next phase of the ACT4CAP27 project, ensuring that research and policy discussions remain aligned with the evolving landscape of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) post-2027.</p> <p>The Rome meeting will focus on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revisiting project objectives and expectations 	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7296909972674633728	02/16/2025	All followers	238		28	0.117647059	4	1	0.138655469	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✔ Refining strategies for WP2 & WP3, including database expansion & model improvements ✔ Strengthening collaboration and setting clear timelines for deliverables ✔ Addressing research gaps & enhancing analytical tools for sustainable food systems <p>With WP leaders and task coordinators taking the lead, the discussions will drive progress on health, environmental, and socio-economic assessments as well as food system innovations. This meeting is a crucial step in ensuring the project's impact on shaping future agricultural policies in the EU.</p> <p>📅 Looking forward to insightful discussions in Rome! #ACT4CAP27 #Agriculture #Sustainability #EUPolicy #Research #Collaboration</p>											
<p>🌐 CAPRI Developer Seminar 2025 – Advancing Agricultural Economic Modelling</p> <p>We are excited to announce the CAPRI Developer Seminar 2025:</p> <p>📅 Date: 11-12 March 2025 📍 Place: Berlin, Germany Host: Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, International Agricultural Trade and Development (IATD) Thünen Institute of Farm Economics (Thünen)</p> <p>This event will bring together researchers, software developers, and agricultural economists to explore the latest advancements in the Common Agricultural Policy Regionalised Impact (CAPRI) Modelling System, a key tool for economic analysis in agriculture.</p> <p>Key topics include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✔ Latest policy simulations, data updates, and methodological advancements ✔ Insights from BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project & ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project, enhancing CAPRI's ability to assess sustainability, climate impacts, and policy interventions ✔ Opportunities for collaboration and knowledge exchange among CAPRI developers, policymakers, and researchers <p>The seminar is open to students and PhD candidates interested in agricultural economic modeling, providing them with a unique opportunity to engage with experts in the field.</p> <p>📅 Mark your calendar! 📄 View the agenda here: https://lnkd.in/d8c7YrHK Maximum number of participants: 30</p> <p>🔗 Learn more about CAPRI: https://lnkd.in/dQfnSwFd</p> <p>#CAPRI #AgriculturalEconomics #PolicyModelling #Sustainability #CapacityBuilding</p> <p>EuroCare Bonn, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, European Commission Joint Research Centre JRC Seville and Ispra, EAER - Swiss Federal Office for Agriculture</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7293991926054240257	02/08/2025	All followers	622		24	0.038585208	19	1	0.070739552	
<p>🔗 Predicting EU Funding Success with Machine Learning 🧠</p> <p>At the XXIII SIEPI Annual Workshop (University of Bologna, Jan 30-31, 2025), Cristina Vaquero Piñeiro from the UNIROMA3 team of the ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project presented their research on leveraging Machine Learning (ML) to predict EU funding success.</p> <p>🔍 Why does this matter? EU funding plays a crucial role in economic development, particularly in rural and environmental policies under the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD). Understanding what factors influence funding allocation before decisions are made can help policymakers optimize resource distribution and guide applicants toward success.</p> <p>📌 The Research Approach:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✔ Firm-level data from the Italian Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) ✔ 8 different ML algorithms tested - Random Forest delivered the best predictions 	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7293926745685024770	02/08/2025	All followers	309		26	0.084142394	6	0	0.103559874	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p>✅ Key factors influencing funding success:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Location (firms in mountain areas more likely to receive funds) Economic diversification (smaller, diversified farms had better chances) Sustainability & Certification (organic certification boosted funding prospects) Generational shift (younger entrepreneurs had higher success rates) <p>🔑 Key Takeaways for Policy & Practice:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better targeting of funds—policymakers can anticipate who is most likely to win funding and identify potential gaps. Smarter investment decisions—farmers & businesses can align strategies with key funding success factors. Boosting sustainability efforts—incentivizing environmentally friendly practices through better-designed policies. <p>🔗 Access the presentation at the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community page https://lnkd.in/dq4hTs33</p> <p>Source: University of Roma Tre</p> <p>#MachineLearning #EUfunding #PolicyInnovation #Agriculture #RuralDevelopment #Sustainability #ACT4CAP27 #SIEPI</p>											
<p>🌱 GREEN & DIGITAL POLISSIA: AGRICULTURE 🌱</p> <p>The second key event of the year took place at POLIDIH, the European Digital Innovation Hub at Polissya National University. Opened by Rector of Polissya National University, Oleh Skydan, the forum gathered farmers, entrepreneurs, and stakeholders from the Zhytomyr and Rivne regions, offering a platform to explore digital opportunities and sustainable agribusiness solutions.</p> <p>The ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project was presented by Olga Nikolyuk, Head of the Educational and Research Center for Digital Technologies and Natural Resources Systems Modelling at Polissya National University. Olga showcased how ACT4CAP27 aims to strengthen data-driven approaches and analytical tools that will support the evolution of the EU's Common Agricultural Policy beyond 2027. 🙌 https://lnkd.in/dDcM8PJw</p> <p>The forum also featured insights on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital solutions for sustainable agriculture GIS services for farmers Drone applications in modern farming AGROSUS_HE agroecological strategies for sustainable weed management <p>#ACT4CAP27 #SustainableAgriculture #DigitalInnovation #PolissyaUniversity #AgriTech #CommonAgriculturalPolicy</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7292265621969371136	02/03/2025	All followers	240		23	0.095833331	7	0	0.125	
<p>Driving EU Agricultural Policy Forward 🌱 EU: ACT4CAP27, BrightSpace, and Lamasus Collaborate 🤝</p> <p>Following an online kick-off discussion in December 2024 🗣️, colleagues from the ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project, BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project, and LAMASUS project convened in Laxenburg, Austria 🇦🇹 on 22-23 January 2025, for an in-person working retreat. The goal was to reinforce joint efforts to align EU agricultural #competitiveness with #sustainability goals 🌱🌿 through innovative policy modeling 📊📈.</p> <p>Alan Matthews and Tassos Haniotis, as key members of the Project Advisory Group, offered invaluable guidance and inputs to shape the discussion and outcomes. 🙌</p> <p>Aligning Goals for Impact 🎯</p> <p>During the retreat, we worked toward developing a joint paper 📄, synthesizing insights from the three projects to provide actionable recommendations for EU agricultural policy 🌱.</p> <p>The meeting focused on identifying and reaching consensus on the 🗣️ messages for the paper, ensuring coherence across the participating projects. The team finalized the outline and timeline 🕒, assigning responsibilities for drafting various sections. Additionally, the scenario frameworks proposed by ACT4CAP27, BrightSpace, and Lamasus were reviewed and aligned to maximize complementarity and synergies 🤝, enhancing the collective impact of the projects.</p> <p>Collaboration as a Catalyst for Change 🤝</p> <p>This retreat underscores the importance of partnership 🤝 in tackling the complex challenges of EU agriculture 🌱. By pooling expertise 🧠.</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7288298967308636161	01/23/2025	All followers	407	165	40	0.098280095	8	1	0.12039312	Video

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<p>and integrating diverse perspectives 🧑‍🌾, the participating projects aim to deliver a comprehensive framework that balances agricultural competitiveness with sustainable practices 🌱.</p> <p>🙏 We are especially grateful to our colleagues at IIASA 🧑‍🌾 for their role in initiating, organizing, and fostering the positive and productive atmosphere of this retreat.</p> <p>The outcomes of this retreat will culminate in a joint paper 📄, presenting strategic recommendations and actionable insights to guide EU agricultural policy forward.</p> <p>🔔 Stay tuned for updates as this important work progresses!</p>											
<p>Wageningen Social & Economic Research, Thünen Institute, INRAE, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Planlab Kft., POSSESSIO Ltd. ACT4CAP27 Prepares for its 1st Annual Consortium Meeting in Rome</p> <p>As ACT4CAP27 approaches its first anniversary, preparations are underway for the Annual Consortium Meeting, which will be held in Rome on 24–25 February 2025, hosted by our UniRoma3 partner. To ensure the meeting's success, work package (WP) leaders gathered online on 14 January to discuss the draft agenda and logistics.</p> <p>What's on the Agenda? The Annual Consortium Meeting will focus on key objectives to guide the project into its second year:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Revisiting Objectives: Reflect on ACT4CAP27's goals and reconfirm its relevance in the current research and political landscape. ◆ Strategic Planning: Identify priority topics for Year Two, aligned with the project's work plan. ◆ Deliverable Roadmap: Establish a clear understanding of deliverables up to the 1st interim report in August 2025 and beyond. ◆ Defining Strategies: Develop actionable strategies at both the project and WP levels. <p>Areas of Focus Special attention will be given to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔆 Developing the conceptual framework for the project. 🔆 Advancing the database and model portal for accessibility and usability. 🔆 Strengthening the modular modelling toolbox for robust analytical capabilities. 🔆 Supporting capacity building for young researchers and partners from non-participating organizations. 🔆 Enhancing the stakeholder process and dissemination to maximize project impact. <p>The online WP leaders' meeting helped align priorities and ensure all preparations are on track for Rome. We look forward to the insights and strategies that will emerge from the consortium meeting as ACT4CAP27 continues to drive collaboration in addressing challenges in modelling EU agri-food policies.</p> <p>Stay tuned for updates on the outcomes from Rome!</p> <p>#ACT4CAP27 #HorizonEurope</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7285007269518336000	01/14/2025	All followers	235		18	0.076595746	4	0	0.093617022	
<p>Are you interested in how value-added tax reforms can support global health, environmental, and economic policy targets?</p> <p>Read this fresh #OpenAccess article from #ACT4CAP27's fellow project: BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project!</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7284637276184203265	01/13/2025	All followers	110		8	0.07272727	1	0	0.081818178	
<p>. ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project addresses the need for improved data & modelling tools highlighted at #EUAgriFoodDays by advancing key analytical frameworks (CAPRI, GLOBIOM, MAGNET, AGMEMOD) to support post-2027 agri-food policies.</p> <p>Many thanks to Sophie Helaine & Balázs Bence TÓTH for their continued support to our project!</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7272651418056998915	12/11/2024	All followers	209		23	0.110047847	11	1	0.167464122	

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<p>! Talk with us at the EU #AGRIFOODDAYS 2024 for the #PolicyModelling #HorizonEurope #WeCooperate projects' stand:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project #EUagriSIOS LAMASUS #LandUse ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project #FoodSystem @mind step project #FarmDecisions <p>Many thanks to our Sci.Officer EUAgri Fanny Le Gloux!</p> <p>ACT4CAP27 partners: Wageningen Economic Research, Ecorys, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Thünen Institute, Polissia National University Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, UCL, EuroCare, UniRoma3, SLU, Joint Research Centre of the European Commission, Wageningen University & Research, POSSESSIO Ltd.</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7272281334738280448	12/10/2024	All followers	168		9	0.053571429	9	2	0.119047619	
<p>We are very pleased to inform you that we have just released the 1st issue of the ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project Newsletter.</p> <p>Access and browse it here: https://lnkd.in/dMN_VY3q</p> <p>What ACT4CAP27 is all about?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ACT4CAP27 is an EC funded 5-year Horizon Europe research and innovation action aiming to enhance analytical capabilities, tools, and collaborative technical infrastructure within the policy modelling community, to provide support for evidence-based EU agri-food policies post-2027. <p>From this issue of our newsletter, you can get to know:</p> <p>Which organisations are in the project team?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The consortium of ACT4CAP27 consists of 13 partners from 10 countries in Europe (AT, BE, DE, IT, HU, NL, ES, SE, UA, UK), and the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission. <p>How is the project structured?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The ACT4CAP27 project is managed through 8 work packages (WP), each of which is responsible for various parts of the five-year project. <p>What are the latest developments in our project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Read the letter from our Coordinator, Siemen van Berkum looking back at the first 10 months of project implementation. From kick-off to various activities: learn more about how our partners work to keep focus on project implementation, including our 1st Stakeholder Meeting held in-presence in October. Get to know our latest ACT4CAP27 highlights from Ukraine. Read our 1st policy brief. <p>Where and how are we networking and cooperate with other Horizon Europe Projects?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Read more how we cooperate with our fellow project BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project. Read further highlights from our fellow projects, including results from Tools4CAP. <p>What are the upcoming international events where you can meet us?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> There are several events on our list, e.g. ACT4CAP27 will be represented at the Agricultural Outlook Conference in Brussels organized in the framework of the EU #AGRIFOODDAYS between 10-12 December 2024. 	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7272260040240091139	12/10/2024	All followers	316		17	0.053797469	6	1	0.075949363	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p>We hope you will enjoy delving into the latest info about our project.</p> <p>Continue reading the PDF version here: https://lnkd.in/dMN_VY3q</p> <p>Thank you for being an integral part of the ACT4CAP27 community.</p> <p>Wishing you a peaceful festive season and all the best for the new year ahead.</p> <p>Best regards, The ACT4CAP27 project team</p>											
<p></p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7267120944207339520	11/26/2024	All followers	121		3	0.024793388	6	1	0.082644626	
<p>ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project will also be featured today at the Annual Meeting of our fellow project: BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project in Seville. Read the press release of the meeting here:</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7259509875062296577	11/05/2024	All followers	73		2	0.02739726	0	0	0.02739726	
<p>Possessio was representing the ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project at the Conference on Sustainable Agricultural Productivity to Address Food Systems Challenges: Measurement, Data, Drivers and Policies organised on 28 October 2024 in Paris by the OECD Trade and Agriculture Directorate, in collaboration with the European Commission's @Directorate-General on Agriculture and Rural Development and the United States Department of Agriculture.</p> <p>The conference brought together policy makers and researchers to discuss the concept and measurement of sustainable agricultural productivity. It aimed to bridge the gap between academic and policy communities and translate and orient research efforts to pragmatic and policy relevant ways to measure agricultural performance for achieving sustainable productivity growth to address food systems challenges. The exchange among experts and policy makers focussed on the current and evolving state of sustainable agricultural productivity performance and the state of the art on measurement and data, as well as on the main challenges to reconcile productivity and sustainability, focusing particularly on the environmental aspects of sustainability.</p> <p>ACT4CAP27 project communications task leader, Katalin Balázs, invited participant to the event, emphasized how ACT4CAP's interdisciplinary analytical framework can grasp all dimensions of sustainable agricultural productivity, and will provide robust, data-driven insights to aid policymakers in crafting well-informed, effective agri-food policies for the post-2027 landscape in the EU. The creation of sustainable food systems is crucial for the long-term resilience and prosperity of the EU agricultural sector. https://lnkd.in/dSEqmFNc</p> <p>We would like to also thank here the organisers for the invitation and for this great opportunity to expose our project to a wide array of policy makers and professionals working in this area across the world.</p> <p>The full recording of the conference is available at the event's page: https://lnkd.in/eaYaCNiv</p> <p>https://lnkd.in/dUEqK77H</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7258782742874574850	11/03/2024	All followers	268		14	0.052238807	7	0	0.078358211	
<p>Join us on-site or on-line oe.cd/SPGconf for the OECD Trade and Agriculture Conference on #sustainable #agricultural #productivity on 28 October!</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:725627	10/27/2024	All followers	62		2	0.032258064	0	0	0.032258064	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
	2090226442240										
The #ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project also works for - Enhancing #analyticaltools enabling coherent and reliable #policyevaluations for supporting Evidence-Based Policymaking Post-2027 by providing robust, data-driven insights to aid policymakers in crafting well-informed, effective agri-food policies for the post-2027 landscape, - Interdisciplinary Analytical Framework: to quantify economic, social, environmental, and climate #sustainability impacts of EU #agri-food policies, addressing all components of the European #GreenDeal, ensuring comprehensive policy #impact #assessments.	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7256259300468150272	10/27/2024	All followers	100		3	0.029999999	2	0	0.050000001	
👏 Many thanks to all participants of the 1st Stakeholder Meeting of ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project for their valuable contributions! Read more: https://lnkd.in/dxss8a88 Wageningen Economic Research, Ecorys, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Thünen Institute, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, UCL	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7254857886504247297	10/23/2024	All followers	288	239	23	0.079861112	13	2	0.131944448	Video
📄 #ACT4CAP27 was introduced to EC officers & representatives of fellow projects today at the European Research Executive Agency (REA) Horizon EU projects Cluster meeting in Brussels https://lnkd.in/dAnymAF BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project, LAMASUS, ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project, AgEnRes, STEP UP, MATS H2020, Trade4SD - EU Horizon 2020, BATModel, Tools4CAP	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7254583594025689089	10/22/2024	All followers	497	274	27	0.054325957	16	8	0.102615692	Video
📅 The meeting agenda is out! Register for the ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project 1st Stakeholder Meeting: 📅 Wed, 23 October 2024, 09:00 to 13:00 📍 Thon Hotel EU, Wetstraat / Rue de la Loi 75, Brussels 1040, Belgium Join the ACT4CAP27 Stakeholder Community! Read more, Download the meeting agenda & Register: → https://lnkd.in/dzpjG2dQ #ACT4CAP27, #HorizonEU, #EuropeanGreenDeal, #PolicyModelling, #AgriFoodPolicies, #Sustainability, #Resilience, #FoodSystems, #EvidenceBasedPolicy, #EUAgriFood, #ClimateAction, #Collaboration, #Research, #CapacityBuilding #PolicyModelling, #FutureOfCAP, #EuropeanPolicy, #PolicyImpact, #HolisticApproach, #Synergies, #AgriFoodResearch	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7250436279337635840	10/11/2024	All followers	264		16	0.060606062	5	2	0.087121211	
Are you interested in the future of European #livestock? On 2nd October 2024 join the 1st stakeholder gathering online of our fellow project STEP UP! Check out here what the #HorizonEurope STEP UP project is all about: https://lnkd.in/g9XA6W_8	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7244243162066534403	09/24/2024	All followers	78		3	0.03846154	0	0	0.03846154	
WP6 Workshop on Modelling the Future of EU-Ukraine Relationship 18 September 2024 The ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project project hosted a hybrid workshop on modelling the future of EU-Ukraine relations on 18 September 2024 at the Warsaw University of Life Sciences (SGGW), Poland. Organized by the Thünen Institute of Market Analysis (Germany), Wageningen Economic Research (Netherlands), and Polissia National University (Ukraine), this workshop was a side event to the 189th EAAE Seminar "EU Entanglement by (Post)-War Ukraine: Implications for the Agri-Food Markets." The workshop, held in the frame of ACT4CAP27's WP6 activities (Tasks 6.1 and 6.2), focused on assessing EU agri-food policies post-2027 with a specific emphasis on the EU-Ukraine relationship. Over the course of three hours, more than 30 participants openly discussed the current and future state of this relationship and explored possible scenarios for modelling agricultural markets. Read the full article here: https://lnkd.in/dYuzt6ia	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7242797300970868736	09/20/2024	All followers	315		13	0.041269843	11	2	0.082539685	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p>📌 We are pleased to announce the ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project 1st Stakeholder Meeting</p> <p>📅 Wed, 23 October 2024, 09:00 to 13:00 📍 Thon Hotel EU, Wetstraat / Rue de la Loi 75, Brussels 1040, Belgium</p> <p>Join the ACT4CAP27 Stakeholder Community!</p> <p>Read more & Register: → https://lnkd.in/dzpjG2dQ</p> <p>#ACT4CAP27 #HorizonEU #EuropeanGreenDeal #PolicyModelling #AgriFoodPolicies #Sustainability #Resilience #FoodSystems #EvidenceBasedPolicy #EUAgriFood #ClimateAction #Collaboration #Research #CapacityBuilding #FutureOfCAP #EuropeanPolicy #PolicyImpact #HolisticApproach #Synergies #AgriFoodResearch</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7237354524921741313	09/05/2024	All followers	630		54	0.085714288	15	6	0.119047619	
<p>Did you know that as part of our dedication to #OpenAccess, we have a specific community page for ACT4CAP27 at Zenodo?</p> <p>Why is this important? Disseminating our research through open access ensures that valuable insights and advancements are freely accessible to the global community. By regularly updating and making our emerging project outputs available on the ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project Zenodo Community page – that is also part of the EU Open Research Repository – we aim to foster collaboration, encourage dialogue among stakeholders, and contribute to the collective progress of policy research and development.</p> <p>How can you stay updated? We invite you to follow and regularly check the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo community page for the latest updates, publications, and findings from our project.</p> <p>Visit the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo community page: https://lnkd.in/gHxQfv5Z</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7361115161404825600	08/12/2025	All followers	54		0	0	0	0	0	
<p>📄 📄 New Joint Perspective Paper: Why Sustainable Agriculture Matters for Europe's Future 🌱</p> <p>The Horizon Europe projects ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project, BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project, and LAMASUS have released a joint perspective paper highlighting how a sustainable agricultural sector is essential to the EU's economic prosperity, food security, and environmental sustainability.</p> <p>With agriculture underpinning a €1 trillion agrifood supply chain and playing a key role in climate and trade policy, the paper identifies five Priority Action Areas (PAAs) to strengthen Europe's future:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✅ PAA1. Fostering income and resilience through result-based policies that integrate economic and environmental performance. ✅ PAA2. Integrated nutrient management to enhance strategic autonomy. ✅ PAA3. Enhancing the agrifood sector competitiveness and food security through level-playing field trade agreements. ✅ PAA4. Strengthening innovation leadership in the new bioeconomy ✅ PAA5. Democratizing digitalization to ensure agricultural sector attractiveness and technological innovation. <p>Backed by decades of modelling expertise, the authors call for updated tools to better connect economics, environment, and innovation — laying the groundwork for smarter, more impactful policies beyond 2027.</p> <p>👉 Read how economic modelling is shaping the next generation of EU agri-food policy:</p> <p>📄 Executive summary (pdf on Zenodo): https://lnkd.in/d4k4tPR8</p> <p>📄 Full perspective paper (pdf on Zenodo): https://lnkd.in/df_TKN8N</p> <p>📄 Press release (pdf / text-only version on Zenodo): https://lnkd.in/d48tNhMp</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7354216483343761408	07/24/2025	All followers	721		33	0.045769766	20	3	0.077669904	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p>Authors: Petr Havlik, Hans Van Meijl, Tamás Krisztin, Marc Müller, Siemen Van Berkum, Thomas Fellmann, Alexander Gocht, Hervé Guyomard, Tassos Haniotis, Alan Matthews, Paolo Scokkai, Davit Stepanyan, Dr. , Peter Witzke, Katalin Balázs, Dylan Bos</p> <p>International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen Social & Economic Research, Joint Research Centre – European Commission, Seville , Thünen Institute, Trinity College Dublin, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Planslab Kft., POSSESSIO Ltd.</p> <p>#HorizonEurope #CAP #VisionForAgriculture, #EUagriculture, #FutureOfFood, and #SustainableFoodSystem #SustainableAgriculture #Bioeconomy #DigitalFarming #FoodSecurity #EUGreenDeal #ACT4CAP27 #BrightSpace #LAMASUS #WeCooperate</p>											
<p> https://agmemod.eu/</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7348287191955005441	07/08/2025	All followers	382		35	0.091623038	12	0	0.123036653	
<p> Learn more about the project: https://act4cap27.eu/</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7339235376592486402	06/13/2025	All followers	295		15	0.050847456	7	3	0.091525421	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
#ACT4CAP27 #HorizonEurope #AgriFoodPolicy #SustainableAgriculture #PolicyModelling #ScienceToPolicy #AMYRN #EURResearch #NewsletterUpdate											
<p> https://lnkd.in/dEfdZnKu Let's build a sustainable and inclusive future for European agriculture, together. #ACT4CAP27 #HorizonEurope #AgriFoodPolicy #EUProjects #StakeholderEngagement #ProjectCommunication #SustainableAgriculture #ScienceToPolicy</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7339229625102884865	06/13/2025	All followers	178		2	0.011235955	4	1	0.039325844	
<p> https://lnkd.in/d7n2wyBK</p> <p>#ACT4CAP27 #HorizonEurope #AgriFoodPolicy #SustainableAgriculture #PolicyModelling #StakeholderEngagement #EURResearch #Newsletter #CAP27</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7333121924371316737	05/27/2025	All followers	156		4	0.025641026	2	1	0.044871796	
<p> https://lnkd.in/dbivyeEq</p> <p>#ACT4CAP27 #HorizonEurope #SustainableAgriculture #FoodSystems #AgriFoodPolicy #ScienceToPolicy #StakeholderEngagement #ResearchImpact</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7333116566722494465	05/27/2025	All followers	952		57	0.05987395	27	1	0.089285716	
<p>ACT4CAP27 WP Leaders' Meeting: Progress, Planning & Policy Insights On 20 May, the ACT4CAP27 WP leads met to reflect on recent milestones —including an online stakeholder meeting with 60+ participants — and to coordinate the next steps across all work streams. From finalizing the Fast Track Scenarios to expanding modelling collaborations and launching the AMYRN Young Researcher Network, the project continues to advance its mission of delivering cutting-edge tools for EU agri-food policy modelling beyond 2027.</p> <p> https://lnkd.in/dJmQUp</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7333109123577700352	05/27/2025	All followers	293		37	0.126279861	6	0	0.146757677	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
#ACT4CAP27 #HorizonEurope #AgriFoodPolicy #SustainableAgriculture #ResearchImpact #AMYRN #ModelingEUFoodSystems #StakeholderEngagement #CAP27											
<p>On 24 April, the ACT4CAP27 project was presented at a dialogue event hosted by Polissia National University and organised by ULEAD with Europe. Local leaders, researchers, and innovators came together to explore how Horizon Europe and Digital Europe programmes can support communities in the Zhytomyr region.</p> <p>🔗 ACT4CAP27 was highlighted as a key initiative helping shape future EU agricultural policy through model-based research and collaboration.</p> <p>📄 Read the full story: https://lnkd.in/dBg9aVTN</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7330254406849859584	05/19/2025	All followers	86		0	0	5	0	0.058139537	
#ACT4CAP27 #HorizonEurope #DigitalEurope #EUFunded #RegionalDevelopment #Ukraine #CAPreform #Innovation #PolissiaUniversity #EUresearch											
<p>🎉 On 6 May, ACT4CAP27 hosted its second stakeholder consultation, bringing together researchers, policymakers, and agri-food sector voices from across Europe to explore priorities for the Common Agricultural Policy post-2027. From result-based income support to private financing options and eligibility conditions — the discussions were rich, diverse, and future-focused.</p> <p>👏 We would like to thank also here to all stakeholders for their contributions!</p> <p>🔗 Curious about the key insights and what comes next?</p> <p>👉 Read the full recap on our website: https://lnkd.in/dVXHwdSN</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7328733409323671553	05/15/2025	All followers	238		15	0.063025214	4	1	0.084033616	
#CAP #EUAgriPolicy #EUAgriVision #ACT4CAP27 #SustainableFarming #StakeholderEngagement #HorizonEurope											
<p>ACT4CAP27 Training Activities for 2025 – Planning & Collaboration</p> <p>On 4 April 2025, an online meeting was held to discuss Task 5.4 – Planning Training Activities for 2025 as part of ACT4CAP27's ongoing capacity-building efforts. Convened by WP5 leader Universidad Politécnica de Madrid and moderated by Maria Blanco, the session outlined upcoming training initiatives, collaboration opportunities, and budget considerations.</p> <p>🔴 Key Discussion Points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✅ Training Plans for 2025 – Overview of past and upcoming training events: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔗 #CAPRI Developer Seminar (11-12 March 2025, Berlin) 🔗 CAPRI Course 2025 – Now open for registration! 🔗 #AGMEMOD Training Course (17-20 June 2025, The Hague) ✅ Collaboration with Fellow Projects – Strengthening synergies with BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project and Tools4CAP to enhance knowledge exchange and capacity-building efforts. ✅ Training Budget & Technicalities – Reviewing procedures to ensure efficient use of the ACT4CAP27 training budget. <p>📌 Stay updated on ACT4CAP27's capacity-building activities here: https://lnkd.in/dhu6z5N2</p> <p>🔗 Read more about the meeting: https://lnkd.in/dXbtdZja</p> <p>#ACT4CAP27 #CapacityBuilding #AgriFoodModelling #Training #Collaboration</p> <p>Thünen Institute, Wageningen Social & Economic Research, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Università degli studi Roma TRE</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7313880598715031553	04/04/2025	All followers	245		27	0.110204078	8	1	0.146938771	
Capacity Building: CAPRI Course 2025: Applied Data Analysis – Now Open for Registration! https://lnkd.in/dDP4DmYC											
<p>🏠 Organized by the Thünen Institute with support from the CAPRI consortium, this course provides hands-on training in the CAPRI partial equilibrium model, widely used for market and policy analysis.</p> <p>📅 April 17 – July 17, 2025</p> <p>🕒 Every Thursday 12:00 – 16:00 CET</p> <p>📍 Hybrid format Humboldt University of Berlin</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7311347690263502848	03/28/2025	All followers	366		45	0.122950822	10	3	0.158469945	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p>As part of ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project and BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project, the course is open to external participants and Master's students in Agricultural Economics at Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin.</p> <p>💡 Led by Alexander Gocht (Thünen) with support of Davit Stepanyan, Dr., Davide Pignotti, Ferike Thom, Dr. Jörg Rieger, and with contributions of core developers of the CAPRI network such as Maria Blanco, Torbjörn Jansson, Caetano Luiz Beber, the course covers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 Introduction to the GAMS modelling language 🔴 Overview of the CAPRI modelling system 🔴 Hands-on exercises & deep dives into model components <p>This is a unique opportunity to develop practical skills in agri-food policy modelling.</p> <p>📌 Register now: Moodle Registration https://lnkd.in/ejeUgBkm</p> <p>📄 Course details: CAPRI Course Webpage https://lnkd.in/eWuzYb88</p> <p>#CAPRI #CapacityBuilding #AgriFoodModelling #EconomicModelling #PolicyAnalysis #ACT4CAP27 #BrightSpaceEU</p>											
<p>🔗 Capacity Building: AGMEMOD Training Course, 17-20 June 2025, The Hague, NL https://lnkd.in/dyqdHkV5</p> <p>Wageningen University & Research (WUR) and the Thünen Institute (THÜNEN) invite researchers, policymakers, and professionals to the upcoming AGMEMOD Training Course, taking place June 17-20, 2025, in The Hague.</p> <p>🔍 About AGMEMOD AGMEMOD is a key partial equilibrium model used for agricultural economic analysis across the EU. This training will equip new modellers with essential skills and foster collaboration within the AGMEMOD consortium and beyond.</p> <p>🎯 Course Highlights:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 Applications of AGMEMOD – Research & policy relevance 🔴 Data requirements & processing 🔴 Model structure & equations 🔴 Scenario modelling & analysis <p>💡 Who should attend?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✅ Researchers & analysts in agricultural policy modelling ✅ Early-career professionals in economic modelling ✅ AGMEMOD consortium members & partners <p>📄 Participation & Registration The course is free, supported by Horizon Europe projects Tools4CAP, BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project, and ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project, but participants must cover their own travel, accommodation, and meals.</p> <p>📧 For inquiries, contact Ana Gonzalez Martinez at ana.gonzalezmartinez@wur.nl.</p> <p>We look forward to welcoming you to The Hague for this exciting training opportunity!</p> <p>#AGMEMOD #CapacityBuilding #EconomicModelling #AgriculturalPolicy #BrightSpaceEU #Tools4CAP #ACT4CAP27</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7310590095298904064	03/25/2025	All followers	241		9	0.0373444	6	2	0.070539422	
<p>ACT4CAP27 WP8 Work Package Leaders' Meeting – 18 March 2025 https://lnkd.in/d6eA3h2b</p> <p>On 18 March 2025, the ACT4CAP27 WP8 leads met online to align priorities and drive forward key project activities. Key updates from the meeting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 DG AGRI Vision Conference (8 May, Brussels & online) 	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:731021	03/25/2025	All followers	85		1	0.011764706	3	0	0.047058824	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p>Work is underway to finalize the Vision100 paper in collaboration with the BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project and LAMASUS projects, ahead of the conference.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fast-Track Scenarios <p>A consolidated report is nearing completion and will soon be shared internally for review and discussion.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP2 Follow-Up <p>Rome meeting documentation is being finalized to ensure action points are effectively tracked.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder Engagement <p>The 2nd stakeholder meeting is planned for early May 2025, focusing on Vision100 and post-CAP27 themes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agri-Food Modelling Young Researcher Network (#AMYRN) <p>Funding opportunities for early - career researchers to collaborate across ACT4CAP27 partners - first expressions of interest have already been received!</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> First Reporting Period <p>The timeline for the first reporting period (March 2024 – August 2025) was presented, ensuring smooth documentation and reporting processes.</p> <p>Next WP8 meeting: 15 April 2025</p> <p>Looking forward to continued progress in the coming months! #ACT4CAP27 #AgriFoodPolicy #ResearchCollaboration #ClimateResilience</p>	9592293875712										
<p>Supporting the Next Generation of Agri-Food Modellers</p> <p>As part of ACT4CAP27, the Agri-Food Model Young Researcher Network (AMYRN) is fostering a new wave of expertise in simulation modelling for agri-food policy within the ACT4CAP27 partner organisations.</p> <p>Economic models like AGMEMOD, CAPRI, GLOBIOM, and MAGNET play a crucial role in assessing land use, biodiversity, climate change, and food security. Mastering these models requires specialized knowledge, from using software like GAMS and GEMPACK to handling large geospatial datasets.</p> <p>AMYRN is open to PhDs and early-career postdocs already engaged in ACT4CAP27 research, helping them gain practical experience and build future modelling capacity.</p> <p>Are you a young ACT4CAP27 researcher interested in joining? The AMYRN call will soon be published!</p> <p>Keep being informed and learn more here: https://lnkd.in/dRb6VjBN</p> <p>#ACT4CAP27 #AgriFoodModelling #YoungResearchers #CapacityBuilding</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7310216644499283968	03/25/2025	All followers	582		39	0.067010306	22	5	0.113402061	
<p>ACT4CAP2 Annual Meeting – Day 1 in Rome!</p> <p>A day full of insightful discussions, innovative ideas, and great collaboration! Here's a visual summary capturing the highlights of our first day.</p> <p>For more details, check out the full summary here: https://lnkd.in/dg-b7nMC</p> <p>Looking forward to another productive day tomorrow!</p> <p>#ACT4CAP2 #SustainableFoodSystems #Collaboration #Innovation #EUAgri</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7300314869294129152	02/26/2025	All followers	334	320	41	0.122754492	12	5	0.173652694	Video
<p>Shaping the Future of EU Agri-Food Policy</p> <p>We're excited to kick off the ACT4CAP27 Annual Consortium Meeting 2025 at the Università degli studi Roma TRE! This gathering brings together our project partners to review progress and map out the next steps in supporting EU agri-food policies beyond 2027.</p> <p>Our focus?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthening analytical tools Refining research methodologies Enhancing collaboration to address future challenges 	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7300090663004479488	02/25/2025	All followers	238		10	0.042016808	8	3	0.088235296	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p>With the evolving European Green Deal and CAP post-2027, we're working to improve policy impact assessments and develop better modelling frameworks to support evidence-based decision-making.</p> <p>📄 Read our press release https://lnkd.in/dUKqE94e</p>											
<p>📄 New Open Access Article: Optimizing Policy Funding Allocation with Machine Learning</p> <p>We're proud to share that Cristina Vaquero Piñeiro from the ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project contributed to the new open-access article, "Predicting Policy Funding Allocation with Machine Learning", published in Socio-Economic Planning Sciences. This work, partly funded by ACT4CAP27, explores how machine learning can improve the efficiency of agricultural policy funding, ensuring resources are allocated where they will have the most impact.</p> <p>Key takeaways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♦ Accurate Predictions: Machine learning models forecast policy funding allocation with greater precision. ♦ Data-Driven Decisions: Using insights from large datasets, policymakers can optimize their funding strategies. ♦ Supporting Sustainability: This research helps align funding with sustainable agricultural goals. <p>📄 Read the full article here: https://lnkd.in/duF2BvVs</p> <p>#Policy #MachineLearning #Sustainability #Agriculture #ACT4CAP27 #DataScience</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7296944110790205440	02/16/2025	All followers	625		26	0.0416	16	1	0.068800002	
<p>Summer School 2025: Applications Open until February 28, 2025! Land Management for Sustainability 📅 June 2-6, 2025 📍 Laxenburg, Austria</p> <p>The LAMASUS / BrightSpace Summer School 2025 is now accepting applications! This unique one-week program offers an immersive deep dive into advanced land-use and policy modelling, equipping participants with cutting-edge tools to assess the impacts of European agricultural policies.</p> <p>Why Join?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♦ Learn from leading researchers at IIASA, BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project, and LAMASUS ♦ Gain hands-on experience with econometric, biophysical, and integrated modelling ♦ Explore policy pathways, land-use dynamics, and sustainability challenges ♦ Engage in interactive workshops and real-world applications of policy analysis <p>Who Should Apply? This summer school is ideal for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✅ PhD students & early-career researchers ✅ Policy analysts supporting ministries & EU institutions ✅ Experts working in land-use, climate, and sustainability sectors <p>Trainers The course will be taught by experienced International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA) scientists working in the LAMASUS project and BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project: Tamás Krisztin, Petr Havlik, Tassos Haniotis, Linda See, Michael Wögerer, Juraj Balkovic, Richard Cornford, Felicity Addo</p> <p>Application Deadline: February 28, 2025</p> <p>Don't miss this opportunity to enhance your expertise in sustainable land management and policy evaluation!</p> <p>📄 Apply Now & Learn More: https://lnkd.in/d6cg-Nqe</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7296911549208657920	02/16/2025	All followers	192		5	0.026041666	2	0	0.036458332	
<p>ACT4CAP27 is now also on Bluesky!</p> <p>☀️ Stay updated on the latest in agricultural sustainability, policy insights, and policy modelling research — now on Bluesky! 🌱 Follow us for project updates, events, and key discussions shaping the future of European food systems.</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:acti	02/16/2025	All followers	122		7	0.057377048	5	0	0.098360658	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p>Join the conversation & follow us today!</p> <p>https://lnkd.in/d5NtuGee</p>	<p>vity:7296910972877729793</p>										
<p>WP8 Leaders Prepare for the ACT4CAP27 Annual Consortium Meeting</p> <p>On 11 February 2025, the WP8 work package leaders met online to refine the agenda for the Annual Consortium Meeting, taking place on 25-26 February in Rome, Italy. This key event will set the course for the next phase of the ACT4CAP27 project, ensuring that research and policy discussions remain aligned with the evolving landscape of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) post-2027.</p> <p>The Rome meeting will focus on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✔ Revisiting project objectives and expectations ✔ Refining strategies for WP2 & WP3, including database expansion & model improvements ✔ Strengthening collaboration and setting clear timelines for deliverables ✔ Addressing research gaps & enhancing analytical tools for sustainable food systems <p>With WP leaders and task coordinators taking the lead, the discussions will drive progress on health, environmental, and socio-economic assessments as well as food system innovations. This meeting is a crucial step in ensuring the project's impact on shaping future agricultural policies in the EU.</p> <p>📅 Looking forward to insightful discussions in Rome! #ACT4CAP27 #Agriculture #Sustainability #EUPolicy #Research #Collaboration</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7296909972674633728</p>	02/16/2025	All followers	238		28	0.117647059	4	1	0.138655469	
<p>CAPRI Developer Seminar 2025 – Advancing Agricultural Economic Modelling</p> <p>We are excited to announce the CAPRI Developer Seminar 2025:</p> <p>📅 Date: 11-12 March 2025 📍 Place: Berlin, Germany Host: Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, International Agricultural Trade and Development (IATD) Thünen Institute of Farm Economics (Thünen)</p> <p>This event will bring together researchers, software developers, and agricultural economists to explore the latest advancements in the Common Agricultural Policy Regionalised Impact (CAPRI) Modelling System, a key tool for economic analysis in agriculture.</p> <p>Key topics include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✔ Latest policy simulations, data updates, and methodological advancements ✔ Insights from BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project & ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project, enhancing CAPRI's ability to assess sustainability, climate impacts, and policy interventions ✔ Opportunities for collaboration and knowledge exchange among CAPRI developers, policymakers, and researchers <p>The seminar is open to students and PhD candidates interested in agricultural economic modeling, providing them with a unique opportunity to engage with experts in the field.</p> <p>📅 Mark your calendar! 📄 View the agenda here: https://lnkd.in/d8c7YrHK Maximum number of participants: 30</p> <p>🔗 Learn more about CAPRI: https://lnkd.in/dQfnSwFd</p> <p>#CAPRI #AgriculturalEconomics #PolicyModelling #Sustainability #CapacityBuilding</p> <p>EuroCare Bonn, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, European Commission Joint Research Centre JRC Seville and Ispra, EAER - Swiss Federal Office for Agriculture</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7293991926054240257</p>	02/08/2025	All followers	622		24	0.038585208	19	1	0.070739552	
<p>Predicting EU Funding Success with Machine Learning</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com</p>	02/08/2025	All followers	309		26	0.084142394	6	0	0.103559874	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p>At the XXIII SIEPI Annual Workshop (University of Bologna, Jan 30-31, 2025), Cristina Vaquero Piñeiro from the UNIROMA3 team of the ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project presented their research on leveraging Machine Learning (ML) to predict EU funding success.</p> <p> Why does this matter? EU funding plays a crucial role in economic development, particularly in rural and environmental policies under the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD). Understanding what factors influence funding allocation before decisions are made can help policymakers optimize resource distribution and guide applicants toward success.</p> <p> The Research Approach:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Firm-level data from the Italian Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) 8 different ML algorithms tested - Random Forest delivered the best predictions Key factors influencing funding success: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Location (firms in mountain areas more likely to receive funds) Economic diversification (smaller, diversified farms had better chances) Sustainability & Certification (organic certification boosted funding prospects) Generational shift (younger entrepreneurs had higher success rates) <p> Key Takeaways for Policy & Practice:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better targeting of funds—policymakers can anticipate who is most likely to win funding and identify potential gaps. Smarter investment decisions—farmers & businesses can align strategies with key funding success factors. Boosting sustainability efforts—incentivizing environmentally friendly practices through better-designed policies. <p> Access the presentation at the ACT4CAP27 Zenodo Community page https://lnkd.in/dq4hTs33</p> <p>Source: University of Roma Tre</p> <p>#MachineLearning #EUFunding #PolicyInnovation #Agriculture #RuralDevelopment #Sustainability #ACT4CAP27 #SIEPI</p>	m/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7293926745685024770										
<p> GREEN & DIGITAL POLISSIA: AGRICULTURE </p> <p>The second key event of the year took place at POLIDIH, the European Digital Innovation Hub at Polissya National University. Opened by Rector of Polissya National University, Oleh Skydan, the forum gathered farmers, entrepreneurs, and stakeholders from the Zhytomyr and Rivne regions, offering a platform to explore digital opportunities and sustainable agribusiness solutions.</p> <p>The ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project was presented by Olga Nikoljuk, Head of the Educational and Research Center for Digital Technologies and Natural Resources Systems Modelling at Polissya National University. Olga showcased how ACT4CAP27 aims to strengthen data-driven approaches and analytical tools that will support the evolution of the EU's Common Agricultural Policy beyond 2027. </p> <p>https://lnkd.in/dDcM8PJw</p> <p>The forum also featured insights on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital solutions for sustainable agriculture GIS services for farmers Drone applications in modern farming AGROSUS_HE agroecological strategies for sustainable weed management <p>#ACT4CAP27 #SustainableAgriculture #DigitalInnovation #PolissyaUniversity #Agritech #CommonAgriculturalPolicy</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7292265621969371136	02/03/2025	All followers	240		23	0.095833331	7	0	0.125	
<p>Driving EU Agricultural Policy Forward Eu: ACT4CAP27, BrightSpace, and Lamasus Collaborate </p> <p>Following an online kick-off discussion in December 2024 , colleagues from the ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project, BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project, and LAMASUS project convened in Laxenburg, Austria on 22-23 January 2025, for an in-person working retreat. The goal was to reinforce joint efforts to align EU agricultural #competitiveness with #sustainability goals through innovative policy modeling .</p> <p>Alan Matthews and Tassos Haniotis, as key members of the Project Advisory Group, offered invaluable guidance and inputs to shape the discussion and outcomes. </p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7288298967308636161	01/23/2025	All followers	407	165	40	0.098280095	8	1	0.12039312	Video

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p>Aligning Goals for Impact 🎯</p> <p>During the retreat, we worked toward developing a joint paper 📄, synthesizing insights from the three projects to provide actionable recommendations for EU agricultural policy 🌱.</p> <p>The meeting focused on identifying and reaching consensus on the 🗣️ messages for the paper, ensuring coherence across the participating projects. The team finalized the outline and timeline 🕒, assigning responsibilities for drafting various sections. Additionally, the scenario frameworks proposed by ACT4CAP27, BrightSpace, and Lamasus were reviewed and aligned to maximize complementarity and synergies 🔄, enhancing the collective impact of the projects.</p> <p>Collaboration as a Catalyst for Change 🤝</p> <p>This retreat underscores the importance of partnership 🤝 in tackling the complex challenges of EU agriculture 🌱. By pooling expertise 🧠 and integrating diverse perspectives 🗣️, the participating projects aim to deliver a comprehensive framework that balances agricultural competitiveness with sustainable practices 🌿.</p> <p>🙏 We are especially grateful to our colleagues at IIASA 🧑‍🌾 for their role in initiating, organizing, and fostering the positive and productive atmosphere of this retreat.</p> <p>The outcomes of this retreat will culminate in a joint paper 📄, presenting strategic recommendations and actionable insights to guide EU agricultural policy forward.</p> <p>📢 Stay tuned for updates as this important work progresses!</p> <p>Wageningen Social & Economic Research, Thünen Institute, INRAE, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Planlab Kft., POSSESSIO Ltd. ACT4CAP27 Prepares for its 1st Annual Consortium Meeting in Rome</p>											
<p>As ACT4CAP27 approaches its first anniversary, preparations are underway for the Annual Consortium Meeting, which will be held in Rome on 24–25 February 2025, hosted by our UniRoma3 partner. To ensure the meeting’s success, work package (WP) leaders gathered online on 14 January to discuss the draft agenda and logistics.</p> <p>What’s on the Agenda?</p> <p>The Annual Consortium Meeting will focus on key objectives to guide the project into its second year:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Revisiting Objectives: Reflect on ACT4CAP27’s goals and reconfirm its relevance in the current research and political landscape. ◆ Strategic Planning: Identify priority topics for Year Two, aligned with the project’s work plan. ◆ Deliverable Roadmap: Establish a clear understanding of deliverables up to the 1st interim report in August 2025 and beyond. ◆ Defining Strategies: Develop actionable strategies at both the project and WP levels. <p>Areas of Focus</p> <p>Special attention will be given to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Developing the conceptual framework for the project. ◆ Advancing the database and model portal for accessibility and usability. ◆ Strengthening the modular modelling toolbox for robust analytical capabilities. ◆ Supporting capacity building for young researchers and partners from non-participating organizations. ◆ Enhancing the stakeholder process and dissemination to maximize project impact. <p>The online WP leaders’ meeting helped align priorities and ensure all preparations are on track for Rome. We look forward to the insights and strategies that will emerge from the consortium meeting as ACT4CAP27 continues to drive collaboration in addressing challenges in modelling EU agri-food policies.</p> <p>Stay tuned for updates on the outcomes from Rome!</p> <p>#ACT4CAP27 #HorizonEurope</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7285007269518336000	01/14/2025	All followers	235		18	0.076595746	4	0	0.093617022	
<p>Are you interested in how value-added tax reforms can support global health, environmental, and economic policy targets?</p> <p>Read this fresh #OpenAccess article from #ACT4CAP27’s fellow project: BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project!</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/	01/13/2025	All followers	110		8	0.07272727	1	0	0.081818178	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
	te/urn:li:activity:7284637276184203265										
. ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project addresses the need for improved data & modelling tools highlighted at #EUAgriFoodDays by advancing key analytical frameworks (CAPRI, GLOBIOM, MAGNET, AGMEMOD) to support post-2027 agri-food policies. Many thanks to Sophie Helaine & Balázs Bence TÓTH for their continued support to our project!	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7272651418056998915	12/11/2024	All followers	209		23	0.110047847	11	1	0.167464122	
! Talk with us at the EU #AGRIFOODDAYS 2024 👉 for the #PolicyModelling #HorizonEurope #WeCooperate projects' stand: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♦ BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project #EUagriSIOS ♦ LAMASUS #LandUse ♦ ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project #FoodSystem ♦ @mind step project #FarmDecisions Many thanks to our Sci.Officer EUAgri Fanny Le Gloux! ACT4CAP27 partners: Wageningen Economic Research, Ecorys, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Thünen Institute, Polissia National University Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, UCL, EuroCare, UniRoma3, SLU, Joint Research Centre of the European Commission, Wageningen University & Research, POSSESSIO Ltd.	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7272281334738280448	12/10/2024	All followers	168		9	0.053571429	9	2	0.119047619	
We are very pleased to inform you that we have just released the 1st issue of the ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project Newsletter. Access and browse it here: https://lnkd.in/dMN_VY3q What ACT4CAP27 is all about? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♦ ACT4CAP27 is an EC funded 5-year Horizon Europe research and innovation action aiming to enhance analytical capabilities, tools, and collaborative technical infrastructure within the policy modelling community, to provide support for evidence-based EU agri-food policies post-2027. From this issue of our newsletter, you can get to know: Which organisations are in the project team? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♦ The consortium of ACT4CAP27 consists of 13 partners from 10 countries in Europe (AT, BE, DE, IT, HU, NL, ES, SE, UA, UK), and the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission. How is the project structured? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♦ The ACT4CAP27 project is managed through 8 work packages (WP), each of which is responsible for various parts of the five-year project. What are the latest developments in our project? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♦ Read the letter from our Coordinator, Siemen van Berkum looking back at the first 10 months of project implementation. ♦ From kick-off to various activities: learn more about how our partners work to keep focus on project implementation, including our 1st Stakeholder Meeting held in-presence in October. ♦ Get to know our latest ACT4CAP27 highlights from Ukraine. ♦ Read our 1st policy brief. Where and how are we networking and cooperate with other Horizon Europe Projects?	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7272260040240091139	12/10/2024	All followers	316		17	0.053797469	6	1	0.075949363	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Read more how we cooperate with our fellow project BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project. Read further highlights from our fellow projects, including results from Tools4CAP. <p>What are the upcoming international events where you can meet us?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> There are several events on our list, e.g. ACT4CAP27 will be represented at the Agricultural Outlook Conference in Brussels organized in the framework of the EU #AGRIFOODDAYS between 10-12 December 2024. <p>We hope you will enjoy delving into the latest info about our project.</p> <p>Continue reading the PDF version here: https://lnkd.in/dMN_VY3q</p> <p>Thank you for being an integral part of the ACT4CAP27 community.</p> <p>Wishing you a peaceful festive season and all the best for the new year ahead.</p> <p>Best regards, The ACT4CAP27 project team</p>											
<p> The 1st ACT4CAP27 Newsletter is coming soon!</p> <p>In the first issue of our 6 monthly newsletters you will find information on what ACT4CAP27 is all about, the latest developments and progress in the project, upcoming project activities and relevant events.</p> <p> Subscribe now: https://lnkd.in/d7n2wyBK</p> <p>#ACT4CAP27 #EUAgriFood #Sustainability #HorizonEU #EuropeanGreenDeal </p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7267120944207339520	11/26/2024	All followers	121		3	0.024793388	6	1	0.082644626	
<p>ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project will also be featured today at the Annual Meeting of our fellow project: BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project in Seville. Read the press release of the meeting here:</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7259509875062296577	11/05/2024	All followers	73		2	0.02739726	0	0	0.02739726	
<p>Possessio was representing the ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project at the Conference on Sustainable Agricultural Productivity to Address Food Systems Challenges: Measurement, Data, Drivers and Policies organised on 28 October 2024 in Paris by the OECD Trade and Agriculture Directorate, in collaboration with the European Commission's @Directorate-General on Agriculture and Rural Development and the United States Department of Agriculture.</p> <p>The conference brought together policy makers and researchers to discuss the concept and measurement of sustainable agricultural productivity. It aimed to bridge the gap between academic and policy communities and translate and orient research efforts to pragmatic and policy relevant ways to measure agricultural performance for achieving sustainable productivity growth to address food systems challenges. The exchange among experts and policy makers focussed on the current and evolving state of sustainable agricultural productivity performance and the state of the art on measurement and data, as well as on the main challenges to reconcile productivity and sustainability, focusing particularly on the environmental aspects of sustainability.</p> <p>ACT4CAP27 project communications task leader, Katalin Balázs, invited participant to the event, emphasized how ACT4CAP's interdisciplinary analytical framework can grasp all dimensions of sustainable agricultural productivity, and will provide robust, data-driven insights to aid policymakers in crafting well-informed, effective agri-food policies for the post-2027 landscape in the EU. The creation of sustainable food systems is crucial for the long-term resilience and prosperity of the EU agricultural sector. https://lnkd.in/dSEqmFNc</p> <p>We would like to also thank here the organisers for the invitation and for this great opportunity to expose our project to a wide array of policy makers and professionals working in this area across the world.</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7258782742874574850	11/03/2024	All followers	268		14	0.052238807	7	0	0.078358211	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
The full recording of the conference is available at the event's page: https://lnkd.in/eaYaCNiv https://lnkd.in/dUEqK77H											
Join us on-site or on-line oe.cd/SPGconf for the OECD Trade and Agriculture Conference on #sustainable #agricultural #productivity on 28 October!	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7256272090226442240	10/27/2024	All followers	62		2	0.032258064	0	0	0.032258064	
The #ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project also works for - Enhancing #analyticaltools enabling coherent and reliable #policyevaluations for supporting Evidence-Based Policymaking Post-2027 by providing robust, data-driven insights to aid policymakers in crafting well-informed, effective agri-food policies for the post-2027 landscape, - Interdisciplinary Analytical Framework: to quantify economic, social, environmental, and climate #sustainability impacts of EU #agri-food policies, addressing all components of the European #GreenDeal, ensuring comprehensive policy #impact #assessments.	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7256259300468150272	10/27/2024	All followers	100		3	0.029999999	2	0	0.050000001	
Many thanks to all participants of the 1st Stakeholder Meeting of ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project for their valuable contributions! Read more: https://lnkd.in/dxss8a88 Wageningen Economic Research, Ecorys, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Thünen Institute, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, UCL	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7254857886504247297	10/23/2024	All followers	288	239	23	0.079861112	13	2	0.131944448	Video
#ACT4CAP27 was introduced to EC officers & representatives of fellow projects today at the European Research Executive Agency (REA) Horizon EU projects Cluster meeting in Brussels https://lnkd.in/dAnymAF BrightSpace Horizon Europe Project, LAMASUS, ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project, AgEnRes, STEP UP, MATS H2020, Trade4SD - EU Horizon 2020, BATModel, Tools4CAP	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7254583594025689089	10/22/2024	All followers	497	274	27	0.054325957	16	8	0.102615692	Video
Thon Hotel EU, Wetstraat / Rue de la Loi 75, Brussels 1040, Belgium Join the ACT4CAP27 Stakeholder Community! Read more, Download the meeting agenda & Register: → https://lnkd.in/dzpjG2dQ #ACT4CAP27, #HorizonEU, #EuropeanGreenDeal, #PolicyModelling, #AgriFoodPolicies, #Sustainability, #Resilience, #FoodSystems, #EvidenceBasedPolicy, #EUAgriFood, #ClimateAction, #Collaboration, #Research, #CapacityBuilding #PolicyModelling, #FutureOfCAP, #EuropeanPolicy, #PolicyImpact, #HolisticApproach, #Synergies, #AgriFoodResearch	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7250436279337635840	10/11/2024	All followers	264		16	0.060606062	5	2	0.087121211	
Are you interested in the future of European #livestock? On 2nd October 2024 join the 1st stakeholder gathering online of our fellow project STEP UP! Check out here what the #HorizonEurope STEP UP project is all about: https://lnkd.in/g9XA6W_8	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7244243162066534403	09/24/2024	All followers	78		3	0.03846154	0	0	0.03846154	

Post title	Post link	Created date (mm/dd/yyyy)	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	Click through rate (CTR)	Likes	Reposts	Engagement rate	Content Type
<p>WP6 Workshop on Modelling the Future of EU-Ukraine Relationship 18 September 2024</p> <p>The ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project project hosted a hybrid workshop on modelling the future of EU-Ukraine relations on 18 September 2024 at the Warsaw University of Life Sciences (SGGW), Poland. Organized by the Thünen Institute of Market Analysis (Germany), Wageningen Economic Research (Netherlands), and Polissia National University (Ukraine), this workshop was a side event to the 189th EAAE Seminar “EU Enlargement by (Post)-War Ukraine: Implications for the Agri-Food Markets.”</p> <p>The workshop, held in the frame of ACT4CAP27’s WP6 activities (Tasks 6.1 and 6.2), focused on assessing EU agri-food policies post-2027 with a specific emphasis on the EU-Ukraine relationship. Over the course of three hours, more than 30 participants openly discussed the current and future state of this relationship and explored possible scenarios for modelling agricultural markets. Read the full article here: https://lnkd.in/dYuzt6ia</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7242797300970868736	09/20/2024	All followers	315		13	0.041269843	11	2	0.082539685	
<p>📌 We are pleased to announce the ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe Project 1st Stakeholder Meeting</p> <p>📅 Wed, 23 October 2024, 09:00 to 13:00 📍 Thon Hotel EU, Wetstraat / Rue de la Loi 75, Brussels 1040, Belgium</p> <p>Join the ACT4CAP27 Stakeholder Community!</p> <p>Read more & Register: ➔ https://lnkd.in/dzpjG2dQ</p> <p>#ACT4CAP27 #HorizonEU #EuropeanGreenDeal #PolicyModelling #AgriFoodPolicies #Sustainability #Resilience #FoodSystems #EvidenceBasedPolicy #EUAgriFood #ClimateAction #Collaboration #Research #CapacityBuilding #FutureOfCAP #EuropeanPolicy #PolicyImpact #HolisticApproach #Synergies #AgriFoodResearch</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7237354524921741313	09/05/2024	All followers	630		54	0.085714288	15	6	0.119047619	

APPENDIX 4 ZENODO COMMUNITY PAGE RECORDS

July 24, 2025 (v1) Other Open

Press release: Sustainable Agriculture: A Cornerstone of Europe's Economic Prosperity and Strategic Security

International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis ; Planslab Kft.; and 1 other

This is a press release about the launch of the joint perspective paper available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413131> Horizon Europe projects ACT4CAP27, BrightSpace and LAMASUS release a joint perspective paper offering new insights for the future of the EU's agri-food poli...

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Uploaded on July 24, 2025

 94
 73

July 24, 2025 (v1) Working paper Open

Executive summary: Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security

Havlik, Petr ; and 12 others

This is the Executive summary of the paper: Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security The EU is facing a convergence of strategic challenges — geopolitical uncertainty, climate crisis, economic stagnation, and social inequality. The 2024–202...

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 85

July 24, 2025 (v1) Working paper Open

Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security

Havlik, Petr ; and 12 others

The EU is facing a convergence of strategic challenges — geopolitical uncertainty, climate crisis, economic stagnation, and social inequality. The 2024–2029 Strategic Agenda underscores the urgency to ensure Europe remains free, democratic, secure, competitive, and prosperous...

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Uploaded on July 24, 2025

 315
 244

June 12, 2025 (final version) Other Open

Project flyer: ACT4CAP27: Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

Wageningen University & Research ; Possessio Kft.

This is the English language version of the project flyer introducing the ACT4CAP27 project (updated in 2025). Further information ACT4CAP27 Project coordination: Wageningen Economic Research, The Hague, NLContact: act4cap27@wur.nl | Website: <https://act4cap27.eu/> Project...

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Uploaded on June 13, 2025

1 more versions exist for this record

 53

June 12, 2025 (final version) Other Open

Буклет проекту: АСТ4САР27: Розвиток потенціалуаналітичних інструментів для підтримки спільної сільськогосподарської політики після 2027 року

Wageningen University & Research ; Planslab Kft.

Ось українська версія інформаційного буклету, що представляє проєкт АСТ4САР27. Додаткова інформація Координація проєкту АСТ4САР27: Wageningen Social and Economic Research, Гаага, НідерландиКонтакт: act4cap27@wur.nl | Вебсайт: <https://act4cap27.eu/>...

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Uploaded on June 13, 2025

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June 12, 2025 (final version) Other Open

Projektbroschyr: ACT4CAP27: Förbättra kapacitet och analytiska verktyg för att stödja den gemensamma jordbrukspolitiken efter 2027

Wageningen University & Research ; Possessio Kft.

Detta är den svenska versionen av projektbroschyren som presenterar ACT4CAP27-projektet. Mer information Samordning av ACT4CAP27-projektet: Wageningen Social and Economic Research, Haag, Nederländerna Kontakt: act4cap27@wur.nl | Webbplats: <https://act4cap27.eu/>...

Part of EU Open Research Repository

Uploaded on June 13, 2025

 9

June 12, 2025 (final) Other Open

Projectfolder: ACT4CAP27: Bevordering van de capaciteit en analytische instrumenten ter ondersteuning van het Gemeenschappelijk Landbouwbeleid na 2027

Wageningen University & Research ; Possessio Kft.

Dit is de Nederlandstalige versie van de projectfolder ter introductie van het ACT4CAP27-project. Meer informatie Projectcoördinatie ACT4CAP27: Wageningen Economic Research, Den Haag, Nederland Contact: act4cap27@wur.nl | Website: <https://act4cap27.eu/> Projectduur: 1 maart 2024 ...

Part of EU Open Research Repository

Uploaded on June 13, 2025

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June 12, 2025 (final version) Other Open

Volantino del progetto: ACT4CAP27: Competenze e strumenti analitici per supportare la Politica Agricola Comune dopo il 2027

Wageningen University & Research ; Possessio Kft.

Ecco la versione italiana del volantino del progetto che presenta il progetto ACT4CAP27. Ulteriori informazioni Coordinamento del progetto ACT4CAP27: Wageningen Social and Economic Research, L'Aia, Paesi Bassi Contatto: act4cap27@wur.nl | Sito web: <https://act4cap27.eu/> Dur...

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Uploaded on June 13, 2025

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June 12, 2025 (final version) Other Open

Projektismertető: AT4CAP27: Elemzési eszközök fejlesztése és modellezési kapacitás építése a 2027 utáni Közös Agrárpolitika támogatásához

Wageningen University & Research ; Possessio Kft.

Ez az anyag az ACT4CAP27 projekt tájékoztatójának magyar nyelvű változata. További információ ACT4CAP27 projekt koordinátor: Wageningen Social and Economic Research, Hága, Hollandia Kapcsolat: act4cap27@wur.nl | Honlap: <https://act4cap27.eu/> A projekt időtartama: 2024. márci...

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Folleto del proyecto: ACT4CAP27: Mejora de la capacitación y de las herramientas analíticas para el apoyo de la Política Agraria Común a partir de 2027

Wageningen University & Research ; Possessio Kft.

Esta es la versión en español del folleto del proyecto que presenta el proyecto ACT4CAP27. Más información Coordinación del proyecto ACT4CAP27: Wageningen Social and Economic Research, La Haya, Países Bajos Contacto: act4cap27@wur.nl | Sitio web: <https://act4cap27.eu/>...

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Projektflyer: ACT4CAP27: Weiterentwicklung von Kapazitäten und Analyseinstrumenten zur Unterstützung der Gemeinsamen Agrarpolitik nach 2027

Wageningen University & Research ; Possessio Kft.

Dies ist die deutsche Version des Projektflyers zur Vorstellung des ACT4CAP27-Projekts. Weitere Informationen Projektkoordination ACT4CAP27: Wageningen Social and Economic Research, Den Haag, NLKontakt: act4cap27@wur.nl | Website: <https://act4cap27.eu/> Projektlaufzeit: 1. März...

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Balazs, Katalin

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April 24, 2025 (v1) Presentation Open

Розвиток потенціалу та аналітичних інструментів для підтримки спільної аграрної політики після 2027 року (Development of capacities and analytical tools to support the Common Agricultural Policy after 2027)

Nikolyuk, Olga

This material was presented at the Zhytomyr Dialogue Event on April 24, 2025, hosted by the POLIDIH Digital Innovation Hub of the Polissia National University (PNU). Organized by ULEAD with Europe in Zhytomyr Oblast, the event aimed to inform community leaders about local...

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February 25, 2025 (final) Other Open

Press release: ACT4CAP27 Annual Consortium Meeting 2025

Wageningen University & Research ; Possessio Kft.

Rome, Italy – February 25-26, 2025 The ACT4CAP27 Annual Consortium Meeting 2025 is taking place at the University of Roma Tre, bringing together project partners to review progress and plan the next steps in supporting EU agri-food policies beyond 2027. The meeting focuses on...

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Uploaded on February 25, 2025

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February 13, 2025 (final) Journal article Open

Predicting policy funding allocation with Machine Learning

Caravaggio, Nicola

Abstract Allocating funds through competitive opportunities is a core tool of place-based development policies, and it can generate economic benefits and support the revitalisation of left-behind territories. By relying on Machine Learning techniques, this paper investigates the predictabil...

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Uploaded on February 16, 2025 | Published in: Socio-Economic Planning Sciences, 98, 102175, ISSN: 0038-0121, 2025.

 24

January 31, 2025 (final)

Presentation

 Open

Predicting EU Funding Success with Machine Learning

Caravaggio, Nicola

This material was presented by Cristina Vaquero-Piñeiro, representing the UNIROMA3 team within the ACT4CAP27 project, at the the XXIII Annual Workshop of the Società Italiana di Economia e Politica Industriale (SIEPI) on 31 January 2025 in Bologna. The study, co-authored with...

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January 16, 2025 (final version)

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 Open

Розвиток потенціалу та аналітичних інструментів для підтримки спільної аграрної політики після 2027 року (Capacity building and analytical tools to support the Common Agricultural Policy after 2027)

Nykylyuk, Olga

This material was presented at the forum "GREEN & DIGITAL POLISSIA: AGRICULTURE" on 16 January 2025 at the European Digital Innovation Hub "POLIDIH" at Polissya National University (Ukraine). The forum gathered farmers, entrepreneurs, and stakeholders from the Zhytomyr and...

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September 18, 2024 (final version)

Presentation

 Open

Scenario in AGMEMOD: Ukrainian Producers Separation

Pyvovar, Petro

This material was presented at the ACT4CAP27 WP6 Workshop on Modelling the Future of EU-Ukraine Relationship on 18 September 2024 organized by the Thünen Institute of Market Analysis (Germany), Wageningen Economic Research (Netherlands), and Polissia National Universi...

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Uploaded on December 7, 2024

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September 18, 2024 (final version)

Presentation

 Open

Ukraine in AGMEMOD and future assumptions regarding policies, demographics, macro economics, production capacities

Bogonos, Mariia; Nazarkina, Roksolana ; Nykylyuk, Olga; and 4 others

This material was presented at the ACT4CAP27 WP6 Workshop on Modelling the Future of EU-Ukraine Relationship on 18 September 2024 organized by the Thünen Institute of Market Analysis (Germany), Wageningen Economic Research (Netherlands), and Polissia National Universi...

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September 18, 2024 (final version)

Presentation

 Open

Current situation and implications of a Ukraine accession to the EU

JONGENEEL, Roel ; GONZALEZ, Ana

This material was presented at the ACT4CAP27 WP6 Workshop on Modelling the Future of EU-Ukraine Relationship on 18 September 2024 organized by the Thünen Institute of Market Analysis (Germany), Wageningen Economic Research (Netherlands), and Polissia National Universi...

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November 25, 2024 (final version)

Project deliverable

 Open

Deliverable D7.5 Policy brief: Advancing Capacity & Analytical Tools for Supporting Common Agricultural Policies Post-2027

Balázs, Katalin

Deliverable D7.5 Policy brief: Advancing Capacity & Analytical Tools for Supporting Common Agricultural Policies Post-2027 2 December 2024 This the first in the series of policy briefs in the ACT4CAP27 project. This policy brief is addressing the urgent need for advanced tools to guide t...

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Uploaded on December 6, 2024

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March 18, 2024 (final)

Other

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Press release: Launch of the ACT4CAP27project

Wageningen University & Research ; POSSESSIO Kft.

Press release: Launch of the ACT4CAP27project ACT4CAP27 Horizon EU project: Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027 18 March 2024 A new project entitled the ACT4CAP27 Project funded under Horizon Europe is launche...

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APPENDIX 5 PROJECT LEAFLET

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.15655760](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655760)

Expected results

- Novel food systems framework, holistic indicators & gap analysis to guide development of agri-food models.
- Modular Toolbox for Sustainable Food System Policy Modelling to support agricultural modelling capacity of EU member states.
- Assessment of potential future agri-food policy options.
- Monitoring and projecting environmental, social & economic indicators of the EU food system.
- New generation of agri-food system modellers & EU wide community of model practitioners.
- Dissemination & Stakeholder Platform bringing together food system experts and EU modellers and analysts providing them with an open access to the ACT4CAP27 Portal.
- Impact of agricultural policy analysis on performance of the EU food system fostered through a programme of engagement with key stakeholders at regional, country and EU levels.
- ACT4CAP27 Interactive Roadmap with transition narratives and pathways to achieve medium- to long-term sustainable food systems in the EU.

Partners

Project coordination

Siemen van Berkum, Project Coordinator
Hans van Meijl, Scientific Coordinator

Wageningen Social & Economic Research
The Hague, NL

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Project information on CORDIS

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101134874>

Project duration

03/2024 - 02/2029

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ACT4CAP27

Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

Funded by the European Union

Challenges in Policy Impact Assessment

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) stands as the European Union's cornerstone for supporting agriculture, ensuring food security, and driving rural development. Aligned with the objectives of the European Green Deal, encompassing the Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategy, the CAP plays a pivotal role in reshaping Europe's agri-food systems for sustainability.

In the evolving landscape of the European Green Deal, existing quantitative modeling tools face a monumental challenge in comprehensively addressing all components of the policy. The need to align with the ambitious goals of the Green Deal, including sustainability and biodiversity, demands a significant enhancement in thematic coverage.

Specific objectives

- DESIGNING a conceptual data and modelling framework to operationalize and better understand the determinants and indicators for an improved EU food system performance and ASSESSING policy impact.
- Developing an enhanced modular MODELLING Toolbox to quantify the transition to a sustainable EU food system and its contribution to societal goals.
- SAFEGUARDING the uptake and update of the integrated and modular toolbox and community building.
- PLATFORM for stakeholder interaction and dialogues – at different stages of the project

Support for evidence-based EU agri-food policies post-2027

ACT4CAP27 aims to enhance analytical capabilities, tools, and collaborative technical infrastructure within the policy modelling community.

The project adopts a comprehensive food system (FS) approach, focusing on building analytical capacity for the quantitative assessment of the impacts of upcoming agri-food policies on the economic, social (including health), environmental, and climate sustainability of food systems.

Through the identification of synergies, trade-offs, and linkages, the project enhances the effectiveness and efficiency of regulatory pathways, particularly in the context of ongoing shocks and disruptions across Europe and globally.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15655078

Erwartete Ergebnisse

- Neuartiger Rahmen für Lebensmittelsysteme, ganzheitliche Indikatoren und Lückenanalyse zur Unterstützung für die Weiterentwicklung von Agrar- und Lebensmittelsystemen.
- Modularer Werkzeugkasten für die Modellierung nachhaltiger Lebensmittelsysteme zur Unterstützung der landwirtschaftlichen Modellierungskapazitäten in den EU-Mitgliedsstaaten.
- Bewertung potenzieller zukünftiger Optionen der Agrar- und Lebensmittelpolitik.
- Monitoring und Projektion ökologischer, sozialer und wirtschaftlicher Indikatoren des EU-Lebensmittelsystems.
- Neue Generation von Modellierern für Agrar- und Lebensmittelsysteme und EU-weite Gemeinschaft von Modellierern.
- Verbreitungs- und Stakeholder-Plattform, die Experten für Lebensmittelsysteme mit EU-Modellierern und -Analysten zusammenbringt und ihnen offenen Zugang zum ACT4CAP27-Portal bietet.
- Auswirkungen der Analyse der Agrarpolitik auf die Leistung des EU-Lebensmittelsystems untermauert durch ein Programm zur Einbindung wichtiger Interessengruppen auf regionaler, nationaler und EU-Ebene.
- Interaktive ACT4CAP27-Roadmap mit transformativen Narrativen und Pfaden zur mittel- bis langfristigen Erreichung nachhaltiger Lebensmittelsysteme in der EU.

Partner

Projektkoordination

Siemen van Berkum, Projektkoordinator
Hans van Meijl, Wissenschaftlicher Koordinator

Wageningen Social & Economic Research,
Den Haag, NL

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<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101134874>

Projektlaufzeit
03/2024 - 02/2029

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Weiterentwicklung von Kapazitäten und Analyseinstrumenten zur Unterstützung der Gemeinsamen Agrarpolitik nach 2027

Finanziert von der Europäischen Union

Gefördert durch die Europäische Union, Horizon Europe Fördervereinbarung Nr. 101134874. Die geäußerten Ansichten und Meinungen sind ausschließlich die der Autoren und spiegeln nicht unbedingt die der Europäischen Union oder der Europäischen Kommission wider. Weder die Europäische Union noch die Förderbehörde können dafür verantwortlich gemacht werden.

Herausforderungen der Politikfolgenabschätzung

Die Gemeinsame Agrarpolitik (GAP) ist der Eckpfeiler der Europäischen Union zur Förderung der Landwirtschaft, der Ernährungssicherheit und der ländlichen Entwicklung. Im Einklang mit den Zielen des Green Deals der EU, der die Farm-to-Fork-Strategie und die Biodiversitätsstrategie umfasst, spielt die GAP eine zentrale Rolle bei der Gestaltung nachhaltiger Agrar- und Lebensmittelsysteme in der EU.

Im sich weiterentwickelnden Umfeld des Europäischen Green Deals stehen bestehende quantitative Modellierungsinstrumente vor der Herausforderung, alle Komponenten der Politik umfassend zu berücksichtigen. Die notwendige Ausrichtung auf die ehrgeizigen Ziele des Green Deals, einschließlich Nachhaltigkeit und Biodiversität, erfordert eine deutliche Erweiterung der thematischen Abdeckung.

Unterstützung einer evidenzbasierten EU-Agrar- und Lebensmittelpolitik nach 2027

ACT4CAP27 zielt darauf ab, die analytischen Fähigkeiten, Instrumente und die kollaborative technische Infrastruktur innerhalb der Politikmodellierergemeinschaft zu verbessern.

Das Projekt verfolgt einen umfassenden Lebensmittelsystemansatz und konzentriert sich auf den Aufbau analytischer Kapazitäten für die quantitative Bewertung der Auswirkungen künftiger Agrar- und Lebensmittelpolitik auf die wirtschaftliche, soziale (einschließlich gesundheitlicher), ökologische und klimatische Nachhaltigkeit von Lebensmittelsystemen.

Durch die Identifizierung von Synergien, Kompromissen und Zusammenhängen verbessert das Projekt die Wirksamkeit und Effizienz regulatorischer Verfahren, insbesondere im Kontext der anhaltenden Schocks und Störungen in Europa und weltweit.

Spezifische Ziele

- ENTWICKLUNG eines konzeptionellen Daten- und Modellierungsrahmens zur Operationalisierung und zum besseren Verständnis der Determinanten und Indikatoren für eine verbesserte Leistung des EU-Lebensmittelsystems sowie zur BEWERTUNG der politischen Auswirkungen.
- Entwicklung einer verbesserten modular aufgebauten MODELL-Toolbox zur Quantifizierung des Übergangs zu einem nachhaltigen EU-Lebensmittelsystem und seines Beitrags zu gesellschaftlichen Zielen.
- SICHERSTELLEN der Nutzung und Aktualisierung der integrierten, modularen Toolbox und Aufbau einer Gemeinschaft.
- PLATFORM zur Interaktion und Dialog mit Stakeholdern – in verschiedenen Projektphasen.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15655340

Várható eredmények

- ✔ **Új értékelési keretrendszer**
Holisztikus mutatókkal és hiányelemzéssel segíti a fenntartható agrár-élelmiszerrendszerek modellezését.
- ✔ **Moduláris eszköztár a szakpolitikákhoz**
Segítséget nyújt az uniós tagállamoknak az élelmiszerrendszerek modellezésében és tervezésében.
- ✔ **Jövőbe mutató szakpolitikai forgatókönyvek**
Környezeti, társadalmi és gazdasági mutatók nyomon követése és előrejelzése 2050-ig és azon túl.
- ✔ **Modellezői közösségépítés**
Európai szakértők hálózatának kiépítése a fenntartható élelmiszerrendszerekért.
- ✔ **Nyitott tudásmegosztás**
Az ACT4CAP27 portál mindenki számára elérhetővé teszi a tudást és eszközöket.
- ✔ **Érdektelt felek bevonása**
Párbeszéd regionális, nemzeti és EU-szinten a politikák hatásainak erősítésére.
- ✔ **Interaktív ütemterv és forgatókönyvek**
Gyakorlati útmutató a fenntartható jövő felé vezető úthoz.

Partnerek

Projekt koordináció

Siemen van Berkum, projektkoordinátor
Hans van Meijl, tudományos koordinátor
Wageningen Társadalmi és Gazdasági Kutatóintézet, Hága, NL

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Projektinformációk a CORDIS-on

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Projekt időtartama

03/2024 - 02/2029

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Elemzési eszközök fejlesztése és modellezési kapacitás építése a 2027 utáni Közös Agrárpolitika támogatásához

Az Európai Unió támogatásával

Kihívások a szakpolitikai hatásvizsgálatban

A Közös Agrárpolitika (KAP) az Európai Unió alapjaira a mezőgazdaság támogatásában, az élelmiszerbiztonság biztosításában és a vidékfejlesztés előmozdításában. Az Európai Zöld Megállapodás – beleértve az "A termelőtől a fogyasztóig" és a Biológiai Sokféleség stratégiákat – célkitűzéseivel összhangban a KAP kulcs szerepet játszik Európa agrár-élelmiszer rendszereinek fenntarthatóságra való átalakításában.

Az Európai Zöld Megállapodás változó környezetében a meglévő kvantitatív modellezési eszközök hatalmas kihívással néznek szembe: nehézséget okoz számukra a szakpolitika minden elemének átfogó kezelése. A Zöld Megállapodás ambíciózus céljaival – köztük a fenntarthatósággal és a biológiai sokféleséggel – való összehangolás jelentős tematikus bővítést igényel.

Konkrét célkitűzések

- az EU élelmiszeri rendszerére vonatkozó koncepcionális adat- és modellezési keretrendszer MEGTERVEZÉSE.
- az élelmiszeri rendszer teljesítményének és szakpolitikai hatásainak az ÉRTEKELÉSÉRE alkalmas tényezők és mutatók meghatározása.
- Továbbfejlesztett moduláris MODELLEZÉSI Eszköztár kidolgozása a fenntartható uniós élelmiszer-rendszerre való átmenetre, különösen tekintettel a társadalmi célokhoz való hozzájárulás számszerűsítésére.
- Az adatok és modellezési keretrendszer használatának, frissítésének BIZTOSÍTÁSA.
- PLATFORM kialakítása az érdekelt felekkel - a projekt különböző szakaszaiban - folytatott interakcióhoz és párbeszédre.

Az EU agrár-élelmiszerpolitikájának szakmai támogatása 2027 után

Az ACT4CAP27 célja, hogy megerősítse az elemzési kapacitásokat, a szakpolitikai modellezéshez szükséges eszköztárat és az együttműködésen alapuló technikai infrastruktúrát az érintett szakmai közösségekben.

A projekt egy **átfogó élelmiszerrendszer-megközelítést** alkalmaz, melynek fókuszában olyan kvantitatív elemzési képességek fejlesztése áll, amelyek lehetővé teszik a közlegő agrár-élelmiszerpolitikák hatásainak átfogó értékelését – gazdasági, társadalmi (beleértve az egészséget), környezeti és klímavédelmi szempontból egyaránt.

A projekt célja továbbá, hogy azonosítsa a szinergiákat, ellentmondásokat és összefüggéseket, ezáltal segítve a szakpolitikai szabályozási utak **hatékonyágának és eredményességének növelését** – különösen a jelenlegi, Európát és a világot egyaránt érintő sokkok és zavarok közepette.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15655467

Risultati attesi

- Nuova concettualizzazione dei sistemi alimentari, indicatori sintetici e analisi dei fabbisogni per guidare lo sviluppo dei modelli agroalimentari.
- Toolbox modulare di supporto agli stati membri dell'UE nel modellare politiche per sistemi alimentari sostenibili orientati a supportare la capacità di modellazione.
- Valutazione di futuri interventi di politica economica.
- Monitoraggio e proiezione di indicatori ambientali, sociali ed economici del sistema agroalimentare dell'UE.
- Formazione di nuovi giovani esperti in modellazione come parte di una comunità di esperti in tutta l'UE.
- Piattaforma di comunicazione e disseminazione per connettere esperti di sistemi agroalimentari, di modellazione e di valutazione dell'UE, fornendo loro un accesso aperto al portale ACT4CAP27.
- Valutazione dell'impatto delle politiche agricole sui risultati del sistema alimentare dell'UE tramite un programma di partecipazione attiva delle principali parti interessate a livello regionale, nazionale e dell'UE.
- Roadmap ACT4CAP27 interattiva e narrante per i per raggiungere sistemi alimentari sostenibili a medio e lungo termine nell'UE.

Partner

Coordinamento del progetto

Siemen van Berkum, Coordinatore del progetto
Hans van Meijl, Coordinatore scientifico
Wageningen Social & Economic Research
L'Aia, NL

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Durata del progetto
03/2024 - 02/2029

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Competenze e strumenti analitici per supportare la Politica Agricola Comune dopo il 2027

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Sfide nella valutazione di impatto delle politiche

La Politica Agricola Comune (PAC) è lo strumento principale dell'Unione Europea per sostenere il settore agricolo, garantire la sicurezza alimentare e guidare lo sviluppo delle aree rurali. In linea con gli obiettivi del Green Deal europeo, declinati nella strategia Farm to Fork e la strategia sulla Biodiversità, la PAC svolge un ruolo fondamentale nel tentativo di rimodellare la sostenibilità dei sistemi agroalimentari europei.

Nel contesto del Green Deal Europeo, gli strumenti di modellazione quantitativa esistenti sono chiamati ad affrontare una sfida di adattamento alle diverse componenti della politica. La necessità di allinearsi agli ambiziosi obiettivi del Green Deal, tra cui sostenibilità e biodiversità, richiede un significativo miglioramento della copertura tematica dei modelli.

Obiettivi specifici

- PROGETTARE un quadro concettuale di riferimento per dati e modelli con l'obiettivo di identificare le determinanti e gli indicatori che possono contribuire a migliorare la performance del sistema alimentare dell'UE e VALUTARE l'impatto delle politiche.
- Sviluppare un toolbox di MODELLIZZAZIONE modulare adatto a studiare la transizione dell'UE verso un sistema agroalimentare sostenibile e il suo contributo per la società.
- GARANTIRE l'adozione e l'aggiornamento del toolbox integrato, e dei diversi moduli, e la creazione di una comunità di esperti.
- Costruire una PIATTAFORMA per l'interazione e i dialoghi con le parti interessate nelle diverse fasi del progetto.

Supporto per politiche agroalimentari post-2027 basate su evidenze empiriche

ACT4CAP27 mira a migliorare le capacità analitiche, gli strumenti e la collaborazione all'interno di una comunità di esperti in modellazione delle politiche.

Il progetto adotta un approccio integrato guardando all'intero sistema agroalimentare e concentrandosi sul miglioramento delle competenze di valutazione quantitativa degli impatti delle politiche agroalimentari sulla sostenibilità economica, sociale (inclusa la salute), ambientale e climatica dei sistemi agroalimentari.

Identificando sinergie e trade-off, il progetto mira a migliorare l'efficacia e l'efficienza dei percorsi istituzionali di regolamentazione, con particolare attenzione all'attuale contesto di instabilità europea e globale.

WP7 Coinvolgimento degli attori interessati e disseminazione

- Pilastro 1 PROGETTARE e VALUTARE sistemi alimentari sostenibili in UE**
 - WP1 Contesto di riferimento e strumenti analitici gap analysis
 - WP5 Valutazione delle politiche agroalimentari dell'UE dopo il 2027
- Pilastro 2 MODELLIZZAZIONE sistemi alimentari sostenibili in UE**
 - WP2 Considerazione della sostenibilità economica, sociale, ambientale e climatica dei sistemi alimentari
 - WP3 Modelli per rappresentare il sistema agroalimentare e le sue politiche
- Pilastro 3 GARANTIRNE l'utilizzo, l'aggiornamento dei dati e del quadro di modellazione**
 - WP4 Portale con i dati e i modelli ACT4CAP27
 - WP6 Gestione e sviluppo delle infrastrutture delle capacità

WP8 Gestione e Coordinamento

Analisi del quadro concettuale (left), **Analisi dei criteri di un sistema alimentare sostenibile** (right), **Analisi della progettazione di studi di scenario** (right), **Analisi dei risultati dello scenario del modello** (right), **Gestione e supporto alle decisioni** (left)

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.1565532](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1565532)

Verwachte resultaten

- Nieuw kader voor voedselsystemen, holistische indicatoren en gap-analyse om de ontwikkeling van agrovoedingsmodellen te begeleiden.
- Modulaire toolbox voor het modelleren van beleid voor duurzame voedselsystemen ter ondersteuning van de landbouw modelleringscapaciteit van EU-lidstaten.
- Beoordeling van mogelijke toekomstige beleidsopties voor voedselsystemen.
- Monitoring en projectie van milieu-, sociale en economische indicatoren van het EU-voedselsysteem.
- Nieuwe generatie modellers en EU-brede gemeenschap van modelbeoefenaars van agrovoedingsmodellen.
- Disseminatie- en stakeholdersplatform dat experts op het gebied van voedselsystemen en modellers en analisten samenbrengt en hen open toegang biedt tot de ACT4CAP27-portal.
- Impact van landbouwbeleidsanalyse op de prestaties van het EU-voedselsysteem vergroten middels een programma dat de betrokkenheid met belangrijke belanghebbenden op regionaal, nationaal en EU-niveau bevordert.
- ACT4CAP27 Interactieve routekaart met transitieverhaten en -paden om op de middellange tot lange termijn duurzame voedselsystemen in de EU te realiseren.

Partners

Projectcoördinatie

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Hans van Meijl, Wetenschappelijk Coördinator
Wageningen Sociaal & Economisch Onderzoek
Den Haag, NL

Bezoek onze website & Zenodo-pagina

www.act4cap27.eu
<https://zenodo.org/communities/act4cap27-eu-project/>

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Projectinformatie op CORDIS

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101134874>

Projectduur

03/2024 - 02/2029

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ACT4CAP27

Bevordering van de capaciteit en analytische instrumenten ter ondersteuning van het Gemeenschappelijk Landbouwbeleid na 2027

Gefinancierd door de Europese Unie

Uitdagingen bij beleidseffectbeoordeling

Het Gemeenschappelijk Landbouwbeleid (GLB) is de hoeksteen van de Europese Unie voor de ondersteuning van landbouw, het waarborgen van voedselzekerheid en het stimuleren van plattelandsontwikkeling. In lijn met de doelstellingen van de Europese Green Deal, die de Farm to Fork- en Biodiversity Strategy omvat, speelt het GLB een cruciale rol bij het hervormen van de Europese agrovoedingsystemen voor duurzaamheid.

In het veranderende landschap van de Europese Green Deal staan de huidige kwantitatieve modelleringstools voor een grote uitdaging bij het uitgebreid analyseren van alle componenten van het beleid. De noodzaak om aan te sluiten bij de ambitieuze doelstellingen van de Green Deal, waaronder duurzaamheid en biodiversiteit, vereist een aanzienlijke verbetering van de thematische dekking van de modellen.

Specifieke doelstellingen

- ONTWERPEN van een conceptueel data- en modelleringkader om de determinanten en indicatoren voor gewenste uitkomsten van het EU-voedselsysteem te operationaliseren en beter te begrijpen, en de gevolgen van het beleid te kunnen BEPALEN.
- Ontwikkelen van een verbeterde modulaire MODELLEERINGS toolbox om de transitie naar een duurzaam EU-voedselsysteem en de bijdrage ervan aan maatschappelijke doelen te kwantificeren.
- VEILIGSTELLEN van het gebruik en actualiseren van de geïntegreerde en modulaire toolbox en community building.
- PLATFORM voor stakeholderinteractie en dialogen – in verschillende fasen van het project.

Ondersteuning voor op bewijs gebaseerd EU-agrovoedingsbeleid na 2027

ACT4CAP27 is gericht op het verbeteren van analytische mogelijkheden, tools en collaboratieve technische infrastructuur binnen de beleids-modelleringsgemeenschap. Het project hanteert een uitgebreide voedselsysteembenadering, met de focus op het opbouwen van analytische capaciteit voor de kwantitatieve beoordeling van de impact van toekomstig agrovoedselbeleid op de economische, sociale (inclusief gezondheid), milieu- en klimaatduurzaamheid van voedselsystemen. Door de identificatie van synergieën, afwegingen en verbanden verbetert het project de effectiviteit en efficiëntie van regelgevende paden, met name in de context van aanhoudende schokken en verstoringen in Europa en wereldwijd.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15655609

Förväntade resultat

- Ett ramverk för livsmedelssystemet, holistiska indikatorer och en behovsanalys som vägleder modellering av jordbruk och livsmedel.
- En modulär verktygslåda för modellering av hållbara livsmedelssystem, som stödjer medlemsländernas förmåga till jordbruksmodellering.
- Bedömning av möjliga framtida alternativ för jordbruks- och livsmedelspolitiken.
- Övervakning och prognostisering av miljömässiga, sociala & ekonomiska indikatorer i EU:s livsmedelssystem.
- En ny generation modellörer inom jordbruks- och livsmedelssystem och ett EU-omfattande nätverk av modellärvandare.
- En plattform för resultatspridning och intressenter som samlar experter inom livsmedelssystem, modellörer och analytiker, och ger dem öppen tillgång till ACT4CAP27-portalen.
- Analyser av jordbrukspolitiken som påverkar hur EU:s livsmedelssystem fungerar, genom samverkan med centrala intressenter på regional, nationell och EU-nivå.
- En interaktiv färdplan som beskriver vägar för att uppnå hållbara livsmedelssystem på medellång till lång sikt i EU.

Partners

Projektkoordinering

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Projektets varaktighet

03/2024 - 02/2029

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Förbättra kapacitet och analytiska verktyg för att stödja den gemensamma jordbrukspolitiken efter 2027

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Finansieras av Europeiska unionen

Utmaningar i policykonsekvensbedömning

Den gemensamma jordbrukspolitiken (CAP) är den Europeiska unionens hörsten för att stödja jordbruket, säkerställa livsmedelssäkerhet och främja landsbygdsutveckling. I linje med målen för den europeiska gröna given, som omfattar "från jord till bord"-strategin och strategin för biologisk mångfald, spelar CAP en avgörande roll för omställningen till ett mer hållbart europeiskt jordbruks- och livsmedelssystem.

De befintliga kvantitativa modelleringsverktygen står inför en enorm utmaning på ett heltäckande sätt hantera med de förändringar i politiken som den europeiska gröna given innebär. Behovet av att anpassa sig till de ambitiösa målen, inklusive mål för hållbarhet och biologisk mångfald, gör att modelleringen av dessa teman måste förbättras avsevärt.

Specifika mål

- UTFORMA ett konceptuellt ramverk för data och modellering. Ramverket används för att operationalisera och bättre förstå viktiga faktorer och indikatorer som påverkar hur väl EU:s livsmedelssystem fungerar, samt för att UTVÄRDERA effekterna av politiken.
- Utveckla en förbättrad modulär MODELLERINGS-verktygslåda för att kvantifiera omställningen till ett hållbart livsmedelssystem i EU och dess bidrag till samhälleliga mål.
- SÄKERSTÄLLA införande och uppdatering av den integrerade och modulära verktygslådan samt bygga upp en gemenskap av modellörer.
- Skapa en PLATTFORM för samverkan och dialog med intressenter – i olika skeden av projektet.

Stöd till evidensbaserad EU-politik för jordbruk och livsmedel efter 2027

ACT4CAP27 syftar till att förbättra analytiska möjligheter, verktyg och teknisk infrastruktur för samarbete inom en gemenskap för policymodellering.

Projektet studerar livsmedelssystem med ett omfattande angreppssätt. Fokus ligger på att bygga analytisk kapacitet för att göra kvantitativa bedömningar av effekten av kommande jordbruks- och livsmedelspolitik på ekonomiska, sociala, hälsorelaterade, miljömässiga och klimatomfattiga dimensioner av livsmedelssystemets hållbarhet.

Genom att identifiera synergier, målkonflikter och samband, bidrar projektet till ökad effektivitet i utvecklingen av regelverk, särskilt mot bakgrund av de pågående chocker och störningar som påverkar Europa och världen.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15655672

Очікувані результати

- Нова структура продовольчих систем, цілісні індикатори та аналіз прогалин для керування розробкою агропродовольчих моделей.
- Модульний інструментарій для моделювання політики сталих продовольчих систем, що підтримує спроможність країн-членів ЄС у сфері аграрного моделювання.
- Оцінка потенційних майбутніх варіантів агропродовольчої політики.
- Моніторинг та проектування екологічних, соціальних та економічних показників продовольчої системи ЄС.
- Нове покоління моделювальників агропродовольчих систем та загальноєвропейська спільнота практиків у сфері моделювання.
- Платформа розповсюдження інформації та взаємодії із зацікавленими сторонами, яка об'єднує експертів у сфері продовольчих систем, моделювальників і аналітиків ЄС, забезпечуючи їм відкритий доступ до порталу ACT4CAP27.
- Посилення впливу аналізу аграрної політики на ефективність продовольчої системи ЄС через програму взаємодії з ключовими зацікавленими сторонами на регіональному, національному та загальноєвропейському рівнях.
- Інтерактивна дорожня карта ACT4CAP27 із сценаріями переходу та шляхами досягнення сталих продовольчих систем у середньо- та довгостроковій перспективі в ЄС.

Партнери

Координація проекту

Сімен ван Беркум, координатор проекту
Ганс ван Мейл, науковий координатор

Соціальні та економічні дослідження
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Тривалість проекту
03/2024 - 02/2029

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Розвиток потенціалу аналітичних інструментів для підтримки спільної сільськогосподарської політики після 2027 року

Фінансується Європейським Союзом. Грантова угода Horizon Europe Nr. 101134874. Висловлені погляди та думки належать лише авторам і не обов'язково відображають політику Європейського Союзу, ні Європейської Комісії, ні Європейський Союз, ні орган, що надає гранти, не можуть нести за них відповідальності.

Фінансується Європейським Союзом

Проблеми в оцінці впливу політики

Спільна аграрна політика (САР) є наріжним каменем Європейського Союзу у підтримці сільського господарства, забезпеченні продовольчої безпеки та сприянні розвитку сільських територій. Відповідно до ший Європейського зеленого курсу, включаючи стратегію «Від ферми до вилка» та біорізноманіття, САР відіграє ключову роль у трансформації агропродовольчих систем Європи задля їхньої сталості.

У контексті динамічних змін, пов'язаних із Європейським зеленим курсом, наявні кількісні моделювальні інструменти стикаються з величезним викликом – необхідністю комплексного охоплення всіх аспектів цієї політики. Для відповідності амбіним цілям Зеленого курсу, зокрема щодо сталого розвитку та збереження біорізноманіття, потрібно значно розширити тематичне охоплення моделювання.

Конкретні цілі

- РОЗРОБКА концептуальної платформи даних і моделювання для практичного застосування та кращого розуміння чинників і показників, що сприяють підвищенню ефективності продовольчої системи ЄС, а також ОЦІНКА впливу політики.
- Створення вдосконаленого модульного ІНСТРУМЕНТАРІЮ МОДЕЛЮВАННЯ для кількісної оцінки переходу до сталі продовольчої системи ЄС та її внеску в досягнення суспільних цілей.
- ЗАБЕЗПЕЧЕННЯ впровадження та оновлення інтервованого та модульного інструментарію, а також розбудова спільноти.
- ПЛАТФОРМА для взаємодії та діалогу зацікавлених сторін – на різних етапах проекту.

WP7 Залучення зацікавлених сторін та поширення інформації

Огляд концептуальна основа

Стовп 1 ПРОЕКТУВАННЯ та ОЦІНКА продуктових ланцюгів ЄС

WP1 Концептуальні основи та аналіз недоліків аналітичних інструментів

WP6 Оцінка агропродовольчої політики Європейського Союзу після 2027 року

Огляд метрики продуктивних систем

Стовп 2 МОДЕЛЮВАННЯ продуктових ланцюгів ЄС

WP2 Висвітлення економічної, соціальної, екологічної та кліматичної стійкості продовольчих систем

WP3 Структури моделей для представлення агропродовольчих системи та політики

Огляд дизайн сценарних досліджень

Стовп 3 ЗАБЕЗПЕЧЕННЯ впровадження та оновлення даних і платформ для моделювання

WP4 Портал даних і моделей ACT4CAP27

WP5 Інфраструктура моделювання та формування потенціалу

Дорожня карта та підтримка рішень

Огляд результати моделювання сценаріїв

WP8 Управління та координація

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Фінансується Європейським Союзом

APPENDIX 6 PRESS RELEASES

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PRESS RELEASE

Advancing Capacity and Analytical Tools for Supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

March 18, 2024

A new project entitled the ACT4CAP27 Project funded under Horizon Europe is launched to providing continuous support for evidence-based EU agri-food policies post 2027 aligning with the objectives of the European Green Deal.

Challenges in Policy Impact Assessment

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) stands as the European Union's cornerstone for supporting agriculture, ensuring food security, and driving rural development. Aligned with the objectives of the European Green Deal, encompassing the Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategy, the CAP plays a pivotal role in reshaping Europe's agri-food systems for sustainability.

In the evolving landscape of the European Green Deal, existing quantitative modelling tools face a huge challenge in comprehensively addressing all components of the policy. The need to align with the ambitious goals of the Green Deal, including sustainability and biodiversity, demands a significant enhancement in thematic coverage.

Enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency of regulatory pathways

The project aims to enhance analytical capabilities, tools, and collaborative technical infrastructure within the policy modelling community. This effort is directed towards providing continuous support for ex-ante analyses of EU agri-food policies post 2027 aligning with the objectives of the European Green Deal. The project adopts a comprehensive food system approach.

"We need to simultaneously look at the economic, social (including health), environmental, and climate sustainability of food systems. By taking a holistic view on the policy landscape and through the identification of synergies, trade-offs, and linkages, the project will enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of regulatory pathways, particularly in the context of ongoing shocks and disruptions across Europe and globally." – explains Siemen van Berkum, coordinator of the ACT4CAP27 project and senior researcher at Wageningen Economic Research.

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PRESS RELEASE

Assessing policy impacts, guiding policymakers

The objective is to assess both short-term and long-term policy impacts on the EU's agri-food systems, providing evidence-based knowledge crucial for designing agri-food policies post-2027. The project goes beyond modelling and tools; it launches an Interactive Roadmap designed to guide EU, national, and regional policymakers. This tool facilitates informed decision-making by helping policymakers weigh up policy objectives towards more sustainable outcomes.

ACT4CAP brings together 13 research institutions from eight EU countries, Ukraine, the UK, and builds on established modelling tools that are used to predict the impacts of climate, agricultural, and forestry policies, at the local, national, and regional levels.

Project kick-off in the Hague

At the kick-off meeting, hosted by Wageningen Economic Research between 18 and 19 March 2024, the partners discuss how the project can address current challenges to policymakers in the EU and draw up a road map for the first year of the project.

To ensure that the project meets the EU's policy needs in the short- and long-term, representatives of the European Commission, as well as noted experts in agricultural policy and impact assessment participate in the kick-off meeting. An important point on the agenda is to discuss how recent developments may impact on the proposed research agenda.

"European agriculture faces enormous challenges. The impact of European agriculture on the environment, biodiversity and climate change (and vice versa) is becoming increasingly visible. The COVID pandemic and the Ukraine crisis led to significant disruptions in international food markets, and increasing geopolitical tensions in the world could affect trade relations. To address the adverse long-term trends impacting EU agriculture, it is imperative to enact substantial policy changes in the agricultural sector. However, policymakers and opinion leaders often do not have enough information to properly assess the policy options for their country. As a result, they miss the opportunity to identify, design and implement policy actions that can best avoid short- and long-term risks and seize opportunities." – concludes Hans van Meijl, ACT4CAP27 scientific coordinator and chief economist at Wageningen Economic Research.

Further information

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Advancing Capacity and Analytical Tools for Supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

Rome, Italy – February 25-26, 2025

ACT4CAP27 Annual Consortium Meeting to Shape Future Agri-Food Policy Analysis

PRESS RELEASE

The ACT4CAP27 Annual Consortium Meeting 2025 is taking place at the University of Roma Tre, bringing together project partners to review progress and plan the next steps in supporting EU agri-food policies beyond 2027. The meeting focuses on strengthening analytical tools, refining research methodologies, and fostering collaboration among partners.

Challenges in Policy Impact Assessment

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) stands as the European Union's cornerstone for supporting agriculture, ensuring food security, and driving rural development. Aligned with the objectives of the European Green Deal, encompassing the Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategy, the CAP plays a pivotal role in reshaping Europe's agri-food systems for sustainability.

In the evolving landscape of the European Green Deal, existing quantitative modelling tools face a huge challenge in comprehensively addressing all components of the policy. The need to align with the ambitious goals of the Green Deal, including sustainability and competitiveness, calls for a major enhancement in the thematic coverage of these tools.

Advancing Agricultural Policy Research

ACT4CAP27 is a European research initiative aimed at improving the analytical capacity needed for policy evaluation in the agri-food sector. By enhancing modelling frameworks, expanding databases, and integrating different assessment modules, the project supports evidence-based policymaking in line with the European Green Deal and future agricultural policy developments. ACT4CAP brings together 13 research institutions from eight EU countries, Ukraine, the UK, and builds on established modelling tools that are used to predict the impacts of climate, agricultural, and forestry policies, at the local, national, and regional levels.

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Meeting Agenda Highlights

The meeting will begin with a review of recent policy developments related to CAP post-2027, followed by updates on the project's conceptual framework and ongoing research activities. Discussions will focus on modelling gaps, policy scenarios, and early findings from the project's fast-track scenario analysis. A series of technical sessions will provide an opportunity to discuss different assessment modules. These include health and environmental impact assessments, as well as socio-economic evaluations of agricultural policies. Participants will examine how these modules contribute to a comprehensive understanding of food systems and policy outcomes.

The second day will focus on innovations in modeling, covering topics such as input use in agricultural production, changing consumer preferences, food value chains, and policy analysis related to CAP and the Green Deal. The discussions will explore how these elements can be better integrated into the project's analytical framework. The meeting will also address stakeholder engagement strategies and communication efforts to ensure that project findings reach relevant policymakers and stakeholders. The discussions will conclude with an overview of the roadmap leading to the interim project report, due in August 2025.

This meeting will provide an opportunity for partners to align their efforts, clarify upcoming deliverables, and refine methodologies to support EU agricultural policy discussions. The insights gained will contribute to further strengthening the tools and approaches used in ACT4CAP27.

Further information

ACT4CAP27 Project coordination:
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Partners

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Sustainable Agriculture: A Cornerstone of Europe's Economic Prosperity and Strategic Security

Horizon Europe projects ACT4CAP27, BrightSpace, &
LAMASUS release joint perspective paper offering new
insights for the future of EU agri-food policy

July 24, 2025

The three Horizon Europe research projects — LAMASUS, BrightSpace, and ACT4CAP27 — launched a joint perspective paper entitled:

"Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security – An economic modellers' perspective."

This joint publication provides a timely contribution to the ongoing debate on the future of agriculture and food systems in Europe. It emphasises that a **sustainable agricultural sector is not only essential for achieving environmental goals but is also central to ensuring economic resilience, food security, and broader societal well-being across the EU.**

Drawing on the combined expertise of economic modellers and policy analysts from across Europe, the paper sets out how scientific insights can support more coherent, evidence-based agricultural policymaking in the years ahead — particularly in the context of the **post-2027 Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)** and the European Commission's **Vision for Agriculture and Food**.

Five Priority Action Areas

The authors highlight **five Priority Action Areas (PAAs)** where action is urgently needed to support a thriving and sustainable EU agricultural sector:

- PAA1. Fostering income and resilience through result-based policies that integrate economic and environmental performance.**
- PAA2. Integrated nutrient management to enhance strategic autonomy.**
- PAA3. Enhancing the agrifood sector competitiveness and food security through level-playing field trade agreements.**
- PAA4. Strengthening innovation leadership in the new bioeconomy.**
- PAA5. Democratizing digitalization to ensure agricultural sector attractiveness and technological innovation.**

These priority areas reflect both short-term policy needs and longer-term structural challenges. They also offer opportunities for the EU to strengthen its position as a global leader in sustainable agriculture.

"Realizing the full contribution of the agricultural sector to economic prosperity, food security and environmental sustainability requires both innovations and policies that foster synergies between the public and private sectors and different policy objectives."

Dr. Petr Havlík, Deputy Director, Energy, Climate, and Environment Programme, IIASA
Scientific coordinator of LAMASUS and lead co-author of the perspective paper

Integrated Modelling for Better Policy

The paper demonstrates how advanced policy modelling tools — such as **CAPRI**, **GLOBIOM**, and **MAGNET** — can be used to evaluate trade-offs, anticipate systemic risks, and explore future scenarios. By combining economic, environmental, and social indicators, these models help decision-makers assess the impact of different policy options across the EU and beyond.

"ACT4CAP27, BrightSpace, and LAMASUS are uniquely positioned to contribute to the European Commission's Vision for Agriculture and Food by improving the tools and data that underpin EU policy. Our joint work helps close knowledge gaps and supports more forward-looking, coherent decision-making."

Prof. Hans van Meijl, Senior Researcher, Wageningen Social and Economic Research
Scientific coordinator of BrightSpace and ACT4CAP27, co-author of the perspective paper

The joint perspective paper is part of a broader commitment by the three Horizon Europe projects to support the European Commission's strategic agenda through robust scientific collaboration. It builds on the projects' ongoing engagement with policy stakeholders, including recent workshops, dialogues, and presentations at DG AGRI.

Access the perspective paper

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413131>

Contact

For media inquiries and further details, please reach out to our Joint Paper Communications Coordination Team:

Petr HAVLÍK, email: havlikpt@iiasa.ac.at

Further information

ACT4CAP27: Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027
<https://act4cap27.eu/> | <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101134874>

BrightSpace: Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space |
<https://brightspace-project.eu/> | <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060075>

LAMASUS: LAnd use and MAnagement modelling for SUSTainable governance |
<https://www.lamasus.eu/> | <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060423>

APPENDIX 9 INFOGRAPHIC POSTERS

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BIODIVERSITY FUTURES

HOW WILL CLIMATE POLICIES, BIODIVERSITY PROTECTION MEASURES,
& AGRICULTURAL TRANSFORMATIONS AFFECT LAND USE AND BIODIVERSITY?

MAIN OBJECTIVES

- Quantify biodiversity futures under various policy setups
- Compare models to assess uncertainty
- Develop a biodiversity assessment pipeline for policy planning

MODELLING FRAMEWORK

Economic & Land-Use Models

Models used
GLOBIOM,
CAPRI,
AGMEMOD,
MAGNET

Sectors covered
Agriculture,
Forestry,
Full Ecosystems

Downscaling Module

Provides high-resolution spatial data for biodiversity assessments

Biodiversity Modelling Tools

Utilizes tools like
ibis, ISDM &
PREDICTS
for biodiversity analysis

SCENARIOS EXPLORED

EXPECTED RESULTS

- Spatially explicit land cover data at 5 arcmin resolution under each scenario
- Biodiversity trajectories such as habitat suitability and biodiversity intactness under each scenario
- Agriculture and forestry markets impacts, and other related economic, socio-economic, and environmental indicators
- Improved understanding of results' uncertainties through intercomparison across models with different mechanisms

WHY IT MATTERS

- Provides insights into the interaction between agricultural policies, climate goals, & biodiversity conservation
- Supports the EU's vision for sustainable food systems & biodiversity restoration

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STRATEGIC DIALOGUE & COMMON AGRICULTURAL POLICY

HOW CAP STRATEGIC PLANS ALIGN WITH THE STRATEGIC DIALOGUE ON THE
FUTURE OF FARMING AND THE GREEN DEAL?

HOW AGRICULTURAL POLICIES CAN IMPROVE COMPETITIVENESS AND
ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY IN THE EU FARMING SECTOR?

MAIN OBJECTIVES

Assess CAP's Role - How can CAP contribute to:
Greenhouse Gas Mitigation, Animal Welfare Improvements,
Nutrient Management, Sustainable Diets, Pesticide Reduction,
Organic Farming Growth

Stakeholder Impact: How do these policy shifts impact:
Farmers: Costs, farming practices, compliance with new regulations
Policymakers: Informing decisions for CAP reforms
Consumers: Prices, food availability
Environmental Groups: Conservation and biodiversity targets

MODELLING FRAMEWORK

CAPRI

IFM-CAP

AGMEMOD

MAGNET

EXPECTED RESULTS

Farm-level impacts: Insight into how farmers' costs and
consumer prices could shift due to policy changes

Sustainability: Detailed analysis of the effectiveness of
CAP in making farming more environmentally
sustainable.

Economic Adjustments: Projections on how policy
adjustments affect farmer income and market prices

CONTACT US FOR MORE INFORMATION

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OPTIONS FOR THIS SCENARIO

A **GHG Mitigation Target**
- Reduce agriculture emissions by a target (ex.:20%).
- Adjust farming practices to shift CSP payments and align with climate-
friendly technologies.

B **Animal Welfare Standards**
- Apply animal welfare practices at farm, transport, & slaughter levels
- Shift more CSP payments towards welfare-focused interventions

C **Nutrient Management**
- Reduce mineral fertilizers (N, P, K) to tackle over-
fertilization and nutrient surpluses

D **Sustainable Diets**
- A shift towards the EAT Lancet diet
(25% of population by 2040)

E **Pesticide Reduction & Organic Farming**
- Reduce pesticide usage
- Expand organic farming through CAP measures

F **Agricultural Land Use**
- Impact of fallow land and non-productive areas on food production
- Link to eco-scheme payments

WHY IT MATTERS

Policy Relevance

These results will guide future CAP policies to ensure they effectively
balance economic and environmental goals, aligning with the EU
Green Deal and the Strategic Dialogue on the Future of Farming

Insights for Stakeholders

Farmers: Could face increased production costs and must adopt
new practices

Policymakers: Results can inform support measures for affected
stakeholders

Environmental Groups: Gain insights into how policies can reduce
environmental impact.

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HEALTH & NUTRITION

THE IMPACT OF A SUGAR TAX ON HEALTH AND NUTRITION

MAIN OBJECTIVES

- analyze the **impact of a sugar tax** on sugar intake and health outcomes
- explore **how different designs of the sugar tax** (e.g. SSB-only, broader food groups, ad-valorem vs. tiered based on sugar content) **influence outcomes**

WHY IT MATTERS POLICY RELEVANCE

- The **sugar tax** is a key policy for improving **public health** by reducing **sugar intake** and lowering the **environmental impact of diets**.
- Sugar substitution options vary across different products, influencing how the tax will affect production

STAKEHOLDER IMPACT

- Lower sugar demand** in countries with a sugar tax could lead to **higher net exports** of sugary products
- Improved health outcomes** will reduce health sector costs
- Environmental benefits** from healthier diets

Processing of primary commodities into food products

MODELLING FRAMEWORK – TOOLS USED

CAPRI
(agricultural model)

Health Module

Tools for linking market balance, food intake data, & elasticity estimates

EXPECTED RESULTS

- The sugar tax on **SSBs** will reduce sugar intake for some **consumer groups** more than others
- Health benefits** will vary across different groups, depending on their initial sugar consumption.
- More accurate results** will emerge by aggregating the health benefits of these groups instead of assuming an average reduction.
- Expanding the tax to other food groups offers **smaller benefits** compared to an SSB-only tax.

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UKRAINE'S POTENTIAL ACCESSION TO THE EU

MAIN OBJECTIVES

- Explore the **current situation and future implications** of Ukraine joining the EU.
- Understand the **effects on Ukraine & EU Member States**, particularly for farmers, markets, and policy

OPTIONS FOR SCENARIOS

- 1 CAP reform**
 - Improve targeting of Direct Payments
 - Rural Development Policy
- 2 Trade & Level Playing Field**
 - Level playing field between farms and Member States
 - Meeting EU's environmental & animal welfare standards
- 3 Ukraine after the conflict**
 - Available productive land & Damaging
 - Infrastructure repair and demand recovery
- 4 Macroeconomic, Demographic & Budget issues in Ukraine and EU**
 - GDP recovery, exchange rate
 - Migration (5 million people left Ukraine) & Labour force
 - EU budget constraints and Member State positions

MODELLING FRAMEWORK

AGMEMOD

CAPRI

MAGNET

WHY IT MATTERS

POLICY RELEVANCE

High geopolitical importance, **strengthening EU food security** and contributing to sustainability targets e.g., Green Deal, CAP

STAKEHOLDER IMPACT – EU FARMERS

Competitive pressure from Ukrainian farmers, especially in **grains, poultry, and apples sectors**

STAKEHOLDER IMPACT – POLICY MAKERS

Redesigning the CAP budget to meet the expectations of both **UA and EU farmers**

Managing challenges of **agroholding scale** in Ukraine

Ensuring a **level playing field of direct payments & adapting rural development policies**

STAKEHOLDER IMPACT – AGROFOOD INDUSTRY

Potential shifts in market dynamics for both **EU member states and Ukraine**.

EXPECTED RESULTS

Insights into the consequences of different Ukraine accession pathways for:

EU self-sufficiency and trade patterns

Agrifood product prices

Structural changes in product allocation across EU member states

Sustainability indicators

EU budget implications and allocation

CONTACT US FOR MORE INFORMATION

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APPENDIX 8 POLICY BRIEFS

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Advancing Capacity & Analytical Tools for Supporting Common Agricultural Policies Post-2027

25 November 2024

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POLICY BRIEF

Key messages

- Evidence-based policymaking under the EU's Better Regulation agenda demands being supported by advanced, holistic models that account for economic, environmental, and social factors.
- Policy innovation is needed to address climate, biodiversity, health, and equity concerns, requiring robust data, stakeholder alignment, and scenario analysis.
- Current policy-relevant scientific challenges include modelling the integrated environmental, social and economic impacts of CAP changes, allowing an improved understanding of potential trade-offs between policy objectives.
- ACT4CAP27 aims to enhance capacity and tools for analyzing the impacts of CAP reforms, focusing on sustainability, stakeholder engagement, and future-proofing EU agri-food policies.

What is the issue?

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is central to shaping Europe's agricultural sector, yet traditional policy analysis tools often fail to address its multifaceted impacts on sustainability, equity, and resilience.

As Europe gears up for the post-2027 CAP reform, challenges like climate change, biodiversity loss, income inequality, and rural demographics demand a systemic and forward-looking approach.

Current models often lack the granularity to reflect regional variations and the transformative impacts of emerging technologies, sustainability measures, and geopolitical shifts, including Ukraine's potential accession to the EU.

ACT4CAP27 is a European research project aiming to enhance analytical capabilities, tools, and collaborative technical infrastructure within the policy modelling community, to provide support for evidence-based EU agri-food policies post-2027.
| Project timeframe: 01/03/2024 – 28/02/2025
ACT4CAP27 Project coordination: Wageningen Economic Research, The Hague, NL | Contact: act4cap27@wur.nl
| www.act4cap27.eu | linkedin.com/company/act4cap27.eu/project/ | Twitter: @ACT4CAP27 |

Advancing Capacity & Analytical Tools for Supporting Common Agricultural Policies Post-2027

25 November 2024

Funded by the European Union
GA Nr. 101003075

POLICY BRIEF

Why is this important?

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) faces a critical juncture as Europe navigates pressing sustainability challenges. Effective CAP policies are essential to mitigate climate impacts, curb greenhouse gas emissions, and reverse biodiversity loss, all of which are vital to achieving Europe's environmental commitments.

At the same time, these policies must prioritize equity and inclusion, as ecological transitions may disproportionately burden smaller farms and vulnerable rural communities, deepening income disparities.

Moreover, Europe's global competitiveness is at stake, with emerging challenges such as geopolitical tensions, trade disruptions, and shifting consumer preferences toward sustainable diets demanding strategic adaptability.

A lack of robust, real-time data and comprehensive scenario planning hampers the effectiveness of policy interventions, limiting the CAP's ability to respond swiftly and effectively to a rapidly changing agri-food landscape.

What can policy makers do?

1. **Enhance Modelling and Data Integration.** Invest in tools that reflect regional, social, and economic nuances. Align CAP analysis with global frameworks like the IPCC's SSP scenarios for consistency and relevance. Incorporate real-time data on eco-scheme adoption, digital innovations, and agricultural education trends.
2. **Address Environmental and Social Goals.** Develop clear benchmarks for biodiversity, soil health, and emissions reductions. Integrate nature-based solutions and agroforestry into CAP frameworks. Address demographic challenges by incentivizing technology adoption among younger and older farmers.
3. **Support Strategic Dialogue and Stakeholder Engagement.** Use platforms like ACT4CAP27 to facilitate collaboration among policymakers, researchers, and farmers. Prioritize policies with broad stakeholder support, including innovative payments for ecosystem services and sustainable diets. Expand scenario analysis to include geopolitical factors, such as Ukraine's accession and its impact on EU trade, standards, and sustainability goals.
4. **Reform Incentives and Payments.** Transition from area-based subsidies to results-driven payments aligned with environmental and climate targets. Introduce complementary measures, such as carbon taxes or eco-scheme rewards, to drive adoption of sustainable practices. Address trade-offs in policy coherence (e.g. reducing sugar subsidies while considering consumer taxation impacts).
5. **Promote Knowledge Transfer and Innovation.** Enhance agricultural education and training, focusing on digitalization and sustainability. Foster knowledge-sharing networks between current EU states and potential new members like Ukraine. Support research on alternative farming practices, such as organic farming, green fertilizers, and digital solutions.

References and further reading

<https://act4cap27.eu>

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APPENDIX 9 ROLLUP BANNER

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